

Philippine Christian University

Institute of Philosophy and Religious Studies

**SOWING THE SEEDS OF FAITH: TOWARDS DEVELOPMENT
OF A WESLEYAN IDENTITY OF CHURCH PLANTING
MISSION CURRICULUM**

A Dissertation
Presented to the
Faculty of Graduate School
Institute of Philosophy and Religious Studies

In Partial Fulfilment
of the Requirement for the Degree of
Doctor of Philosophy
major in Religious Studies

CESAR TAQUEBAN REYES JR.

2024

APPROVAL SHEET

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Religious Studies, this dissertation entitled **SOWING THE SEEDS OF FAITH: TOWARDS DEVELOPMENT OF A WESLEYAN IDENTITY OF CHURCH PLANTING MISSION CURRICULUM**, was prepared and submitted to the Graduate School of the Institute of Philosophy and Religious Studies of Philippine Christian University by **CESAR T. REYES JR.**, is at this moment recommended for acceptance and approval.

ADONIS ABELARD O. GOROSPE, PhD
Adviser

PANEL OF EXAMINERS

The committee on Oral Examination approved it on May 27, 2024, with a grade of *A*

REVELINO D. GARCIA, PhD
Chairman

[Signature]
GERVASIS KARUMATHY, PhD
Member

[Signature]
ENRIQUE C. RONQUILLO, PhD
Member

[Signature]
MARCELINO B. PADAMA, JR., PhD
Member

[Signature]
EDUARDO B. COPLITING, JR., PhD
Member

This was accepted and approved in partial fulfillment of the Doctor of Philosophy in Religious Studies degree requirements.

[Signature]
MARCELINO B. PADAMA, JR., PhD
Acting Director- IPRS

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iii

DEDICATION

The whole research and work are dedicated to God as an instrument to further His ministry through the United Methodist Church's church planting mission, which aims to reach and win more souls for His kingdom.

C.T.R.JR.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

It is with the highest honor of the researcher that he offers his humble and sincerest gratitude to God Almighty, who provided him with all that he needed to finish the whole study through Jesus Christ.

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Philippine Christian University

Institute of Philosophy and Religious Studies

v

To Northwest Philippines Annual Conference for helping the researcher through scholarship grants, data gathering, and the respondents who gave their time in providing their insights and experiences as church leaders;

To God be all the praises and glory, now and forever!

C.T.R.JR.

ABSTRACT

Title : SOWING THE SEEDS OF FAITH: TOWARDS DEVELOPMENT OF A WESLEYAN IDENTITY OF CHURCH PLANTING MISSION CURRICULUM

Researcher : CESAR T. REYES JR.

**Degree : Doctor of Philosophy
major in Religious Studies**

**Institution : Philippine Christian University
Taft Ave, Manila**

Adviser : Rev. Adonis Abelard O. Gorospe, PhD

Year : 2024

The United Methodist Church Northwest Philippines Annual Conference church planting mission program is challenged by numerous obstacles in implementing church-planting programs which undermines the efficacy of the church planting efforts and restricts the capacity to engage with other populations leading to this dissertation which aims to develop a church planting mission curriculum in Wesleyan identity to bridge the gap of theory and practice of church planting mission endeavors.

The dissertation utilized the Qualitative research design specifically the Grounded Theory method by Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1998) in determining the components of the curriculum. There were eighteen (18) respondents, where six (6) of them were lay leaders, and the rest were ordained elders with experiences as mission pastors. The grounded theory, "A Way Forward: PANAGMULA Church Planting

Philippine Christian University

Institute of Philosophy and Religious Studies

vii

Mission Curriculum," was structured in eight (8) main categories: Assessment Framework, Grounded Methodology, Church Planting Missiology, Missiological Identity, Strategic Planning and Implementation, Church Mission Dynamics Maximization, Ministry Area Analysis, and Navigating Impediments.

The output of this dissertation was to develop a proposed curriculum in Wesleyan identity to guide the church leaders in effectively establishing church planting mission programs to proclaim the gospel as well as address the needs of their communities, and being proactive in community engagements in a context-sensitive approach, as part of the Wesleyan identity.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page i
Approval Sheetii
Dedicationiii
Acknowledgmentiv
Abstract..... vi

CHAPTER

1 THE PROBLEM AND REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Introduction1
Background Of The Study.....2
Review of Related Literature3
Historical Development of Church Planting3
Church Planting in the Modern Era and Philippine Context.....4
Wesleyan Identity in Mission and Church Planting.....5
Curriculum Development for Church Planting5
United Methodist Church and Social Mission6
Synthesis of Literature Review7
Emergent Theoretical Framework.....9
Emergent Conceptual Framework.....10
Statement Of The Problem.....10
Significance Of The Study12
Scope And Limitations.....12
Definition Of Terms13

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design.....15
Population, Samples, and Sampling Technique16
Research Instrument.....16
Data Gathering Procedures.....17

3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

RQ 1. Demographic Profile.....21
RQ 2. Components of the Curriculum22
RQ 2.1 The Need.....22
 Main Category 1: Assessment Framework22
 Main Category 2: Grounded Methodology27

RQ 2.2 The Biblical and Theological Bases	34
Main Category 3: Church Planting Missiology.....	34
RQ 2.3 The Significance of the Wesleyan Identity.....	42
Main Category 4: Missiological Identity	42
RQ 2.4 The Practical Ways, Methods, and Strategies.....	49
Main Category 5: Strategic Planning and Implementation	49
Main Category 6: Church Mission Dynamics Maximization	56
Main Category 7: Ministry Area Analysis	62
RQ 2.5 The Challenges	69
Main Category 8: Navigating Impediments	69
RQ 3. Church Planting Mission Curriculum.....	75
Emerged Conceptual Framework.....	78
4 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	
Summary of Findings	85
Conclusion.....	89
Recommendation.....	90
REFERENCES.....	241
BIONOTE.....	261

List of Table

Table	Page
1 Demographic Profile	20

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure	Page
1 Emerged Conceptual Framework.....	10 & 78
2 Map of Northwest Philippines Annual Conference	13
3 Assessment Framework.....	22
4 Grounded Methodology	27
5 Church Planting Missiology.....	34
6 Missiological Identity.....	42
7 Strategic Planning and Implementation	49
8 Church Mission Dynamics	56
9 Ministry Area Analysis	62
10 Navigating Impediments	69

CHAPTER 1

THE PROBLEM AND REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

INTRODUCTION

The United Methodist Church (UMC) in the Philippines has been actively engaged in church-planting mission endeavors since the beginning of the Methodist movement in 1898 (History of the UMC in Asia, 2019) to spread the gospel and nurture disciples of Jesus Christ. The Baguio Episcopal Area (BEA) leadership of the Philippine Central Conference (PCC) provides the vision, mission, and objective to direct the mission programs of BEA (Torio, 2022). The PCC is divided into three Episcopal areas (Baguio Episcopal Area, Manila Episcopal Area, and Davao Episcopal Area), comprising 26 annual conferences (Imagining the Future: Philippines Context, 2021). The BEA consists of nine (9) annual conferences (Ocampo, 2022), one of which is the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference (NWPAC), composed of 118 local churches (Torio, 2019). Although the Episcopal Leadership makes an effort to offer mission programs, the execution of these initiatives, particularly the Church planting mission activities, relies on the annual conference, districts, and local church levels without contextualized guides, strategies, and methods (Torio, 2022). Despite the Church's diligent endeavors, it has encountered numerous obstacles in implementing church-planting programs due to the absence of a localized and contextualized curriculum to guide church workers and lay leaders engaged in mission activities related to establishing new churches. The NWPAC church planting mission program is challenged by this situation, which undermines the efficacy of the church planting efforts and restricts their capacity to engage with other populations.

This dissertation seeks to develop a Church Planting Mission Curriculum in Wesleyan Identity for the UMC Northwest Philippines Annual Conference that would bridge the gap between theology and practice, designed to cater to the unique socio-cultural needs of NWPAC. The study investigated (1) the need for developing a Church planting mission curriculum for the six (6) districts of the NWPAC according to their context, (2) the Biblical and Theological foundation of Church planting mission, (3) effective methods and strategies for imparting the Church Planting knowledge, and (4) practical implementation approaches for the Church planting mission curriculum within NWPAC. This contextualized curriculum will provide guidance, strategy, planning and implementation, training, and development for church leaders' Church planting mission program across the region.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The United Methodist Church's commitment to evangelism and church planting has a long tradition tracing back to the early church. The Great Commission (Matthew 28:18-20) serves as a cornerstone for these efforts, emphasizing Jesus' directive to "make disciples of all nations." The early church, led by apostles such as Paul, embraced this mission by traveling, preaching, and establishing faith communities across various regions, as recorded in the Book of Acts. The church's identity and its spread were largely driven by this commitment to evangelism, serving as a template for modern mission practices.

Within the Philippine context, church planting began with Catholic missionaries in the 16th century and expanded with Protestant missions in the 19th century. Despite these longstanding traditions, there remains a growing need to develop an approach to church

planting that is contextualized for the unique cultural landscape of the Philippines, particularly in regions like NWPAC where specific socio-economic and geographic challenges impact mission work. Thus, developing a Church Planting Mission Curriculum in Wesleyan Identity is essential to support church leaders in overcoming these obstacles and effectively engaging in church planting in NWPAC.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Historical Development of Church Planting

Church planting served as a foundational mission since the early days of Christianity, as commanded by Jesus through the Great Commission (Matthew 28:18-20), which calls believers to "make disciples of all nations." This mission is evident in the apostolic journeys, where the early church spread rapidly through preaching and establishing faith communities. Paul's extensive travels documented in the New Testament—covering regions of Asia Minor and Europe are examples of this evangelistic approach, demonstrating the essential need for follow-up and discipleship in church planting efforts (Acts 1:8; Romans 10:14-15; Titus 1:5-9) (Chitty, 1982; Ferguson, 1998). During the monastic period, from the 3rd to the 6th centuries, early monastics retreated into the deserts to embrace solitude, fasting, and prayer, eventually forming communities that drew people toward the Christian faith. These monastic communities acted as hubs of Christian practice, hospitality, and education, revitalizing Christian missions across Europe (Cherniavsky, 1970; McCormick, 2001).

The Reformation (16th and 17th centuries) further emphasized church planting as Reformers like Martin Luther and John Calvin advocated for sola scriptura (Scripture alone) and sola fide (faith alone), urging believers to engage in the active life of the

church. This era saw the rise of independent congregations, reshaping the religious landscape of Europe and paving the way for new denominations to emerge and establish local, self-governing churches rooted in Reformation ideals (Chadwick, 1981; MacCulloch, 2003). The Reformation contributed to Christianity's development by establishing seminaries and encouraging lay engagement in theological discourse (Wills, 1993).

Church Planting in the Modern Era and Philippine Context

The modern church planting movement began in the 18th and 19th centuries as missionary societies focused on bringing the gospel to diverse cultural contexts worldwide, particularly in regions with less Christian influence. Evangelical and Pentecostal churches in the 20th century introduced new models, including multi-site churches, mass evangelism, and contextualized church planting, allowing them to reach a variety of demographics effectively (Hiebert, 2018; Kraft, 2003). The Philippines, as a predominantly Christian nation with a rich history of Catholic and Protestant missions, presents a unique environment for church planting. Protestant churches in the late 19th century gained momentum and established a strong presence in the Philippines through dynamic worship and community-centered outreach, particularly in urban areas (Agcaoili, 2018; Carpio, 2018).

Today, Filipino churches are active in addressing social justice issues such as poverty, healthcare, and inequality. These ministries not only draw people to faith but also nurture local communities through practical support and advocacy (Luzon, 2015). Despite their successes, Philippine church planters face challenges related to geographic

diversity and cultural complexity, requiring strategies tailored to the specific socio-cultural landscape (Agcaoili, 2018).

Wesleyan Identity in Mission and Church Planting

The Wesleyan tradition emphasizes a holistic approach to mission, combining personal holiness with social engagement. Founded by John Wesley, the movement prioritizes personal piety, but also emphasizes social justice, charity, and compassionate acts, all of which are central to Wesleyan spirituality. Wesleyan theology includes prevenient, justifying, and sanctifying grace, offering believers a pathway of faith that emphasizes growth, transformation, and societal responsibility (Cordery, 2006; Boaheng, 2020). These theological principles encourage believers to work toward both spiritual growth and practical support for their communities, creating a faith that is both personal and communal.

The Wesleyan Quadrilateral—Scripture, Tradition, Reason, and Experience—guides believers in integrating faith into their cultural context, promoting a flexible approach that values historical foundations but adapts to new insights (Hlatshwayo & Zondi, 2020). This theological framework shapes church planting within the Wesleyan context by promoting a mission that is as focused on local needs as it is on spreading the gospel (Mutwiri & Kinoti, 2022).

Curriculum Development for Church Planting

Effective church planting requires intentional curriculum development that equips leaders with the knowledge, skills, and theological foundations needed to serve diverse communities. Kern's six-step curriculum model is widely used for this purpose,

incorporating problem identification, needs assessment, goal setting, strategic implementation, and evaluation to ensure that each aspect of the curriculum aligns with the church planting mission (Kern, 1998). SMART Pedagogy, another effective model, emphasizes creating measurable and time-bound learning outcomes, ensuring that each step of church planting training is specific, achievable, and relevant (Daniela, 2018).

A contextual curriculum addresses local issues while imparting theological knowledge, enabling church leaders to respond to community-specific needs. Models like the Praxis Contextual Model of Theology further this approach by combining action with reflection, linking theological principles to real-life experiences and societal challenges (Ganzevoort & Roeland, 2014; Lamola, 2018). This model is particularly useful in diverse settings, such as the Philippines, where church planters must navigate cultural, economic, and geographical factors in their ministry work (Ott, 2014; Sun & Chi, 2022).

United Methodist Church (UMC) and Social Mission

The United Methodist Church emphasizes the integration of faith and social action, promoting discipleship as a transformative process that engages individuals in both spiritual growth and community welfare. UMC doctrine, as outlined in the Book of Discipline, encourages believers to act justly, love mercy, and walk humbly, drawing from the biblical mandate to serve the broader society (UMC Book of Discipline, 2016). This holistic mission is supported by UMC humanitarian efforts such as the United Methodist Committee on Relief (UMCOR), which provides emergency relief, health education, and advocacy for justice (Kruk et al., 2017; Cass, 2020).

In the Philippines, UMC churches actively engage in social initiatives, including education, healthcare, disaster risk reduction, and community health programs. These ministries not only reflect the UMC's commitment to social responsibility but also illustrate its adaptability to local needs. During the COVID-19 pandemic, UMC churches initiated community pantries, providing essential goods to those in need, demonstrating the church's role in addressing immediate and long-term community needs (Seneque et al., 2021; Warren et al., 2009). By fostering a faith that is deeply connected to societal well-being, the UMC continues its mission of holistic transformation, embodying Wesleyan principles of mercy and piety in practical ways that inspire both faith and action.

SYNTHESIS OF LITERATURE REVIEW

The review of literature emphasized the historical and theological evolution of church planting and its foundational role in Christian mission from the early church to modern contexts. Early Christian practices—rooted in Jesus' Great Commission and exemplified through apostolic missions, monastic movements, and the Reformation—established church planting as both a spiritual and community-building endeavor (Chitty, 1982; Ferguson, 1998; Chadwick, 1981). These stages each contributed to the expansion and endurance of Christian communities, providing important models for engaging in faith-based missions.

In contemporary settings, church planting has adapted to address cultural diversity, societal needs, and unique local challenges. The modern mission movement, fueled by evangelical and Pentecostal approaches, introduces innovative methods for reaching diverse communities, emphasizing contextualized church planting in regions like the Philippines (Hiebert, 2018; Kraft, 2003). In the Philippines, a predominantly Christian nation with a distinct blend of Catholic and Protestant heritage, church planting initiatives address issues beyond evangelism—engaging

directly with social justice, poverty alleviation, and community welfare (Agcaoili, 2018; Carpio, 2018). Such initiatives underscore the vital role of churches as agents of both spiritual growth and community transformation in culturally and geographically diverse areas (Luzon, 2015).

The Wesleyan theological framework further deepens this approach to church planting, integrating personal holiness and social responsibility. Rooted in grace, Wesleyan spirituality encourages believers to embody a faith that is both individually transformative and socially engaged, thereby creating holistic mission practices that address the needs of both the spirit and society (Cordery, 2006; Boaheng, 2020). The Wesleyan Quadrilateral—Scripture, Tradition, Reason, and Experience—guides believers in contextualizing their faith, ensuring that church planting efforts align with historical values while adapting to the evolving cultural landscape (Hlatshwayo & Zondi, 2020).

To support effective church planting, curriculum development becomes a critical factor. Models such as Kern’s six-step approach and SMART Pedagogy emphasize measurable, context-sensitive learning goals, preparing church leaders to engage effectively in their communities (Kern, 1998; Daniela, 2018). The Praxis Contextual Model of Theology further enhances this by connecting theological reflection to real-world applications, allowing church leaders to respond thoughtfully to local societal and cultural challenges (Ganzevoort & Roeland, 2014; Lamola, 2018). Such structured and responsive curriculum frameworks ensure that church planting programs are both impactful and relevant, equipping leaders with the necessary tools for effective ministry.

The United Methodist Church (UMC) demonstrates a holistic model of mission, integrating discipleship, humanitarian efforts, and social advocacy into its approach. Through initiatives such as the United Methodist Committee on Relief (UMCOR) and local programs in the Philippines, the UMC exemplifies a faith deeply committed to social justice, community health, and environmental stewardship, reflecting the enduring Wesleyan ideals of mercy, piety, and holistic

transformation (UMC Book of Discipline, 2016; Seneque et al., 2021). By balancing the spiritual and social aspects of the mission, the UMC and Wesleyan tradition continue to shape church planting practices that foster sustainable, culturally attuned faith communities worldwide.

EMERGED THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK (Grounded Theory)

The Church Planting Curriculum is a way forward for church planting mission endeavors because it serves as the foundation. It pertains to the growth, multiplication, and sustenance of church planting mission programs.

PANAGMULA is an Ilocano term translated into Planting. PANAGMULA, the core category, is an abbreviation of the eight (8) main categories.

- P - Planning and Implementation: This involves the strategic planning and execution of church planting initiatives.
- A - Analysis of Ministry Areas: Conducting a thorough analysis of ministry areas to understand the context and needs.
- N - Navigating Impediments: Addressing and overcoming challenges and obstacles in church planting efforts.
- A - Assessment Framework: Developing a systematic framework for evaluating church planting activities.
- G - Grounded Methodology: Using a contextual methodology rooted in the specific cultural and social context.
- M - Missiological Identity: Emphasizing Wesleyan identity in church planting missiology.
- U - Utilizing Dynamics: Maximizing church mission dynamics for effective outreach and growth.

- L - Local Engagement: Engaging with the local community to build relationships and foster support.
- A - Adaptive Strategies: Adapting strategies to fit each planting mission's unique needs and circumstances.

EMERGED CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1. Emerged Conceptual Framework

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

To develop a Church Planting Curriculum in Wesleyan Identity for the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference of the UMC in its context, this dissertation aims to determine the answers to the following questions objectively:

1.7.1 What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:

1.7.1.1 Membership Category;

1.7.1.2 UMC Previous Leadership Role;

1.7.1.3 UMC Current Leadership Role;

1.7.2 What are the contextual components of developing a Church Planting Mission Curriculum in line with the Wesleyan Identity for the church leaders of the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference?

1.7.2.1 What is the need for developing a Church Planting Mission Curriculum in line with the Wesleyan Identity for the church leaders of the NWPAC in their context?

1.7.2.2 What is the biblical and theological foundation of developing a Church Planting Mission Curriculum in line with the Wesleyan Identity for the church leaders of the NWPAC?

1.7.2.3 What is the significance of the Wesleyan Identity in the church planting mission curriculum?

1.7.2.4 What are the practical ways, methods, and strategies for imparting knowledge of the Church planting mission curriculum in line with Wesleyan Identity in the context of NWPAC?

1.7.2.5 What are the challenges encountered in implementing the church planting mission?

1.7.3 Based on the findings of the study, what church planting curriculum should be proposed in the context of NWPAC?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The importance of this study rests in its ability to offer a necessary structure in Wesleyan Identity for Church planting mission programs in the context of NWPAC. The curriculum will offer guidance, strategy, planning and implementation, training, and development for church leaders' church planting mission programs. The proposed dissertation aims to enhance the efficacy of Northwest Philippines Annual Conference church planting efforts and facilitate their expansion into more areas within the region in a contextual manner.

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

The dissertation will cover the entire Northwest Philippines Annual Conference area, which is composed of six (6) Districts: Northern Ilocos Mission (NIMD), Ilocos North (IND), Ilocos South (ISD), Cordillera Mission (CMD), Northeast Pangasinan (NEPD), and Southeast Pangasinan (SEPD).

Figure 2. Map of Northwest Philippines Annual Conference

DEFINITION OF TERMS

- Church Planting Mission Curriculum - Guidelines for training, planning, and execution of the Church Planting mission programs.
- Holistic - Refers to the overall growth or improvement of an individual, church, organization, and mission.

- Northwest Philippines Annual Conference - The oldest and considered to be the mother conference of the Philippine UMC;
- Sowing the Seeds of Faith - Planting the Gospel through evangelism, mission, and ministry to a community;
- Wesleyan Identity - Primarily revolves around the Wesleyan Quadrilateral Understanding of Faith; Scripture; Tradition; Experience; and reason; Also include the Wesleyan Spirituality in doing mission.

CHAPTER 2

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the Research Design, Population, Samples and Sampling Technique, Research Instrument, and Data Gathering Procedures.

Research Design

According to Pope et al. (2000) and Noble & Smith (2013), qualitative research focuses on understanding people's experiences, behaviors, and social situations from their perspective. It gathers and analyzes data from interviews, observations, and groups of people whose data are not numerical to understand how the individual's ideas and experiences be interpreted qualitatively. Researchers utilize various methods such as interviews, participant observations, and focus groups (Noble & Smith, 2013; Liamputtong, 2009). Data gathered through qualitative research undergo several steps, including data familiarization, coding, categorizing, and generating themes (Green et al., 2007). Qualitative research was utilized in this study to explore the components of the Church Planting Curriculum in Wesleyan Identity in NWPAC.

Grounded theory, introduced by Glaser and Strauss in 1967, derives theories from data gathered by making constant comparisons, theoretical sampling, and applying theoretical sensitivity to identify and understand patterns and relationships. In the development of the Church Planting Mission Curriculum in Wesleyan Identity for the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference, the grounded theory method by Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1998) was utilized to determine the components of the curriculum.

Population, Samples, and Sampling Technique

The researcher utilized a purposive sampling technique in the study, which is a non-probability or randomized sampling method. The researcher selected eighteen (18) participants based on certain criteria that would give the highest response quality (Polit & Beck, 2008). Six (6) of them were Lay Persons who are Lay leaders of Annual and District levels, retired deaconesses, university faculty, and twelve (12) Elders who are district superintendents, administrative pastors, mission pastors, bible translators, and chairpersons of BOOM and DCOM.

Research Instrument

Eight (8) semi-structured interview questions were used to collect data. The researcher designed the semi-structured interview questions to encourage an organic and open dialogue with the respondents, allowing the interviewer to derive a grounded theory from the responses. The purpose of this instrument is to obtain qualitative information and a range of insights from the respondents in an open-ended discussion relevant to the research problems. The Semi-structured interview questions are given to the respondents in advance to give them time to prepare their answers, increasing the quality of the research responses.

Validity & Reliability Testing

The Researcher gave the initial semi-structured interview questions to three (3) Church workers of NWPAC who are not official respondents to check for clarity and understandability through a mock interview setup. They answered without difficulty and clearly. Afterward, the researcher presented the semi-structured interview questions

during the proposal defense. After some minor additions, the semi-structured interview questions were approved. Upon the adviser's confirmation to begin interviewing using the semi-structured interview questions, the researcher immediately did so. In the appendices, the original transcriptions of the respondents are preserved and coded accordingly, from open coding to axial coding for transparency.

Data Gathering Procedures

The Researcher wrote an invitation letter to the target respondents until the eighteen (18) respondents distributed across the six (6) districts of NWPAC were completed. Upon completion, the Researcher interviewed the eighteen (18) selected respondents through face-to-face and Zoom meetings from December 2023 to April 2024. All interview sessions were recorded, and the files were accessible for transparency. The responses combined different languages and dialects, notably Filipino, Ilocano, and English. With this, the researcher hired several transcribers who collaborated and are natural speakers of the said languages and dialects, enabling the production of accurate transcriptions of the interview responses. The transcriptions underwent rigorous examination and repeated comparison with the recording files.

Data Analysis

The collected data underwent the grounded theory method by Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1998). First, the Researcher collected the data through semi-structured interviews and then highlighted important words, actions, or events connected to the interview question through the Open Coding process. Line by line, sentence by sentence, and paragraph by paragraph were utilized to determine the codes appropriate to the

respondent's statement. Upon the determination of the open codes, the researcher through the axial coding made connections for each of the interview questions through categorization. Each interview question produced a main category which was divided into six (6) subcategories, namely the (1) Causal Conditions or what causes things to happen; (2) Phenomena or what the main issue or event is; (3) Strategies or how to deal with the phenomena; (4) Consequences or what happens because of these actions; (5) Context or where, when, and how these things happen; and the (6) Intervening Conditions or other factors affecting the phenomena. Finally, in selective coding, the Researcher derived a core category that connects all the main categories arriving at the grounded theory.

Memoing

Memos are records of the researcher's perspective, observations, and reflections that supplement the data collection and analysis. This enables the researcher to understand the data thoroughly, explore emerging categories, and make connections (Mohajan & Mohajan, 2022; Birks et al., 2008). Memos capture initial thoughts about codes, categories, and relationships among data points, allowing researchers to explore their findings' implications (Mehta et al., 2010; Bahadori, 2024).

Theoretical Saturation

Theoretical saturation is achieved when no more new codes, themes, or categories can be derived from the collected data, hence, data collection has reached a level of saturation, where further data gathering will result in similar data previously analyzed (Moura et al., 2022; Leep-Lazar, 2023; Conlon et al., 2020). The Researcher engaged in

a process of constant comparison and continuously analyzed the data while simultaneously collecting it. This iterative process enabled the researcher to refine the categories, leading to the grounded theory's development.

Theoretical Sampling

When new phenomena emerge from the coding analysis and additional information is necessary, the researcher can recruit more respondents to illuminate the newly discovered phenomena or better grasp their meaning. This process is called Theoretical sampling. However, data saturation was reached with the eighteen (18) respondents, and no additional theoretical sampling was made.

Ethical Considerations

In the invitation letter, the Researcher mentioned that the interview would be recorded to ensure data accuracy. The recorded interview sessions will be subjected to various people for validation and checking. The interview did not include personal questions but was limited to demographic information regarding Membership Categorization and past and Present Leadership Roles in the UMC. Code names, such as R1 (Respondent 1), R2 (Respondent 2), and so on, were used to hide the respondents' identities. All the respondents agreed to the terms without hesitation and cooperated fully during the interview.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

This chapter presents the results and analysis of data collected on the contextual components of developing a Church Planting Mission Curriculum in line with the Wesleyan Identity for the church leaders of the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference. The findings are presented systematically through the grounded theory model of Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1998). Primarily, the core category from selective coding is given, followed by the main categories and subcategories derived from axial coding. Initial codes from open coding are used as references or as supporting statements.

The core category from selective coding was derived from the eight (8) main categories based on axial coding, as guided by the grounded theory model of Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1998). Each main category had six (6) subcategories, systematically derived from Causal Conditions, Phenomena, Strategies, Consequences, Context, and Intervening Conditions (Strauss & Corbin, 1999).

RQ 1. The demographic profile of the respondents.

Table 1. Demographic Profile

Respondent No.	UMC Membership Category	UMC Previous Leadership Role	UMC's Current Leadership Role
R1	Elder	Chairperson, DCOM Admin. Pastor, ISD Mission Pastor, ISD	Chairperson, DCOM Admin. Pastor, ISD
R2	Elder	District Superintendent, CMD Admin. Pastor, CMD Mission Pastor, NEPD & CMD	Associate Pastor, CMD
R3	Lay	Lay Leader, IND	Lay Leader, IND

		CFA, NWPAC	
R4	Elder	District Superintendent, CMD Admin. Pastor, ISD Mission Pastor, ISD	Admin. Pastor, ISD
R5	Elder	District Superintendent, SEPD Admin. Pastor, SEPD Mission Pastor, IND & SEPD	District Superintendent, SEPD
R6	Elder	District Superintendent, NEPD Chairperson, BOOM Director, Lay Servant Admin. Pastor, NEPD	Admin. Pastor, NEPD
R7	Elder	Translator, Wycliffe Bible Mission Pastor, ISD, IND & NIMD Admin. Pastor, ISD & CMD	Admin. Pastor, ISD
R8	Elder	Chairperson, DCOM Admin Pastor, CMD Mission Pastor, CMD	Admin Pastor, CMD
R9	Elder	Chairperson, DCOM Admin Pastor, NIMD Mission Pastor, NIMD	Admin Pastor, NIMD
R10	Elder	SCYD Director President & Dean, WDS, and UTS Admin Pastor, SEPD	Retired Pastor, SEPD
R11	Elder	District Superintendent, NIMD Admin. Pastor, NIMD	Admin. Pastor, NIMD
R12	Lay	Lay Leader, ISD	Lay Leader, ISD
R13	Elder	Mission Pastor, NEPD & SEPD Admin. Pastor, SEPD	Admin. Pastor, SEPD
R14	Elder	District Superintendent, NEPD Admin. Pastor, NEPD & ISD	District Superintendent, NEPD
R15	Lay	Lay Leader, NIMD	Lay Leader, NIMD
R16	Lay	Lay Leader, NEPD	Lay Leader, NEPD

R17	Lay	Deaconess, SEPD Chairperson, Christian Education, NWPAC	CE Faculty, WUP
R18	Lay	Deaconess, CMD Chairperson, Christian Education NWPAC	Lay Leader, NWPAC

RQ 2. The contextual components of developing a Church Planting Mission Curriculum in line with the Wesleyan Identity for the church leaders of the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference.

RQ 2.1: Emerged Need for The Development of Church Planting Mission Curriculum

Main Category 1: Assessment Framework

Figure 3. Assessment Framework

The Assessment Framework emerged from six (6) subcategories namely, (1) Church Planting Mission Engagement which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Educational resource as the phenomenon; (3) Critical Needs Analysis in Church

Planting Initiatives as the strategy to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Enhanced Church Planting Efficacy as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Contextualization as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Organizational Structure as the intervening condition.

Subcategory 1: Church Planting Mission Engagement (Causal Condition)

Church growth and mission, “*R5: Tungo sa pagpapalago at pag papalakas sa misyon ng ating Iglesia* (Towards the growth and strengthening of our church's mission)”, provides a clear vision in doing church planting mission (Where there is no vision, the people will perish, R7). Such is the case for intentional mission engagement in church planting (They call them mission churches at the start and do Bible studies and visitations, R10).

Church mission engagement involves a variety of approaches, including pastoral care, reflective practices, spiritual engagement, and social transformation. The mission is to reach out to believers and nurture their faith through prayer, worship, and teaching (Knoetze, 2020). This engagement with the world is crucial for the church's participation in the mission of God (Robinson, 2019). In the era of globalization, the church mission should embody witness, proclamation, fellowship, and service (Kangwa, 2016).

Subcategory 2: Educational Resource (Phenomenon)

The curriculum facilitates the learning process of the students, in this case, the church leaders who will undergo church planting training, “*R1: Kas pangarigan koma iti eskwelaan isu ada curriculum tapno nalakada nga ipatungpal iti panangadal dagitoy nga estudyante* (For example, in schools, there is a curriculum to make it easier to

implement and manage the students' learning).” As an educational resource, the church leaders will have a guide or a blueprint to follow in church planting initiatives, “*R3: Adda sursuroten, adda blueprint nga sursuruten iti panagmula panagpaado iti iglesia* (There is a guideline, a blueprint to follow in planting and expanding the church).” This will result in a universal system, goal orientation, and implementation, “*R14: Para may mas maayos na pagpapatupad at may isang hangarin* (For better implementation and to have a unified goal).”

Developing a well-structured curriculum is important for preparing leaders and educators to effectively carry out the mission of establishing new church communities. This includes adapting to societal changes, embracing digital tools and resources, and promoting teamwork with other church institutions (Masengwe, 2023). Implementing an ethical education curriculum in church-related educational settings highlights the importance of integrating values and moral principles into the educational framework (Bourke et al., 2019).

Subcategory 3: Critical Needs Analysis in Church Planting Initiatives (Strategies)

Critical needs analysis of a certain community for church planting mission programs is crucial, “*R4: Nakilala mo ba yung sitwasyon nila, ano yung pangangailangan nila?* (Do you know their situation and what their needs are?)”, To address the immediate need of that area enabling the church planting mission to be relevant, “*R3: Tapno mai-input tayo diay plano no anya da dagiti masapol tayo* (So that we can incorporate the plan according to what our needs are).”

Tailoring the mission to address the community's unique needs enhances the church's impact (Macallan, 2019). Understanding the needs of the community members and

church leaders is essential for developing effective strategies and programs that cater to those needs and align with the church's mission and goals (Casidy et al., 2010).

Subcategory 4: Enhanced Church Planting Efficacy (Consequences)

Enhancement of church planting efforts efficacy is beneficial because it strengthens the church leaders, “*R6: Ito ay magiging source of empowerment ng both the clergy and lay sa initiative ng church planting within NWPAC* (This will serve as a source of empowerment for both the clergy and laity in the church planting initiative within NWPAC)”, by equipping and training them to do an effective church planting mission program by outlining the steps, necessary actions, and priorities, “*R12: Tapno dito ay maibinsa-binsa dagiti pamay-an, rubbeng nga aramiden ken pang-pangruna* (So that the priorities, necessary actions, and key tasks can be identified here).”

Engagement of the church with the community members improves participation rates and the success of church planting initiatives (Derose et al., 2000). Focusing on structural changes within the church, such as mentorship plans, empowering leaders, and effective communication of the church's vision, can improve leadership effectiveness and overall church operations. These strategies can enhance church planting initiatives' leadership capacity and organizational effectiveness (Deo, 2023).

Subcategory 5: Contextualization (Context)

The context must be determined so that the needs are adequately addressed in both the church and the community, “*R14: Para sa naayon at naangkop sa pangangailangan ng isang simbahan o isang komunidad* (For it to be appropriate and suitable for the needs

of a church or community).” Determining the context will enable the church planter to know the right approach in that community, as emphasized by R15,

Sa lugar na pagtataniman mo ito mapag aaralan mo kung papaano yung magiging approach mo sa ibat ibang klaseng personalidad ng tao and then yung approach kasi napakaimportante lalo na sa panahon ngayon kasi hindi pare pareho yung approach natin sa mga lugar (In the place where you will plant this, you need to study how to approach different types of personalities. The approach is very important, especially today, because our approach cannot be the same in every place).

Contextualization will prepare the church planters for planning and execution (It is beneficial for the team to know the why, what, who, and where of church planting, R17).

Churches must continually adapt to the context of the community to remain relevant and practical (Henry & Soal, 2021). Engaging with the community and addressing their needs is essential for establishing a solid presence (Hermanto et al., 2022), combining local culture and traditions with broader Christian teaching approaches to bridge the gap between local practices and universal Christian principles (Barber, 2020).

Subcategory 6: Organizational Structure (Intervening Condition)

The organizational structure includes the development of a church planting team that will specifically handle the church planting mission (We have a team to be equipped with knowledge and skills, R17; *Masapol et al. ti maysa a committee* [It is necessary to form a committee], R7). Establishing an organized structure for the church planting mission will enable the church leaders to set a common standard or procedure to be followed and implemented (*Magseset na isang standard o kaya procedure* [To set a standard or procedure], R16).

A company's organizational structure, such as management efficiency, decision-making processes, and employee performance, can impact its operations. For instance, a mechanistic organizational structure, characterized by formal lines of authority and specialized functions, can lead to clear hierarchies and well-defined roles within the organization (Kanten et al., 2017). On the other hand, an organic structure, with more decentralized decision-making and flexible roles, can promote innovation and adaptability (Fiol & Lyles, 1985).

Main Category 2: Grounded Methodology

Figure 4. Grounded Methodology

Grounded Methodology emerged from six (6) subcategories, namely, (1) Social Geography, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Contextual Adaptation as the phenomenon; (3) Cultural Immersion as the strategy to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Contextual Missiology as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5)

Community Dynamics as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Collaboration of church workers and lay people as the intervening condition.

Subcategory 1: Social Geography (Causal Condition)

Careful area surveys are essential in understanding the social geography of a specific community before conducting a church planting mission proper, as expressed by R3, *Ti ammok nga kasapulan isu didiay a careful nga ummuna didiay panagsurvey kadagiti mabalin nga panangipatakderan ti panagmulaan iti church iti panagpatakder iti local church haan nga basta basta nga mapan ka magpatakder nu di kitdi masapol ti careful survey nu anya da nga potential nga kamkameng* (I know that what is needed is a careful initial survey of potential sites for church planting. Establishing a local church is not something that can be done hastily. Instead, a careful survey is necessary to determine the potential members).

In addition, potential members should also be identified for they will serve as the pioneers of the community (*the potential members nga mabalin nga agkamkameng to iti dayta nga mapatakder nga simbaan* [the potential members who may become members of that church to be built], R3).

A vital concern with justice, relevance, participatory methods, and ethical responsibility characterizes social geography, reflecting a commitment to addressing social issues and promoting inclusivity within specific contexts (Howitt, 2011). It investigates the role of faith-based organizations, cultural practices, and social movements in shaping communities by addressing social welfare issues (Kong, 2010).

Subcategory 2: Contextual Adaptation (Phenomenon)

Aligning a church mission with the context of the community results in the right action based on context, situation, and needs. As R4 stated,

Ano yung mga kultura konteksto nila kasi nga ito yung pagbabasehan natin kung ano yung mga possibility na pwede nating gawin na naayon sa kanila para sa ganoon ay mas akma yung mga pwede nating gawin (What are their cultural contexts? This will be our basis for determining what possibilities we can pursue that align with them, so that what we do will be more suitable).

Contextual adaptation also enables the church leaders to determine the efficient approach toward a specific community as emphasized by R18,

Yung alamin natin yung context ng mga churches natin specially by district, kagaya dito samin sa Cordillera iba yung approach dito ng pagmimisyon iba din ang approach diyan sa Pangasinan for sure iba din sa Ilocos. Napakaganda na malaman natin yung context ng mga lugar at mga tao (We need to understand the context of our churches, especially by district. For example, here in Cordillera, the approach to missions differs from that in Pangasinan, and it will surely be different in Ilocos. It is essential to know the context of the places and people).

Studies have highlighted the importance of contextual missions customized to the target community's specific needs and characteristics (Silitonga & Simatupang, 2023), emphasizing the role of Diakonia tasks and the significance of conducting quality-oriented missions even with smaller congregations. Implementing a Strong Community Development approach can be an effective strategy for holistic and integrated transformational missions in Indigenous, poverty-stricken, and remote rural areas (Silitonga & Simatupang, 2023). Contextual adaptation in church missions should

consider the shifting cultures and the impact of globalization on mission approaches (Kangwa, 2016).

Subcategory 3: Cultural Immersion (Strategies)

Immersing oneself in a specific community will enable a person to know and understand the culture more deeply and to address their situation better. This would also prevent baseless information that would affect the mission. R4 gave a strong emphasis on this,

Kumbaga hindi mo malalaman yung isang bagay kung wala kang immersion kailangan nating magimmerse muna. Yun yung kwan natin para kapag naging ganito ba ah okay. Hindi nalang tayo basta magassume. Iimmerse nating yung mgasarili natin sa mga lugar kilalanin natin sila, ilan sila ano yung buhay nila. Yun po yun para mas malaman natin kung ano yung the best way to address them (In other words, you won't know something if you don't have any immersion. We need to immerse ourselves first. That's our way of doing it so that when it becomes like this, it's okay. Let's not just assume. We will immerse ourselves in the places to get to know them, how many there are, and what their lives are like. That's it so that we can better understand the best way to address them).

Cultural immersion engages with understanding the cultural context of the community being served to carry out the mission work effectively by immersing the church leaders in the culture of the people they are contacting, allowing them to build meaningful relationships, gain insights into local customs and traditions, and customized their approach to be relevant and impactful (Mugok & Fern, 2018). By immersing themselves in the local culture, missionaries can bridge cultural gaps, demonstrate

respect for the community's way of life, and effectively communicate the message of Christianity to the cultural values and beliefs of the people they serve, which in effect builds trust, encourage connections, and ensuring that the mission work is culturally sensitive and relevant (Scott, 2005).

Subcategory 4: Contextual Missiology (Consequences)

Contextual Missiology involves doing a mission according to the determined needs or adapting to the community's situation and the church's and the planter's capacity. A mission-based program to address the holistic needs of the community and the church. R4's view highlighted this,

Kumbaga meron tayong sinasabing learning situation. Una sa lahat yung capacity mo bilang church kung yung sitwasyon mo ba ay kaya na niyang magchurch planting o yung church naman community naman ay nakilala mo ba yung sitwasyon nila, ano yung pangangailangan nila? Kumbaga learning your situation, their situation and the whole situation para sa gayon ay magkaroon ka ng maliwanag na yung visions mo tsaka missions mo ano bang gagawin natin? (In other words, we have a learning situation. First of all, what is your capacity as a church? Is your situation capable of church planting? Or have you gotten to know the situation of the church community, what their needs are? In other words, learning your situation, their situation, and the whole situation, so that you can have a clear vision and mission - what are we going to do?)

Also, with R9's perspective,

So, masapul nga adda dayjay kuna tayo nga panang surbey kadayjay nga area ken makita jay kasapulan da tapno nu dajigay. Isuda ket maaddressan ngamin, nya tapno immuna ka nga nagpatakder iti simbaan, sir. Tapos, haan gayam nga... nagadayo gayam

dagijay tattao. And then haan gayam dayjay iti... kasta, kasla needs da. So, siguro mapasamak daytoy dayjay mapatakder nga simbaan ijay. (So, it's necessary to conduct a survey of the area to identify their needs so we can address them properly. We should meet their needs first before establishing a church there, sir. However, if it turns out that the people are far away or if their needs are different from what we assumed, establishing a church there might not be feasible.)

Kim (2004) viewed contextual missiology as a process wherein missionaries and church leaders immerse themselves in the local culture, traditions, and practices to communicate the gospel message effectively, involving building relationships, listening to the community's needs and concerns, and adapting mission strategies to align with the cultural norms and values of the people. It also encourages interdisciplinary studies and dialogue between different cultures, denominations, and religious traditions. By engaging in conversations that bridge cultural differences, church planters can better understand the diverse contexts in which mission work occurs and encourage mutual respect and collaboration (Penner, 2018).

Subcategory 5: Community Dynamics (Context)

Establishing presence and building relationships are integral parts of community dynamics to increase the efficacy of church planting programs. There is an immediate need to go to that community, as R3 stated, "*Umuna nga aramid em, mapan ka day lugar* (The first thing you do is go into that place)." R18 explained that build people first before the building,

So maganda yun start from where the people are kung nasaan sila then build people first before church building, kasi di ba ang church naman hindi yung building, hindi lang

yung building kundi yung church ay yung tao. (So, it is best to start where the people are and focus on building the community before constructing a church building. After all, the church is not just the building; the church is the people.)

Community dynamics emphasizes the need to contextualize mission efforts by understanding the changes in the target community by immersing oneself in the local culture, building relationships, and adapting strategies to align with the community's social, cultural, and economic realities (Abimbola, 2019). The missional church is acknowledged for its role in community development, encouraging active participation, and promoting healthy community well-being, including the empowerment of individuals, enhancing social cohesion, and addressing issues affecting the community's health and prosperity (Msebi, 2022).

Subcategory 6: Collaboration of Church Workers and Lay People (Intervening Condition)

Collaboration or teamwork between church workers and laypeople is crucial in missional work. Church workers cannot do it alone, and the involvement of laypeople is imperative so that in working together, more can be accomplished, as emphasized by R11, *Church workers cannot do it alone or hindi natin nagagampanan lahat ng mga trabaho, mas maraming magawa kung andyan ang mga layko na kailangang idevelop, we need to have a passion with heart in doing church planting.* (Church workers cannot do it alone, and we cannot handle all the tasks alone. We can achieve more if we involve lay people who need to be developed. We need to have a passionate heart for church planting). R5 also stated, *“Kailangan ang collaboration ng Lay people at tsaka yung mga Pastors* (Collaboration between laypeople and pastors is essential).”

Research by Dunaetz and Bocock (2021) emphasizes the significance of organizational commitment and work engagement in predicting the ministry involvement of church staff and lay members to encourage dedication and engagement among all individuals involved in church work. Clergy and lay people should integrate their belief in the church's mission while managing church finances, balancing the spiritual mission and practical considerations for sustaining resources (Irvine, 2005).

RQ 2.2: Emerged Biblical and Theological Bases On Church Planting Mission

Main Category 3: Church Planting Missiology

Figure 5. Church Planting Missiology

Church Planting Missiology emerged from six (6) subcategories namely, (1) Church Planting Mission Basis which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) The Biblical and Theological Philosophy of Church Planting as the phenomenon; (3) Intentional Discipleship Programs as the strategy to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Vision

and Mission Articulation as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Spiritual Empowerment as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Human Resource as the intervening condition.

Subcategory 1: Church Planting Mission Basis (Causal Condition)

The Great Commission found in Matthew 28:16-20 marks the grand mandate of the church to go and proclaim the Gospel “*Sinabi ni Hesus na humayo kayo Matthew 28 the great commission yung ipangaral ninyo* [Jesus said in Matthew 28, the Great Commission, to go and preach. This is what you should proclaim], R1”, through the empowerment of the Holy Spirit as “when they received the Holy Spirit, they were empowered, R6”, and evangelized, “Evangelism is key to extending the kingdom, R7”.

The concept of Missio Dei (Mission of God) serves as a foundation for a mission-centered church, highlighting its centrality in God's mission (Cho, 2024) through a thorough exploration of biblical and theological principles that shape church mission (Gelder, 2004). The missional church plays a critical role in community development as part of God's mission, advocating for active citizenship and teamwork to enhance community well-being (Msebi, 2022).

Subcategory 2: The Biblical and Theological Philosophy of Church Planting (Phenomenon)

The philosophy of the Great Commission serves as the turning point of the church planting mission to enable intentional discipleship-making with a compelling vision, which is a crucial aspect in church planting initiatives as emphasized by R2, *Turning point met ti church tayo nga dapat maawatan dagiti miembro daytoy matthew 28:18-20.*

Daytoy ti ibagbaga ni apo Dios nga masapol nga maaddaan to the compelling vision for intentional disciple-making. It is a must. Ngamin no haanka nga agkaroon ti vision nga agpayso, iti major task ti simbaan ket mapukaw ka a. and no naaddan koma iti church ito intentional discipleship process ket amin koma ang aktibidad wenno program ket subservient ito daytoy. (A turning point for our church is that members must understand Matthew 28:18-20. This passage reveals that we must have a compelling vision for intentional disciple-making. It is a must. Without a true vision, you risk losing focus on the significant task of the church. If our church had a process for intentional discipleship, then all activities or programs should be aligned with it.)

The biblical and theological philosophy of church planting covers the concept of stewardship, emphasizing the believers' responsibility to care for creation and participate in charitable work to sustain and replenish communities (Musili, 2024). Church involvement in community development is rooted in the biblical mandate for believers to care for the marginalized, promote justice, and serve the community's needs (Wambugu et al., 2022).

Subcategory 3: Intentional Discipleship Programs (Strategies)

Discipleship programs must be intentional because the mandate of the Great Commission requires an action-oriented mission, as emphasized by R4,

Normal naman sa atin yon yung sa matthew 28 yung go and make disciples of all nations baptizing them teach them. Yun ay hindi request ito ay command kaya nga sabi nila we are commissioned, ibig sabihin nun partner tayo ng Diyos so it is beyond our responsibilities and duties. Ibig sabihin niya dito intentional, kailangan nating gawin yun yung dapat nating gawin. Ano pa ba yung pwede nating gawin pag magiging

kristiano? Wala na tayong ibang pwedeng gawin because we are commissioned partners tayo ng Panginoon na itutuloy ang misyon. (It is normal for us to refer to Matthew 28, where Jesus says, 'Go and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them and teaching them.' This is not a request; it is a command. That's why we say we are commissioned. This means we are partners with God, so it goes beyond just our responsibilities and duties. It signifies that we must be intentional and do what we are called to do. What else can we do as Christians? There is nothing else we can do because we are commissioned partners with the Lord to continue His mission).

Discipleship trains and equips the church leaders to be church planters following the biblical mandate, making it a crucial aspect in church planting mission initiatives that will lead to effective teaching and preaching of the Gospel, as expressed by R9, *Train or isurom ida. Masapul nga adda dayjay nurture. Ipakaawat kanyada ti kinapateg ti panamati kinni Apo Diyos. Awaten da ti nasantoan nga bautismo. adda dayjay kuna tayo nga sumaruno nga hakbang wenno aramiden tayo tapno talaga nga masursuro da, aramiden da jay task a kas maysa nga kristyano.* (Train or teach them. There must be nurturing involved. We need to convey to them the significance of faith in the Lord. They should understand the importance of holy baptism. This is the next step or action we need to take to ensure they genuinely learn and carry out their task as Christians).

Intentional discipleship programs are crucial for nurturing and equipping individuals to deepen their faith and commitment to Christ. They guide believers in their spiritual growth journey, encouraging a deeper understanding of their responsibilities as disciples of Christ. The intentional nature of these programs highlights a purposeful and

structured approach to discipleship, ensuring that participants are actively engaged in their spiritual development (Pr. & Muneja, 2021).

Subcategory 4: Vision and Mission Articulation (Consequences)

Without vision, church workers become limited to maintaining the church instead of engaging in missional activities. Vision enables the church planter to set the goal. In implementing the vision, more extended time in church appointments is necessary. Having a clear vision and mission makes a positive impact on church development. R11 expressed it clearly, *Kung walang vision ang pastor na mag misyon magiging maintaining pastor yan. Bigyang pansin ang mga pastor na nagmemisyon at bigyan ng mas mahabang termino sa iglesia kung saan sila, kung masipag sila at nakikita naman na talagang maganda yung vision bigyan mo ng mas mahabang panahon para siyay makapaglago isang taon na term of conference year naku nakikipagkilala ka lang non sa kanila.* (If a pastor lacks a vision for mission work, they will become a maintaining pastor. Pay attention to pastors who are actively involved in mission work and give them a longer term in their church. If they are diligent and their vision is clearly positive, grant them a longer period to grow and develop the church. A one-year term during the conference year is just the beginning of getting to know them).

A shared or uniform vision, mission, and goals in the broader area like annual or district level, will enable a more effective way of church planting initiatives as R7 stated, *“Nasaysayaat met nga adda kuma, maymaysa a target iti misyon iti tunggal Distrito iti unos iti makatawen* (It would be beneficial to have a specific mission target for each district every year).”

Church leaders are tasked with clearly defining and communicating the church's vision and mission to inspire and mobilize members toward a common goal (Nikolajsen, 2013). By embodying and promoting the vision and mission that the leaders have set for the congregation, they encourage a sense of purpose, unity, and direction in fulfilling the Great Commission (Salu et al., 2023).

Subcategory 5: Spiritual Empowerment (Context)

The Pentecost in the Book of Acts was about the apostles receiving power from the Holy Spirit, enabling them to speak in different tongues. Spiritual Empowerment is vital because human capacity alone will not be enough to fulfill God's mission. R6 clearly expresses this, *Yung the day of Pentecost, ito yung commissioning ng bawat disciples, ito yung empowerment nila. Ito yung commissioning nila, so the disciples were set aside to do the particular task of ministry. Yung proclamation of the word. When they received the Holy Spirit, na empower sila. Ano yung empowerment nila, they were able to speak in other languages, different languages. They were able to testify because of the empowerment of the Spirit, testify in people's language.* (On the day of Pentecost, this marked the commissioning of each disciple and their empowerment. The disciples were set apart for a specific ministry task: the proclamation of the Word. When they received the Holy Spirit, they were empowered. This empowerment allowed them to speak in different languages. They could testify in people's native languages because of the Spirit's empowerment).

The lay people during the time of Acts preached the good news about Jesus through the empowerment of the Holy Spirit, as R11 emphasized, *I would like to share with you the biblical basis taken from the books of Acts 8:4, napapaloob dito, "but the believers*

who were scattered preach the good news about Jesus wherever they went”, sino ba ang unang nag plant ng seed noong nabuwag ang mga believers sa Jerusalem? Edi mga layko, ito yung mga layko na they are filled with the Holy Spirit. (I would like to share the biblical basis from Acts 8:4, which says, 'But the scattered believers preached the good news about Jesus wherever they went.' Who were the first to plant seeds when the believers were scattered from Jerusalem? It was the lay people, those who were filled with the Holy Spirit).

The empowerment of the Holy Spirit is associated with experiences such as speaking in tongues, prophetic utterances, healing, and other manifestations of spiritual gifts, viewed as evidence of the Holy Spirit's presence and empowerment in the lives of believers, enabling them to engage in ministry and mission with boldness and effectiveness (Onyinah, 2013). Believers rely on the guidance and empowerment of the Holy Spirit as they share the Gospel message, trusting in the Spirit's work to convict hearts, bring about repentance, and draw people into a relationship with God (Banda, 2022).

Subcategory 6: Human Resource (Intervening Condition)

Involvement of the Lay people in mission programs is crucial for its growth and sustainability. There is a need to train people who will do church planting missions. As R14 stated, *We need to tap people nga they are trained, na-orient sila nakasama natin kasi sa ibang churches two by two yong ganoon para atleast kung hindi mo man agad-agad ma-absorb kasi minsan sa pagod mo na sa dami ng gusto mo atleast siguro expecting na baka yong kasama mo kung dalawa kayo baka mayroon kang mapag tanungan yong parang mag brainstorming ano ang nangyari na yon. (We need to involve*

people who are trained and oriented, working alongside us. In other churches, they often work in pairs, which helps if you don't immediately absorb everything. Sometimes, with all the tasks and fatigue, it's beneficial to have a partner to discuss and brainstorm what happened and to support each other).

Church workers are limited in their role and capacity to engage in mission while having church appointments and sometimes more than one (1) church appointment per worker. Involving lay will mean multiple mission tasks can be achieved. Continuing the response of R14, *Kaya kailangan siguro mag-train tayo o may kasama hindi lang iisa yong gagawa dito kasi limitasyon sa iyong kasalukuyang tungkulin sa misyon ng pagtatanim, Pero minsan kinukulang na may mga pastor na dalawa-dalawa ang destino how much more na kukunin mo pa dito. Kaya nga ini-encourage kung may mga lay people para maging lay minister atleast pero equip pa rin sila.* (Therefore, we probably need to train or have more than one person involved in the mission of church planting because there are limitations to what one person can do. Sometimes, pastors are already managing two roles, so it's even more challenging to take on additional tasks. That's why it's encouraged to involve laypeople to become lay ministers, as long as they are well-equipped and prepared).

Church leaders are responsible for implementing human resource management practices that align with the church's values, vision, and goals, establishing leadership systems, communication channels, and organizational structures that promote effective ministry, motivation, decision-making, and service quality (Situmorang, 2023). It guides the church leaders in developing and utilizing their talents and discovering the gifts of

individuals within the congregation to grow and advance the church's mission (Sembodo & Prabowo, 2021).

RQ 2.3: Emerged Significance of The Wesleyan Identity In The Development Of Church Planting Mission Curriculum

Main Category 4: Missiological Identity

Figure 6. Missiological Identity

Missiological Identity emerged from six (6) subcategories, namely, (1) Guide in Understanding Faith, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Wesleyan Identity Integration as the phenomenon; (3) Education Among Church Leaders as the strategy to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Spiritual Growth as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Relevance as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Educational Adaptability as the intervening condition.

Subcategory 1: Guide To Understanding Faith (Causal Condition)

Wesleyan Identity serves as a guide in understanding faith. It helps strategically plan church planting missions because of its holistic approach to theological and practical matters. R4's response makes it clear, *Napakahalaga. Kasi kung tignan ninyo yung ginawa ni John Wesley pagdating sa quadrilateral kasi pininpoint niya lahat yung mga aspeto sa buhay ng tao na kailangan nating iconsider bago natin gawin yung isang bagay o bago natin iconfirm. So iconsider po nating yan sa akin ito yung isa sa pinakacore na kailangan nating iconsider sa paggawa ng curriculum at nakahalaga na doon natin ibabase lahat ng mga strategies natin o reasonable ba ito okay ba to sa experience sa tradition okay ba to tsaka yung scripture nandoon na iyon kaya sa akin para sa akin ay napakahalaga po na iintegrate natin lalo na sa paggawa ng curriculum at paggawa ng mga models pagdating sa church planting.* (This is very important. If you look at what John Wesley did with the Quadrilateral, he pinpointed all the aspects of human life that we need to consider before making decisions or confirmations. We should take this into account as it is one of the core elements in curriculum development. It's essential to base all our strategies on this approach—evaluating whether they are reasonable, align with experience and tradition, and are supported by Scripture. For me, integrating these aspects is crucial, especially in curriculum development and in creating models for church planting.)

In the Wesleyan tradition, the theological basis for mission and church planting is informed by the Wesleyan quadrilateral: scripture, tradition, reason, and experience. The framework provides a suitable approach to theological reflection and decision-making,

guiding the mission and church planting efforts within the Wesleyan tradition (Hlatshwayo & Zondi, 2020).

Subcategory 2: Wesleyan Identity Integration (Phenomenon)

Integration of Wesleyan Identity into the development of church curriculum provides a new framework wherein the Scripture, Tradition, Experience, and Reason are utilized as a guiding principle in approaching church planting mission programs. R3 saw the need for this integration, *Masapol nga kasapulan nga kwaen tayo met ti nasantoan a kasuratan, dagiti kapadasan dagiti amamma, mailawsiw kadagiti agtutubo tatta kabataan dagiti experience da masapol nga experience ni john Wesley maisuro ken daydiay rason wenno reason no apay nga masapol nga agkasapulan tayo.* (We need to consider the Holy Scriptures, the experiences of our predecessors, and share these insights with the younger generation. Their experiences should be informed by the experiences of John Wesley, explaining why it is essential for us to consider these needs).

The integration of Wesleyan Identity also enhances the overall mission programs because it becomes the basis for curriculum development, which will serve as resource material as expressed by R9, *Ti pannaka-itipon ti Wesleyan identity ket maysa a napateg nga e-konsider agsipod ta kas paset a desinyo ti curriculum dagitoy ti agbalin nga pundasyon wenno basehan kas agbalin a curriculum materials wenno resouces tayo.* (Embracing the Wesleyan identity is an important aspect to consider, as it serves as a foundation or basis for designing curriculum. This identity should become the cornerstone for our curriculum materials and resources).

The Wesleyan perspective on mission is characterized by a commitment to witness and spirituality, emphasizing the importance of spiritual formation and faith in mission

endeavors (Gallagher, 2018), engaging with contextual theologies and missiological paradigms, which seek to strengthen evangelical practices in a pluralistic world (Yong, 2016). The Wesleyan approach to church planting emphasizes the need for the Church to embody the vision of a better society and play a prophetic and constructive role in society (Villiers, 2011).

Subcategory 3: Education Among Church Leaders (Strategies)

Wesleyan Identity strengthens the missional identity as R3 responded, “*Isu met ti sursoroten tayo maipanggep datoy Wesleyan identity iti panakapapigsa koma dagitoy identity tayo* (Thus, we should follow this Wesleyan identity to strengthen and solidify our own identity).” This creates a need for intensified training and seminars among the church leaders toward the Wesleyan Identity because it involves doctrinal foundation as R14 expressed, “*So, siguro tignan natin yong doctrinal foundation yon yong kailangan na ma-enhance ma-nurture.* (So, we should examine the doctrinal foundation, which needs to be enhanced and nurtured.)”

Niemandt (2021) discussed the importance of missional spirituality in holistic theological education, emphasizing the cultivation of missional leaders for the church and the role of theological education in nurturing a missional identity and spirituality among church leaders.

Subcategory 4: Spiritual Growth (Consequences)

Spiritual growth becomes evident through the lens of the Wesleyan Identity as integrated into the church curriculum as expressed by R5, *Pag Maganda yung foundation ng curriculum ng church planting. Paglaki nila, talagang hindi nila iiwanan yan. Yan*

ang magiging prinsipyo nila at ang basehan din nila at makikita nila itong apat na identity po natin ay Maganda sa pundasyon, hindi lamang sa mga Kabataan, at lalo't higit sa mga bata na susunod sa atin. (When the foundation of the church planting curriculum is strong, they will not abandon it as they grow. It will become their guiding principle and foundation. They will see that these four identities are well-rooted, benefiting not only the youth but also the younger generations who will follow us).

With the Wesleyan Identity as the basis for understanding faith, it encourages spiritual growth as a follower of Jesus, emphasized by R14's response, *Ito yong buod ng ating batayan ng ating paglago ng ating pananampalataya bilang tagasunod ng ating panginoong Hesus at isang follower ng ating simbahan.* (This is the summary of our basis for growing in our faith as followers of our Lord Jesus and church members).

Spiritual growth in the Christian faith involves a continuous developmental journey marked by various aspects such as faith, love, hope, wisdom, peace, patience, humility, and courage (Ferreira et al., 2022), including progressing in faith, deepening knowledge of God, and increasing in grace (Chrismastianto et al., 2022).

Subcategory 5: Relevance (Context)

Relevance ensures that the mission fits the life of the people or the community involved. R10's statement showed that through Wesleyan Identity integration, the church planting mission program can be relevant by adapting to the people's lives, *Makaka affect ng kanilang buhay how they live their lives in this world and how purposeful may goal na nakikita nila na makakatulong ito ng mga tao. Of course, people also find ways to make their lives more meaningful and useful.* (This will affect their lives by shaping how they live in this world and how purposeful their goals are. They will see how it can help

others. Additionally, people will seek ways to make their lives more meaningful and useful).

Church planting missions should consider the effects of globalization on mission work, striving to embrace the missional aspects of church witness, proclamation, fellowship, and service in a globalized world (Kangwa, 2016), engaging stakeholders, identifying implementation strategies, and overcoming barriers within the church culture, norms, values, and resources to ensure the success of faith-based programs (Haughton et al., 2020)

Subcategory 6: Educational Adaptability (Intervening Condition)

The educational adaptability of the church leaders in church planting mission initiatives includes their critical thinking abilities. R1 emphasized the need to think to strategize effectively and critically, *Yung reason naman maganda itong reason para makapagtanong tayo diba makapagdagdag tayo ng idea makapagsalita tayo at makapagtanong tayo kung ano talaga ang nararapat sa atin. Yun talaga kung bakit may reason para makita natin ang isang bagay at makapagbigay tayo ng ideas o makapagtanong tayo kung ano pa ang nais nating gawin na mas nararapat sa pagbuo ng isang curriculum o pagbuo ng iglesiya sa nwpac.* (The reason for this is to allow us to ask questions, add ideas, and discuss what is truly appropriate for us. It helps us see things more clearly and provides an opportunity to contribute ideas or ask what else might be needed to develop a curriculum or build the church in NWPAC.)

In addition, R18's response emphasized the teachability of the Wesleyan Identity integrated curriculum, *At kung ito naintegrate na siya sa kurikulum na na mabubuo sa church planting, bilang worker hindi lang ako magreview, yung mga tao ding*

halimbawa meron ng pag aaral sa ganun at ituturo sa mga tao. From the start, parang naka ugat na sila parang sa halaman, para sa pagdating ng panahon hindi lang pang 12 years old na tayo na pag aaralan natin siya kung baga agad agad na iintegrate na sa kanila o naiintroduce na sa kanila kung ano yung church meron tayo, so para sa akin napaka importante na kasama siya sa gagawin niyong kurikulum. ([The Wesleyan Identity] remains steadfast and continues to speak through any kind of weather and generation. This is the fundamental identity of us Methodists. When this is integrated into the curriculum developed for church planting, as a worker, I will not only review it, but those who have studied it will also teach it to others. From the start, it should be deeply embedded, like roots in a plant, so that it's not just a lesson for 12-year-olds but is immediately integrated and introduced to them about what our church represents. For me, it is crucial that this is included in the curriculum you develop).

Educational adaptability refers to the ability of individuals to effectively adjust, learn, and succeed in diverse educational settings (Nnadi, 2024) as influenced by socio-demographic factors, institutional governance, and social intelligence, which significantly enhance adaptive capacity in educational settings (Mwadzingeni et al., 2022; Starynska et al., 2023).

RQ 2.4: Emerged Practical Ways, Methods, And Strategies for Imparting Knowledge of The Church Planting Mission Curriculum In Line With Wesleyan Identity In The Context Of NWPAC

Main Category 5: Strategic Planning and Implementation

Figure 7. Strategic Planning and Implementation

Strategic Planning and Implementation emerged from six (6) subcategories, namely, (1) Optimal Missional Strategy, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Practical Implementation as the phenomenon; (3) Community Engagement and Relationship Building as the strategy to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Network Enhancement as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Rural-Urban Disparities as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Inclusivity and Openness as the intervening condition.

Subcategory 1: Optimal Missional Strategy (Causal Condition)

Different areas mean different situations that need to be addressed. An optimal missional strategy is crucial in determining the right approach to church planting initiatives. R6 expressed the importance of different approaches depending on the area concerned: *Magkakaiba yung mga approaches din siguro dito practical ways na halimbawa, City. Candon, Urdaneta, San Fernando, Baguio City, Laoag, Vigan. Kung titignan mo halimbawa, saan mo dadalhin yung church planting initiative? Kung sa City yan, o pwede rin yung approach na pupuntahan ng bahay-bahay o pupwede rin yung, meron kasing growing development yung sa mga communities, subdivisions ganyan. Kailangan nila ng community din ng mga iyon, baka pupwedeng tignan, tignan sila na potential na venue ng church planting.* (Different approaches might be needed in practical ways. For example, consider cities like Candon, Urdaneta, San Fernando, Baguio City, Laoag, and Vigan. If you're looking at where to start a church planting initiative, you could consider whether it's more effective in a city or through a house-to-house approach. Another possibility is to look into growing developments, such as communities and subdivisions. These areas may need a community and could be potential venues for church planting).

Optimal mission strategy is the most effective and efficient approach to planning and executing missions to achieve desired objectives, ensuring mission success, minimizing risks, optimizing resource utilization, and aligning with sustainability goals (Eshaghi et al., 2023; Sawik, 2023; Wang, 2023; Saias et al., 2023)

Subcategory 2: Practical Implementation (Phenomenon)

The church leaders' practical implementation of the curriculum is integral to producing an action-oriented mission program. Preparations are required like educating the church leaders through lectures and seminars for them to be equipped as expressed by R9, *Daytoy dayjay kuna tayo nga action nu maaramid tu daytoy nga korrikulum. Haan laeng nga agpapatingga kuma nga nalpas nga naiprint, printed nga materials. Nu di ket daytoy kuma, adda dayjay for example, one district. Adda dayjay maiprograma kadagiti distrito nga maiyadal, maiyadal daytoy. Kasi, uray nag pintas dayjay material nga kuna tayo nu madi tayo met nga usaren, useless. Awan iti na isu nga dayjay kayat ko nga maaramid to daytoy nga korrikulum. Adda daytoy kuna tayo nga pannaka implementar babaen kadagiti panangi lecture, seminar, kadagitay maseknan lalong lalo na kadagiti umuna.* (This is what we should consider for action if we implement this curriculum. It shouldn't just end with printed materials. Instead, for example, in one district, there should be a program in place to apply and utilize this curriculum. Even if the materials are well-prepared, if they are not used, they become useless. What I want to achieve with this curriculum is to have it implemented through lectures, seminars, and relevant training, especially for those who are directly involved).

Effective practical implementation requires clear communication of the mission's purpose and goals to all stakeholders, including church leaders, members, volunteers, and the community. It also involves mobilizing human and material resources to support mission-related activities and initiatives, such as outreach programs, social services, evangelism efforts, and community development projects (Zega, 2023; Kim, 2011; Nyamongo, 2023).

Subcategory 3: Community Engagement and Relationship Building (Strategies)

One of the effective strategies in church planting is ensuring that the church planter's presence is felt. There must be active community engagement and relationship building to increase the chance of being accepted. R11 emphasized such a strategy, *Ang pinaka epektibo ay ang making friends and offering bible studies or home cell groups ito ay nasa book of Acts. Ang isa sa strategies natin ngayon ay house to house visitation and offering prayers and if we have food to share, we will do it but not necessarily, pagkatapos makikipagkilala ulit tayo yun ang procedure. Anong procedure natin? syempre ilalapit natin yung loob natin sa kanila; hanggang sa makuha natin yung loob nila hindi natin ipagsisiksikan kung ano ang gusto natin dapat makipagkaibigan at hindi lamang po yun pagkatapos nun ay yayain natin sila na ipanalangin, yun ay napakagandang way ng pagplant ng church hindi lang literal napagplant ng church [building] kundi pagplant ng church doon sa puso nila.* (The most effective method is making friends and offering Bible studies or home cell groups, as seen in the Book of Acts. One of our strategies is house-to-house visitation, offering prayers, and sharing food if possible. After that, we should engage with people to build relationships. What is our procedure? Naturally, we should open our hearts to them and earn their trust without being pushy. We should aim to build friendships and invite them to prayer. This is a wonderful way to plant a church—not just by establishing a church building, but by planting the church in their hearts).

Community engagement enables the church to understand the community's needs, challenges, and aspirations, empowering it to design its mission initiatives to address specific issues and make a meaningful difference in people's lives by actively involving

community members in mission activities, establishing partnerships, promoting inclusivity, and empowering individuals to contribute to the common good (Hagley, 2020; Kangwa, 2016; Givens, 2012).

Subcategory 4: Network Enhancement (Consequences)

As a relationship is being built and the community feels the presence of the church planter, the social network of the church mission program improves. More people will hear about the mission in their area, which may qualify for an increased hearing of the Gospel. It is essential to establish a presence by building relationships. R16 is clear on this, *I-establish mo rin 'yong presence mo muna. Yung presence ng grupo, hindi mo sila bibiglain kaagad. Establish a presence, iyong puwede kang mag medical mission doon muna. Medical mission or whatever na para bang pag tulong sa tao. Na sabihin bang medyo mapapa angat 'yong kilay, ano 'yong ginagawa ng mga 'yon?', parang okay 'yong grupo na 'yon ah.* (First, establish your presence. Don't surprise them right away. Build a presence by doing things like medical missions or other forms of assistance. This way, people might think, 'What are those people doing?' and notice that 'This group seems okay.' It's about creating a positive impression and making people curious about your group).

Building relationships is essential for establishing community trust, credibility, and authenticity. Nurturing relationships based on respect, compassion, and empathy creates a supportive environment where individuals feel valued, heard, and cared for. Strong relationships facilitate effective communication, teamwork, and mutual understanding between the church and the community (Perry, 2012; Xiong et al., 2014; Bekkerman & McCallum, 2005).

Subcategory 5: Rural-Urban Disparities (Context)

In church mission, there is a significant difference in doing mission-based programs on rural or urban areas as R6 stated, *“Kasi kung titignan mo ang NWPAC, mayroong rural areas, mayroon ding urbanize areas o mayroon ding rural siya pero going to urbanization, meron ganun. Magkakaiba yung mga approaches.* (Because if you look at NWPAC, there are rural areas, urbanized areas, and areas that are rural but are transitioning to urbanization. The approaches will vary depending on these different contexts). One strategy as suggested by R6 is doing area profiling, *“Iba-barangay profile mo o community profile* (You should profile each barangay or community).” In addition, R14 suggested conducting an area survey and information gathering, *“Kailangan diyang survey or feasibility study kung ano yong venue na yan para alam natin kung ano yong nararapat* (A survey or feasibility study is needed to understand the venue, so we know what is appropriate).”

Rural and urban disparities play a significant role in church mission settings, impacting mission initiatives' outreach, engagement, and effectiveness in different communities. They influence access to resources, healthcare, education, and social services, shaping the challenges and opportunities for churches to fulfill their mission in rural and urban areas (Elson et al., 2020; Singh & Siahpush, 2013; Yu & Zhang, 2020).

Subcategory 6: Inclusivity and Openness (Intervening Condition)

The success of the church planting initiative also depends on the inclusivity and openness of the whole organization and on how much support they are willing to give. One of which is the support of the lay people through the leadership of the district superintendent as expressed by R6, *“Ipartner natin yung opisina ng DS or i-*

institutionalize yung term ko kanina. Tapos gamitin natin yung Lay Servant ministry para mainvolve talaga Layko (We should partner with the office of the District Superintendent or institutionalize the term I mentioned earlier. Then, we can use the Lay Servant Ministry to ensure that laypeople are actively involved).” The support of the Church leadership is also integral. Those in leadership positions should include themselves in the support system as emphasized by R17, “And then the church worker/s of course first and foremost should empower the mission team that is expected of us. They empowered the mission team, and the empowered team must trust the committee's leadership.”

Openness in church mission involves transparency, receptivity, and a willingness to engage with new ideas, perspectives, and approaches to mission. Prioritizing openness, adaptability, innovation, and response to the changing needs and challenges of the community allows for continuous growth, learning, and transformation in mission endeavors (Chung, 2023; Niemandt, 2019; Nel & Schoeman, 2019).

Main Category 6: Church Mission Dynamics Maximization

Figure 8. Church Mission Dynamics

Church Mission Dynamics Maximization emerged from six (6) subcategories, namely, (1) Mission Readiness, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Missional Mobilization as the phenomenon; (3) Programmatic Development to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Community Development as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Mission Harmonization as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Mission Optimization as the intervening condition.

Subcategory 1: Mission Readiness (Causal Condition)

The clarity of vision and mission is crucial in the readiness of the mission program, as it is the starting point. R2 emphasized the need for vision and mission to determine the right approach, “*Kasanno to agchurch plant? kasanno ti ag disciple? kasano nga agrow? Adda kuma amin ngay ti option nga nailatag.* (How to plant a church? How to make

disciples? How to grow? There should be all the options laid out).” Vision and Mission should also be district or annual-wide to have uniformity in mission readiness as R7 stated, *“Nasaysayaat met nga adda kuma, maymaysa a target iti misyon iti tunggal Distrito iti unos iti makatawen* (It would also be beneficial to have a unified mission target for each district every year).”

Readiness embraces risks and opportunities associated with the mission (Shambare & Kgatla, 2018). Therefore, it requires a commitment to unity and a reflection of the desire for a missional church through its vision and mission statements, which are deeply ingrained in its core values (Pillay, 2015; Baron & Pali, 2021). Readiness for mission involves being contextually relevant, understanding the church's role in God's new creation, and actively engaging in the world (Dreyer, 2016).

Subcategory 2: Mission Mobilization (Phenomenon)

Community engagement and building relationships are critical in mobilizing the church planting mission to transform the community effectively through the gospel. As R10 stated, Focus on communities and community-building. It would look more like a social work project but then it would be effective in changing or transforming communities because the gospel that goes with it and of course the holy spirit that empowers is the one that makes the church planting mission program effective. R18 also emphasized building people first, *Start from where the people are kung nasaan sila then build people first before church building, kasi di ba ang ang church naman hindi yung building, hindi lang yung building kundi yung church ay yung tao* (Start from where the people are and focus on building people first before building the church. After all, the church is not just a building; it is the people).

Mission mobilization engages and empowers local church communities for practical mission work, promoting church unity and enhancing the impact of mission activities (Pillay, 2015). Rediscovering the importance of disciple-making, evangelistic activities, and faith-sharing becomes essential for encouraging a culture of outreach within the congregation (Nel & Schoeman, 2019), including establishing mission organizations to respond to the Great Commission and carrying out the church's mission (Nikolajsen, 2013).

Subcategory 3: Programmatic Development (Strategies)

One strategy for attaining missional mobilization is having a church planting curriculum that would equip the church leaders through careful study, training, and seminars that would serve as a programmatic development. As R4 emphasized, *“Magiging effective ito kung ito ay talagang pinagaralan* (This will be effective if thoroughly studied).” R6 also emphasized the organizational part of the district level in implementing training and seminars to have a uniform-wide program development, *Kasi kung minsan, hindi kaya ni local church na magprovide ng training. Pero pwedeng ibigay yun ng District yung training ng church planting. It’s the whole District during the church planting project of ministry* (Sometimes, a local church may be unable to provide training. However, the District can offer training for church planting. It involves the entire District during the church planting project or ministry).

Programmatic development integrates research, practice, and partnerships to ensure the program's effectiveness and sustainability (Harden et al. (2016), which includes the identification of barriers and facilitators, as well as the implementation strategies needed for the successful scale-up of faith-based initiatives, such as health promotion programs

within the church community (Haughton et al., 2020). The church's engagement in mission transformation requires a deep understanding of cultural contexts, integrating gospel values into local traditions, and proactive efforts to transform traditional practices for educational purposes (Widjaja, 2022).

Subcategory 4: Community Development (Consequences)

In attaining community development as a goal, doing a contextual analysis is an essential way to determine and address the needs of a particular community. R8 emphasized this, *Kasama na rin diyan yong pag-aaral doon sa community. Ano ba yong tradition nila don. Ano ba yong lengguwahe nila. Ano yong buhay nila. Ano yong needs nila na maaari tayong makapag-ugnay-ugnay at magiging church kung wala pang church doon* (It also includes studying the community—understanding their traditions, language, way of life, and their needs, so that we can connect with them and establish a church if there isn't one already). R9's statement also confirms this, *Makita tayo dayjay talaga nga area ken needs tapno maaddressan tayo dayjay sitwasyon ka dayta nga lugar* (We need to see the actual area and assess the needs so that we can address the situation in that place).

The missional church promotes community development by encouraging active citizenship and individual collaboration to enhance human circumstances (Msebi, 2022) beyond traditional roles to encompass service, the transformation of society, and the development of communities (Pillay, 2020).

Subcategory 5: Mission Harmonization (Context)

The Organizational structure of the UMC in church planting mission initiatives is imperative in pursuing mission harmonization, as R6 emphasized,

Siguro sa tingin ko magiging masyado din tayong structural din, pagkaisahan yan, yung talagang. Bagamat ang gagawa nun ay local church, baka sa tingin ko, Maganda na institutionalize in the District level yun (I think we might become too focused on structure if we approach it that way. While the local church will carry it out, I believe it would be better if it's institutionalized at the District level). R13 stated that the church council and committees should integrate mission into their program, *Ang council ay minimeeting at committee on evangelism at may asking din naman, ito yung budget na kailangan kung sakaling maprovide ganito bu-bugetan naman ng council at hindi programa yun ng pastor programa na yun ng isang iglesia* (The council meets with the committee on evangelism, and there's also a request for the necessary budget. If the council can provide it, they will allocate the budget. This is not just the pastor's program; it's a program of the entire church).

Mission harmonization emphasizes the need for international, national, and regional structures and organizations to mobilize, empower, and enable local church communities for more effective mission and church unity (Pillay, 2015) ensuring that the church's mission activities align with its theological and historical foundations (Nikolajsen, 2013). Constitutional matters, language policy, finances, ministerial preparation, and unity concerns must be harmonized to create a conducive environment for mission activities (Kganyapa & Kgatla, 2016).

Subcategory 6: Mission Optimization (Intervening Condition)

Strategic planning is essential to optimize church planting mission programs. It allows a practical approach and development, as R1 stated,

Kailangang planuhin kung ano ang mga hakbang na gawin. Hindi lang yung nakaisip na punta tayo doon magmisyon cguro pwede rin yon pero mas effective yung talagang pagplaplano. (We need to plan out the steps to take. It's not just about deciding to go on a mission there—although that might work, a well-thought-out plan would be more effective).

Strategic planning of the District level or committees involved will also determine the right approach to the target area of the church planting mission, as R3 emphasized,

No napan iti distriton masapol nga adda makipagna daytoyen adda committee wenno board nga mangigem iti daytoy tapno isuda iti mangkita nu kasano ti panagimplementariti kadagiti local church. No agprogram ti distrito maipanggep iti daytoy ti church planting masapol nga well organized ken masapol nga maorient well supported kadagiti local church (If the district gets involved, there needs to be a committee or board dedicated to this, so they can oversee how it will be implemented in the local churches. If the district plans to have a church planting program, it must be well-organized and correctly oriented, with strong support from the local churches).

To optimize the church's mission, it is important to integrate various aspects of its mission work, such as evangelism, community outreach, discipleship, and social engagement, into a unified and coherent mission strategy (Hughson, 2011). This includes conducting regular assessments of mission activities, identifying areas for improvement, and implementing innovative approaches to enhance the impact of mission initiatives

(Msebi, 2022). This requires the church to embrace contemporary society's diverse and interconnected nature (Kangwa, 2016).

Main Category 7: Ministry Area Analysis

Figure 9. Ministry Area Analysis

Ministry Area Analysis emerged from six (6) subcategories, namely, (1) Recognizing Discrepancies, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Church Mapping as the phenomenon; (3) Geographic Assessment to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Strategic Execution as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Sociological Sensitivity as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Local engagement as the intervening condition.

Subcategory 1: Recognizing Discrepancies (Causal Condition)

Discrepancies impede mission work. Therefore, such discrepancies must be recognized and addressed for an effective church planting program. R2 emphasized the

occurring discrepancies in terms of spiritual life, *Sapulem ti church growth, masapul ti sama samang panalangin. Daydiay ti mapukpukkaw minsan. Mapukpukkaw diay annointing ni Apo Dios. Wala ang power ang Holy Spirit to convince people* (United prayer is essential to achieve church growth. That is often emphasized—sometimes, the anointing of the Lord is being called for. Without the power of the Holy Spirit, there is no ability to convince people).

Another is the lack of human resources, as R3 stated, *Nakapsut talaga tayo ti church planting ken dayta human resource tayo awan ti agtrabaho. Awan metten ti agpastoren* (We are struggling with church planting, and our human resources are limited. There is no one available to work, and we no longer have pastors).

Recognizing discrepancies is crucial for ensuring the effectiveness and integrity of mission work. For example, disparities in funding practices between African churches and their Western counterparts highlight the need to address financial inequalities in mission practices (Kighoma, 2019). Additionally, conflicts and collaborations among missions due to overlapping spheres of influence underscore the importance of understanding and managing mission rivalries to maintain unity and effectiveness in mission endeavors (Tembo, 2024).

Subcategory 2: Church Mapping (Phenomenon)

One methodology of church mapping is to determine and address the needs of the church structure and the community as R4 stated, *“Yung hinahanap talaga ng mga tao at yung kailangan talaga ng tao* (What people are truly looking for and what they need).”

R1 placed a strong emphasis on addressing the needs,

I-identify talaga yung need. Paano ito isakatuparan para ma meet ang pangangailangan? Paano ito i-apply? Paano ito gawin? Ano ang susunod? Kailangan may susunod pa para mamaintain yung talagang purpose (It's important to truly identify the need. How can this be fulfilled to meet the requirements? How can it be applied? How should it be done? What's the next step? There needs to be a follow-up to maintain the true purpose).

Church mapping encompasses a variety of methodologies and approaches to analyze and understand different aspects of church settings. One approach involves utilizing geographic information system mapping and field surveys to map food sources in church neighborhoods, collecting data on food availability, affordability, quality, marketing, environmental safety, and walkability (Derose et al., 2018). Another aspect of church mapping involves reshaping congregational spaces to create places of prayer for diverse groups, raising questions about discernable differences in prayer content and how they relate to the specificity of place (Siôn, 2017).

Subcategory 3: Geographic Assessment (Strategies)

Conducting an area survey or profiling is essential to assess the geography of the mission area. R8 emphasized this, *We can specify the people living in the community. Halimbawa yong community ng mga magsasaka. Ano ba yong kaugnayan ng pagsasaka sa pananamapalataya? paano ba natin i-u-ugnay yong pagsasaka doon sa ginawa ni Kristo and we can understand that the living of the people there na yong ginawa ng ating Panginoong Hesu Kristo ay naka benefit ang lahat ng tao na mananampalataya sa kaniya* (We can specify the people living in the community, for example, the farming community. What is the connection between farming and faith? How can we relate

farming to what Christ did? By understanding the livelihood of the people there, we can see how the work of our Lord Jesus Christ benefits everyone who believes in Him). R18 also emphasized the need for an area survey to determine the condition of the people, *Maganda yung magkaroon din ng survey. halimbawa pupunta ka sa isang lugar para dun nga magchurch planting mag survey ngayon sa mga tao kasi meron at meron na niyang maibibigay na maganda like malalaman mo na marami pala sa lugar na yun kahit sabihin mong madaming church building doon meron pa rin palang hindi nagsisimba o meron pa rin palang naghahanap* (It would be good to conduct a survey as well. For example, if you're going to a place for church planting, you should survey the people there. This way, you can discover valuable insights, like finding out that even though there are many church buildings in the area, there are still people who don't attend church or are still searching for something).

Geographic assessment analyzes and understands the geographical factors that impact mission work, which include mapping food sources in church neighborhoods to address health disparities, reshaping congregational spaces for prayer to enhance spiritual practices, and mapping ethnic settlement regions to aid in cultural preservation and community development efforts (Yamashita, 2014; Kangwa, 2016; Banusing & Bual, 2021). Understanding the dynamics of the area within church mission settings is vital for effective planning and implementing mission activities.

Subcategory 4: Strategic Execution (Consequences)

The church planting curriculum must be executed to be utilized so that its effectiveness can be observed. R6 emphasized the need for curriculum execution, *Kasi pag aaralan ng church planter yun yung actual implementation niya yun yung mas sa*

tingin ko baka kailangan. Tapos it works sa ano mang context, rural man o urban
(Because the church planter will study that, it's part of the actual implementation, which I believe might be what is needed. This approach works in any context, whether rural or urban). R7 stated that executing the church planting curriculum to experience and understand church planting better, *Bubuo ka ng curriculum tapos yung sasali doon eh hanggang Theory lang. Kahit pinag aralan mo ang church planting, kahit hanggang Theory ka lang, kung wala ka namang experience, useless din yun* (You can create a curriculum, but if those who join only focus on theory, it won't be effective. Even if you have studied church planting, if you only stay in the realm of theory and lack practical experience, it becomes useless).

Strategic planning, which defines the mission, sets the objectives, implements strategies, and establishes control systems, enhances the effectiveness of management throughout the organization and leads to improved performance (Dincer et al., 2006), requires strategic leadership to select and develop future leaders, communicate the church's vision, create organizational structures, make strategic decisions, develop competencies, and instill ethical values into the organizational culture (Mabaso, 2021).

Subcategory 5: Sociological Sensitivity (Context)

Immersion is one way to be sociologically sensitive. Being relevant and contextual requires such sensitivity. Additionally, being sociologically sensitive will enable the church planter to determine the underlying needs of that community and respond properly, as R4 emphasized, *Hindi mo malalaman yung isang bagay kung wala kang immersion kailangan nating magimmerse muna. Yun yung kwan natin para kapag naging ganito ba ah okay. Hindi nalang tayo basta magassume. Iimmerse nating yung mgasarili*

natin sa mga lugar kilalanin natin sila, ilan sila ano yung buhay nila. Yun po yun para mas malaman natin kung ano yung the best way to address them (You won't truly understand something without immersion. We need to immerse ourselves first. This way, when faced with certain situations, we can respond appropriately instead of just assuming. We should immerse ourselves in these communities, get to know the people, understand their lives, and learn how many they are. That's how we can determine the best way to address their needs).

Sociological sensitivity understands and empathizes with the congregation's beliefs, practices, and experiences, allowing the researchers to immerse themselves in the community, worship alongside its members, and grasp the nuances of their religious expressions (Rodrigues, 2023). It provides a sense of collective identity, shared symbols, and moral frameworks that contribute to the coherence of social life (Mattis, 2001).

Subcategory 6: Local Engagement (Intervening Condition)

Intentional local engagement is essential to convey the message of the church's mission to the community. It is also a way to establish the church's presence and implement programs. R3 emphasized that there is a need to go to the community, *Mapan ka ka didiay lugar. Mano ti target mo then no adda dagidiay targets mo? Masapol nga i-orient. Ada ti plano mi nga kastoy, syempre no kayat mo evangelismon ah. Masapol nga ada ti evangelistic program mo* (Go to the place. How many people are you targeting? Once you have identified your targets, they need to be oriented. We have a plan like this, especially if you want to evangelize. It is essential to have an evangelistic program in place).

In addition, R10 expressed that it should be an ecumenical approach to enable people to widen their perspective and choose what suits them best in terms of meaningful and valuable lives, *I would like an ecumenical approach to church planting kasi people don't matter about the label. It is how that movement affects their life and how purposeful may goal na nakikita nila na makakatulong ito. The people also find ways by which their lives can be more meaningful and useful* (An ecumenical approach to church planting is indeed powerful because it transcends denominational boundaries and focuses on what truly matters—impacting lives and providing purpose. When people see that the movement contributes positively to their lives and helps them find meaning and usefulness, they are likelier to engage and commit to it).

Local engagement is the active participation of the church within its immediate community to fulfill its mission objectives. It involves the church working closely with residents, understanding their needs, and tailoring its mission activities to address specific community challenges (Silitonga & Simatupang, 2023). In addition, it is the church's incarnational approach, relationality within the community of believers, and the role of the local church in encouraging creativity, discernment, and ethical engagement (Niemandt, 2012).

RQ 2.5: Emerged challenges encountered in the implementation of the church planting mission

Main Category 8: Navigating Impediments

Figure 10. Navigating Impediments

Navigating Impediments emerged from six (6) subcategories namely, (1) Challenging Conditions, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Church planting mission impediments as the phenomenon; (3) Church Resource Optimization as the strategy to address the phenomenon; (4) Productive Mission Deployment as the consequence of addressing the phenomenon; (5) Institutional Framework as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Congregational Care and Support as the intervening condition.

Subcategory 1: Challenging Conditions (Causal Condition)

Financial availability and support are the most challenging conditions of the church

planting mission. R9's stated that, "*Nu limitasyon, umuna nga talaga nga sumsumrek panunot ko ket kwarta. Isu't mangi limit uray kayat tayo, nu awan iti usaren* (When it comes to limitations, the first thing that always comes to my mind is money. It is what limits us even if we want to do something, especially if there is nothing to use)." The lack of manpower followed this and lay involvement in such mission programs as R6 emphasized, "*Yung Lay involvement, iyon ang kakulangan* (Lay involvement is what is lacking)." And lastly is the overwhelming activities and responsibilities of the church leaders in their respective districts, local churches, and personal lives as R15 stated, "*Ako po kasi bilang lay leader po ng district, kasalukuyan din akong isang nanay, isang negosyante at isa rin pong partner* (As a lay leader of the district, I am currently also a mother, a businesswoman, and a partner)."

One significant obstacle is the theological and missional challenges that inhibit the church from fully engaging in God's mission of justice (Magnusson, 2024). The failure to understand the nature of society and its evolution over time significantly impedes its mission (Rosado, 1988). Church planting also faces obstacles related to financial support as Western churches experience decline, parochialism, and a consumerist lifestyle that reduces funding for cross-cultural missions (Ross, 2005).

Subcategory 2: Church Planting Mission Impediments (Phenomenon)

Impediments are the church planting mission's stumbling blocks, especially when such impediments come unexpectedly. R1 emphasized that, "*Mga bagay na magiging balakid o problema sa pagtanim ng simbaan o pagmimisyon* (There are things that will cause hindrance or problems in church planting or mission work)." R8 stated that through these impediments, church planting mission may stumble, "*Along the way, we can meet*

struggles maaari tayong matumba riyon we are not perfect enough to plant a church
(Along the way, we may encounter struggles; we might stumble because we are not perfect enough to plant a church).” R13 expounded that impediments include personal levels, *“Pati din ikaw humihina ka din. Kaya madaming challenges ang problema mo sayo, problema mo sa kasama mo, at problema mo sa trabaho, tao tayo lalaki o minsan babae may mga challenges na talagang struggle talaga* (You also become weak. That is why there are so many challenges—your problems with yourself, your problems with others, and your problems at work. We are human, whether man or woman, and there are challenges that are truly struggles).”

The personality traits of church planters and leaders play a crucial role in the success of church planting initiatives, such as agreeableness and neuroticism that can influence how church planters navigate challenges and opportunities in establishing new faith communities, especially in under-resourced contexts (Foppen et al., 2018). There is a risk of mission drift in church planting efforts, where the focus shifts from a passion for reaching the lost to a pursuit of territorial expansion and structural growth. Without a careful review of strategies, there is a danger of losing sight of the core mission of spreading the gospel and nurturing faith communities (Fagbemi, 2014).

Subcategory 3: Church Resource Optimizations (Strategies)

R2 emphasized proper allocation of church resources in discipleship making which is a prime strategy in church planting, *“Amin kuma nga resources suportaan na diay making disciples tapno makagrow tayo, maka church planting tayo pay* (All resources should support making disciples so that we can grow and even do church planting).” Resources should not only be limited to the grassroots level but also in higher

organizational levels like districts as R3 stated, *“Ti distrito isu ti mangfinance mangsupport ti sweldo ti trabahador nga mapan idia y nga ti sweldo na daydiay minimum salary ti annual tapno awan ti problema na nga awan met sweldo kasdiay* (The district should be the one that will finance and support the salary of the worker who will go there [to plant churches], ensuring that the salary is at least the minimum annual level salary so there will not be any issues with unpaid wages).” Disciple-making is a strong strategy as it adds to the manpower needed in church planting missions. As R4 emphasized, *“Intentional talaga na disciplemaker na talagang kasama mo sa pagchuchurch planting. You need to identify kung sino yung mga taong may puso sa mga yon* (It is intentional to have a disciple-maker who is truly with you in church planting. You need to identify who are the people who have a heart for that).”

Church resources must be strategically utilized to maximize their impact on various aspects such as health promotion, community development, and disaster recovery. Leveraging churches as intervention platforms has been recognized as effective in reaching diverse populations (Lemacks et al., 2018; Ford, 2013). It also involves programs that capitalize on the existing community networks and resources within churches to address disparities and improve overall well-being (Ford, 2013; Allen et al., 2014).

Subcategory 4: Productive Mission Deployment (Consequences)

Commitment, motivation, and persistence of church leaders involved in church planting missions are integral in attaining a productive mission deployment. R11 made an emphasis on this, *Huwag titigil isipin nating part ito ng pagmimisyon regarding church planting, minsan tama yun nakakaranas tayo ng kahinaan or parang napapaisip*

tayo na tutuloy ko pa ba o hindi na, maaaring hindi pa panahon na sila'y mahinog darating at darating din yung panahon na yung kailangan lang ng tiyaga ang isipin natin magpatuloy tayo (Don't stop; let's remember that this is part of the mission regarding church planting. Sometimes it's true that we experience weakness, or we start questioning whether to continue or not. It might not be the right time for them to mature, but the time will come. We just need to be patient and keep going).

And also R15 gave an importance to commitment and giving your best to God, *Sa tingin ko po kasi lahat ng gagawin mo para kay Lord so hahanapan mo talaga po yun ng oras at bilang isang anak ng Diyos o bilang isang volunteer po na worker ay ipoprovide mo yung best effort mo* (I believe that everything you do for the Lord, you will really find time for it. As a child of God or as a volunteer worker, you will give your best effort).

Mission deployment has a transformative impact on both the individuals participating and the communities they serve (Trinitapoli & Vaisey, 2009). It engages in service, fellowship, and proclamation (Kangwa, 2016), as well as factors such as the mission's objectives, available resources, and desired outcomes. A clear mission statement that defines the purpose and identity of the organization is important (Sider & Unruh, 2004).

Subcategory 5: Institutional Framework (Context)

The UMC appointment system was observed in the context of church planting impediments. Church planting mission requires a church worker to stay in that appointment longer. R2 emphasized this, *Ti Sistema tayo nga Methodist daydiay ialis alis da ti pastor ket ti church planting dapat bumayag ka nga talaga dita. Ti Sistema tayo*

ngay nga alis nga alis, awan, kasla mauma ak metten nga agpaalis alisen. Ta no alis ka nga alis kasla met lumangayo nga imulam ialis mo. Diay pastor kasla agadjust manen idiay banger, diay mission nga pinanawan nga irugrugin agadjust manen diay sumaruno (Our Methodist system, where pastors are frequently reassigned, requires you to stay longer in church planting. However, with our constant reassignment system, it feels tiring to keep transferring people. If you keep moving, it is like uprooting what you have planted when reassigning someone. The pastor must adjust again to the new place, and the mission they started must be adjusted by the next one).

The UMC operates under a connectional system, where local churches are connected to regional conferences, which are part of the broader denomination. This system allows for shared governance, resources, and decision-making processes across the church hierarchy (Gearhart, 2020). The itinerant system, a distinctive feature of the UMC, involves bishops' clergy assignment to different churches, promoting mobility and adaptability among ministers (Proeschold-Bell et al., 2009).

Subcategory 6: Congregational Care and Support (Intervening Condition)

The establishment of a support system is crucial in navigating church planting impediments. Support from the members through prayers, finances, etc., will undoubtedly motivate the church planting endeavors. As R6 stated, *Kasi yung church na established kasi, susupport in terms of prayer. Kasi hindi sila makakapag preach, hindi yung mag church planting mismo. Pero sabi nila, pupwedeng mag volunteer kami na magpreach na mag pipray kami for the project, mag support kami financially sa project. Ganun yun. pupwedeng ganun din yung support din nila sa ngayon* (Because the established church will support in terms of prayer. They won't be the ones to preach or

do the church planting themselves. But they said they can volunteer to preach, pray for the project, and provide financial support. That's how it works. That might be the kind of support they can offer for now).

Trusting in God's provisions also has a positive impact in overcoming challenges in the church planting mission. As R13 emphasized, *Yun yung mga estratehiya para sa ganun ang pagtatanim ng iglesia mas maunlad very victorious naman tutulungan ka ng panginoon dun, bigla na lang na may gagamitin ng panginoon na hindi mo alam* (Those are the strategies to ensure that church planting becomes more prosperous and victorious. The Lord will help you with that; suddenly, the Lord will use someone you didn't expect). Implementing needs-oriented diaconal ministry can contribute to building a solid and vibrant church community (Yun, 2012). By addressing the practical needs of individuals within the congregation, such as through social activities, pastoral ministry, and fellowship, churches can create a supportive environment that nurtures spiritual growth and community engagement (Adams & Stark, 2019). In addition, recognizing the strengths and empowerment of the church members will bring a significant positive contribution to the mission and ministry of the church (Herwinesastra et al., 2023).

RQ 3. The Proposed Church Planting Mission Curriculum in Wesleyan Identity in the Context of NWPAC.

The Grounded Theory

The Grounded Theory that emerged for the Church Planting Mission Curriculum in line with the Wesleyan Identity for the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference church leaders is, "A Way Forward: PANAGMULA Church Planting Curriculum."

The Church Planting Curriculum is a way forward for church planting mission endeavors because it serves as the basis or foundation to be studied as R1 stated, “*Ito ‘yung basehan o tungtungan tapno maadal* (This is the basis or reference for studying).” R11 emphasized having a church planting curriculum because it pertains to growth, multiplication, or sharing the word of God so that at least more people can be saved, “*Dahil ito ay tumutukoy sa paglago, pag paparami o pagbabahagi nang salita ng Diyos para at least mas marami pa ang maliligtas* (This refers to the growth, propagation, or sharing of the word of God so that more people may be saved).” Church Planting curriculum also helps to sustain the sprouting or growth of churches as R16 emphasized, “*Ma-sustain ‘yong pag sprout o ‘yong mga pag tubo ng mga churches* (To sustain the sprouting or growth of churches).”

PANAGMULA is an Ilocano term that is translated into Planting. PANAGMULA, the core category, is an abbreviation of the eight (8) main categories.

- P - Planning and Implementation: This involves the strategic planning and execution of church planting initiatives.
- A - Analysis of Ministry Areas: Conducting a thorough analysis of ministry areas to understand the context and needs.
- N - Navigating Impediments: Addressing and overcoming challenges and obstacles in church planting efforts.
- A - Assessment Framework: Developing a systematic framework for evaluating church planting activities.
- G - Grounded Methodology: Using a contextual methodology that is rooted in the specific cultural and social context.

- M - Missiological Identity: Emphasizing Wesleyan identity in church planting missiology.
- U - Utilizing Dynamics: Maximizing church mission dynamics for effective outreach and growth.
- L - Local Engagement: Engaging with the local community to build relationships and foster support.
- A - Adaptive Strategies: Adapting strategies to fit each planting mission's unique needs and circumstances.

According to Mthethwa-Kunene et al. (2022), establishing a Church planting curriculum provides a structured framework for training individuals to establish new congregations. Joshua (2010) further explained that by focusing on formal curricula that include specific courses and field practicum, church planting initiatives can ensure a comprehensive educational approach for ministerial education. The involvement of churches in curriculum management and quality assurance is essential in higher education settings, emphasizing the significance of active church participation in shaping educational programs (Basome, S. Mwangi, P. & Konso G, 2023).

Emerged Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Emerged Conceptual Framework

A Way Forward: P.A.N.A.G.M.U.L.A. Church Planting Mission Curriculum is a practical approach toward church planting mission initiatives and is ideally suited to the unique context of the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference (NWPAC). The

PANAGMULA components are as follows:

Assessment Framework: The Church Planting Curriculum as an assessment framework, enables the learners to determine the needs (Critical Needs Analysis in Church Planting Initiatives) and context of NWPAC (Contextualization) toward a mission-focused program (Church Planting Mission Engagement), enhancing the church's planting mission endeavors (Enhanced Church Planting Efficacy) as a learning material for church leaders (Educational resource). According to Peterson et al. (2002),

integrating such assessment in church mission programs helps identify critical elements to be addressed to achieve effective community programs. There must be collaboration between the UMC organization and the community to go hand in hand regarding program design and delivery for enhanced recruitment of human resources, participation, and sustainability (Campbell et al., 2007).

Grounded Methodology: A Church Planting Curriculum, integrated with a grounded methodology, enables the church leaders (Collaboration of church workers and lay people) to learn, understand, and adapt to the community's tradition and way of life (Contextual Adaptation). This is an integral part of the mission due to varying social factors (Social Geography) that must be considered to undertake the right approach to the mission program (Contextual Missiology). The prime strategy is to engage directly with the community to experience the reality of the people's lives, creating a broader perspective from the point of view of the church planter (Cultural Immersion). In doing so, the church planter will understand how the community works and use further appropriate ethical strategies for bringing the gospel to the people (Community Dynamics). According to Mpofu et al. (2008), Grounded methodology enables the church planting mission to be relevant to the community. As such, the resulting curriculum will address relevant issues and be meaningful to the community. Experiencing local community cultural perspectives bridges the gap between theory and practice, increasing the relevance and effectiveness of the curriculum for the target audience (Jawabreh & Gündüz, 2021).

Church Planting Missiology: The Church Planting Curriculum, integrated with The Missiology of Church Planting, ensures that the curriculum follows the biblical and

theological guidelines of the church planting mission (The Biblical and Theological Philosophy of Church Planting), emphasizing the significance of the Great Commission and the Pentecost experience as founding biblical basis such mission programs. The Pentecost experience is vital in guiding the church planting mission program because it enables the believers to receive spiritual gifts from the Holy Spirit to be utilized for mission purposes (Spiritual Empowerment). According to Rance (2011), church planting should focus on establishing, growing, and multiplying Christian churches to fulfill the Great Commission of making disciples of all nations, emphasizing the need for in-depth training of church leaders as participants (Human Resources) in this mission (Intentional Discipleship Programs). Paas (2012) added that church plants are seen as experimental grounds for church mission endeavors, which become the testing ground of the vision and mission (Vision and Mission Articulation).

Missiological Identity: The Church Planting Curriculum, integrated with The missiological identity ensures that the curriculum will be a Wesleyan approach (Wesleyan Identity Integration) that will further solidify the understanding of faith through the Wesleyan Quadrilateral framework (Guide in Understanding Faith) namely the scripture as the primary basis, followed by the tradition of the early church and the methodist lay movement, then the believer's experiences of God, and lastly the reason which enables the believers to rationalize their faith through societal actions and engagements also called Social Holiness (Spiritual Growth). As Boaheng (2020) mentioned, Wesleyan Spirituality emphasizes holiness, discipline, and faith in a believer's life in both intra and interpersonal aspects (Educational Adaptability), maintaining a balance of personal piety and acts of mercy for transformation and social

justice (Relevance). Wesleyan Identity is a framework for Christian faith and practice for pursuing Christian perfection rooted in love, hence the importance of learning and understanding such framework (Education Among Church Leaders). The Wesleyan tradition of grace has been given a deep and significant meaning in the lives of believers, manifesting God's ultimate love in the lives of the believers and society where they belong, engaging in acts of mercy, justice, and compassion (Cordery, 2006).

Strategic Planning and Implementation: The Church Planting Curriculum, integrated with Strategic planning and implementation in the church planting mission, enables a well-executed program with clarified goals, surveyed areas, informed situations, and the sustenance of the program (Practical Implementation). Welch (2023) explained that Strategic planning requires a structured process that involves formulating a step-by-step strategy to facilitate organizational growth and development (Optimal Missional Strategy). As Welch (2023) noted, the effectiveness of strategic planning is contingent on its implementation. Organizations that strategically implement their plans will likely achieve their goals and objectives. One strategy is to actively engage with the community and establish the presence of the church (Community Engagement and Relationship Building). In doing so, more people will hear and see the mission of the church, inciting more people to be interested and involved (Network Enhancement). Different communities have different needs and contexts. Therefore, learning and understanding these differences is imperative to effectively and ethically approach the mission (Rural-Urban Disparities). Practicing a non-exclusive denominational approach will invite more people, especially those who do not want to have a denominational identity and are limited to hearing the gospel alone. Such a strategy would also prevent proselytizing

(Inclusivity and Openness). Rojas-Arce et al. (2012) further add that Strategic planning provides flexibility in management, allowing organizations to adapt to changing environments, which is evident in in community mission programs.

Church Mission Dynamics Maximization: The Church Planting Curriculum, integrated with Church Mission Dynamics Maximization, will enable an effective church planting mission initiative (Missional Mobilization). By maximizing the church mission dynamics, preparations, plannings, and resources will have a clarity of direction and road maps (Mission Optimization) to effectively apply such mission programs (Mission Readiness) initiated through the development of detailed and systematic mission programs (Programmatic Development). Developing intentional mission programs for the community is vital to address impending needs, making the church planting mission relevant, and leading to the development of the community in a gospel-based manner through social ministries as part of the Wesleyan Identity (Community Development). Pillay, 2015; Breedt & Niemandt (2013) emphasized the need to engage in relational leadership, promotion of unity in mission, and empowerment of local church communities for effective mission outreach. To achieve such mission dynamics, different committees and levels of the UMC organization should go hand in hand with a common goal, in alignment with the biblical and theological principles of the church planting mission (Mission Harmonization). Nkansah-Obrempong (2017) noted that the church's mission activities are rooted in the core teachings of Jesus Christ, focusing on evangelism, discipleship, and service to humanity and creation.

Ministry Area Analysis: The Church Planting Curriculum, integrated with Ministry area analysis, enables the learners to strategically gather information regarding the area of

focus to determine and address the needs of the church planting mission (Recognizing Discrepancies). According to Williams (2011), ministry area analysis critically examines socio-cultural factors (Sociological Sensitivity), ecclesiology, and orthodoxy status to develop compelling mission and ministry strategies (Church Mapping). Msebi, 2022 further adds that understanding the role of a missional church as a community united in living out God's mission within a specific neighborhood (Local Engagement) is essential for impactful community development initiatives (Geographic Assessment). During challenging times like the COVID-19 pandemic, as Sastrohartoyo et al. (2021) stated, churches are to realign their ministerial focus, adapt strategies, and determine the priority of their ministry to continue fulfilling the Great Commission (Strategic Execution).

Navigating Impediments: The Church Planting Curriculum, integrated Navigating impediments, enables the learners to address difficult situations (Challenging Conditions) faced in church planting mission initiatives because such challenges will always be present (Church planting mission impediments). According to Msebi (2022), navigating impediments in church missions involves addressing various challenges that can hinder the effectiveness of spreading the gospel and serving communities. As McMillan (1987) viewed it, one significant impediment is the lack of adequate material resources. This can hamper the Church's mission to reach and teach all nations, emphasizing the need for church resource utilization (Church Resource Optimization). Msebi (2022) further adds that challenges such as religious pluralization and racial polarization can impede missional churches from engaging effectively in community development. To overcome these obstacles, according to Herbst (2020), the church must move beyond traditional structures and programs to enhance its mission. Churches must

renew and reorient their mission to adapt to changing circumstances (Productive Mission Deployment). In support of this, Johnson (2004) iterates that the church must move beyond traditional structures and programs to enhance its mission in the 21st century (Institutional Framework). Lastly, Adams and Stark (2019) emphasized that the practical needs of individuals should be addressed within the congregation, such as through social activities, pastoral ministry, and fellowship. Herwinesastra et al. (2023) stated that churches can create a supportive environment that nurtures spiritual growth and community engagement, recognizes the unique strengths and potential of church members, and empowers them to contribute meaningfully to the mission and ministry of the church (Congregational Care and Support).

Theoretical Contribution: The emerging conceptual framework introduces a church planting mission model through a curriculum rooted in Wesleyan Identity and contextually relevant to the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference. It bridges the gap between theory and practice by presenting a highly applicable and relevant model for church leaders' learning, training, and participation in church-planting missions to further the Gospel in more areas. Added to this is a variety of approaching church planting mission with the following strategic components of Assessment Framework, Grounded Methodology, Church Planting Missiology, Missiological Identity, Strategic Planning and Implementation, Church Mission Dynamics Maximization, Ministry Area Analysis, and Navigating Impediments, to ensure a well-equipped church in church planting mission endeavors.

CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This dissertation aimed to develop a Church Planting Curriculum rooted in Wesleyan Identity for the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference (NWPAC). The findings below address the research questions:

RQ 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

There were 18 respondents interviewed across the six (6) districts of NWPAC. Six (6) were Lay people with different leadership backgrounds, including Annual Conference and District lay leaders, Deaconesses, and Wesleyan University faculty. Twelve (12) were Ordained Elders of the UMC with leadership roles as District Superintendents, Board of Ordained Ministry Chairperson, District Committee on Ministry Chairperson, Mission Pastors, Bible translators, and Administrative Pastors. All respondents were known to have experience and knowledge regarding church planting mission programs.

RQ 2. Contextual Components for Developing a Church Planting Curriculum in Wesleyan Identity

2.1. Need for a Church Planting Curriculum

The Assessment Framework enables the learners to determine the needs (and context) of NWPAC toward a mission-focused program, enhancing the church's planting mission endeavors as learning material for church leaders. It emerged from six (6) subcategories, namely, (1) Church Planting Mission Engagement which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Educational resource as the phenomenon; (3) Critical Needs Analysis in Church Planting Initiatives as the strategy to achieve the phenomenon;

(4) Enhanced Church Planting Efficacy as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Contextualization as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Organizational Structure as the intervening condition.

Grounded Methodology enables church leaders to learn, understand, and adapt to the community's traditions and way of life. It emerged from six (6) subcategories, namely, (1) Social Geography, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Contextual Adaptation as the phenomenon; (3) Cultural Immersion as the strategy to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Contextual Missiology as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Community Dynamics as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Collaboration of church workers and lay people as the intervening condition.

2.2. Biblical and Theological Foundation

Church Planting Missiology ensures that the curriculum follows the biblical and theological guidelines of the church planting mission, emphasizing the significance of the Great Commission and the Pentecost experience as the biblical basis for such mission programs. It emerged from six (6) subcategories namely, (1) Church Planting Mission Basis, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) The Biblical and Theological Philosophy of Church Planting as the phenomenon; (3) Intentional Discipleship Programs as the strategy to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Vision and Mission Articulation as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Spiritual Empowerment as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Human Resource as the intervening condition.

2.3. Significance of Wesleyan Identity in Curriculum Development

Missiological Identity ensures the curriculum adopts the Wesleyan approach further to solidify faith's understanding through the Wesleyan Quadrilateral framework. It emerged from six (6) subcategories, namely, (1) Guide in Understanding Faith, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Wesleyan Identity Integration as the phenomenon; (3) Education Among Church Leaders as the strategy to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Spiritual Growth as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Relevance as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Educational Adaptability as the intervening condition.

2.4. Practical Strategies for Church Planting Mission Curriculum

Strategic Planning and Implementation enables a well-executed program with clarified goals, surveyed areas, informed situations, and sustained program success. It emerged from six (6) subcategories, namely, (1) Optimal Missional Strategy, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Practical Implementation as the phenomenon; (3) Community Engagement and Relationship Building as the strategy to achieve the p, phenomenon; (4) Network Enhancement as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Rural-Urban Disparities as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Inclusivity and Openness as the intervening condition.

Church Mission Dynamics Maximization enables an effective church planting mission initiative by maximizing church mission dynamics, preparations, planning, and resources to achieve clarity of direction and road maps for effectively applying such mission programs. It emerged from six (6) subcategories, namely, (1) Mission Readiness, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Missional Mobilization as the

phenomenon; (3) Programmatic Development to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Community Development as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Mission Harmonization as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Mission Optimization as the intervening condition.

Ministry Area Analysis enables the learners to strategically gather information regarding the area of focus to determine and address the needs of the church planting mission. It emerged from six (6) subcategories, namely, (1) Recognizing Discrepancies, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Church Mapping as the phenomenon; (3) Geographic Assessment to achieve the phenomenon; (4) Strategic Execution as the consequence of achieving the phenomenon; (5) Sociological Sensitivity as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Local engagement as the intervening condition.

2.5. Challenges in Implementing Church Planting Missions

Navigating Impediments enables the learners to address difficult situations faced in church planting mission initiatives because such challenges will always be present. It emerged from six (6) subcategories namely, (1) Challenging Conditions, which is the causal condition for the phenomenon; (2) Church planting mission impediments as the phenomenon; (3) Church Resource Optimization as the strategy to address the phenomenon; (4) Productive Mission Deployment as the consequence of addressing the phenomenon; (5) Institutional Framework as the context of the phenomenon; and (6) Congregational Care and Support as the intervening condition.

RQ 3. Proposed Church Planting Mission Curriculum in Wesleyan Identity

The Grounded Theory emerged as the Church Planting Mission Curriculum in line with the Wesleyan Identity for the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference church leaders is, A Way Forward: PANAGMULA Church Planting Curriculum.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study utilizing the grounded theory analysis, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The lay and church workers' respondents have varying backgrounds, including their leadership roles and church appointment setup, which have provided a grounded theory that is contextually relevant. This theory significantly expressed the need for the curriculum to be adaptable to local contexts and community engagement. The experiences and ideas of the respondents are the pivotal points that enabled this research to derive a church-planting curriculum framework.
2. The Church Planting Missiology component ensures the curriculum aligns with core biblical and theological principles central to the Wesleyan tradition. Focusing on critical events like the Great Commission and Pentecost, the curriculum stays faithful to foundational Christian teachings, providing spiritual depth and doctrinal clarity.
3. The curriculum integrates the Wesleyan Quadrilateral framework, which is crucial for helping leaders deepen their understanding and practice of faith, empowering spiritual growth and educational flexibility among church leaders. It also ensures that the curriculum is relevant to current challenges and remains responsive to the changing needs of the communities.

4. The curriculum component includes practical methods such as strategic planning, community involvement, and mission preparedness, ensuring that the church planting efforts are well-planned and sustainable in the long term. One key factor is its design to address differences between rural and urban settings, promoting inclusivity and optimizing resources.

5. The curriculum also emphasizes the significance of inevitable challenges in church planting. It provides strategies to navigate these difficulties, preparing the church leaders to overcome obstacles, use resources best, and execute mission initiatives effectively.

6. The "A Way Forward: PANAGMULA Church Planting Curriculum" presents a strong, contextually relevant, and theologically sound framework designed for NWPAC. It is theoretically appropriate and practically helpful for the real challenges that church leaders face in this setting. The respondents' varying leadership backgrounds, inclusion of different strategies for social and cultural contexts, and integration of the Wesleyan Identity make the curriculum well-equipped to support church planting efforts in the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference.

RECOMMENDATION

It is hereby then that the following recommendations are presented:

1. Further study should be conducted in more and expanded areas including other denominations, to determine other components that would be beneficial in church planting mission endeavors, especially in the 21st century mission approach;
2. The "A Way Forward: Panagmula Church Planting Mission Curriculum" be implemented by the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference through the different

church agencies according to their contexts and needs, and evaluate the curriculum for improvement and development;

3. That a seminar or a training course be laid out down to the grassroots level of NWPAC on A Way Forward: Panagmula Church Planting Mission Curriculum to equip both church workers and lay people in promoting and practicing church planting mission programs;

4. That the "A Way Forward: Panagmula Church Planting Mission Curriculum" be adapted by other Annual Conferences according to their contexts and needs, and evaluate the curriculum for improvement and development;

5. The "A Way Forward: Panagmula Church Planting Mission Curriculum" be published as a research article and as a book for church mission reference and guide.

Appendix 1. Panagmula Church Planting Curriculum

to the P.A.N.A.G.M.U.L.A. Church Planting Training Manual!

Hey there, future church planter! Are you ready for an incredible journey? You're about to embark on an amazing adventure that will change your life and the lives of many others. This training manual is your trusty guide as you learn how to start a new church in your area. Don't worry if it sounds like a big job – we'll take it step by step, and before you know it, you'll be ready to plant a church that will shine God's love in your community!

First things first – what does P.A.N.A.G.M.U.L.A. stand for? It's a special acronym that reminds us of the important parts of church planting. PANAGMULA is an Ilocano term that is translated into Planting, an abbreviation of the eight (8) components of this training manual.

- P - Planning and Implementation:** The strategic planning and execution of church planting initiatives.
- A - Analysis of Ministry Areas:** Conducting a thorough analysis of ministry areas to understand the context and needs.
- N - Navigating Impediments:** Addressing and overcoming challenges and obstacles in church planting efforts.
- A - Assessment Framework:** Developing a systematic framework for evaluating church planting activities.
- G - Grounded Methodology:** Using a contextual methodology that is rooted in the specific cultural and social context.
- M - Missiological Identity:** Emphasizing Wesleyan identity in church planting missiology.
- U - Utilizing Dynamics:** Maximizing church mission dynamics for effective outreach and growth.
- L - Local Engagement:** Engaging with the local community to build relationships and foster support.
- A - Adaptive Strategies:** Adapting strategies to fit each planting mission's unique needs and circumstances.

Throughout this manual, we'll explore each of these areas in depth. It's like we're going on a treasure hunt, and each module is a map leading us to a new discovery about church planting!

Now, you might be wondering, "Can I really plant a church?" The answer is a big, hearty YES! With God's help and this training, you absolutely can. Remember what Jesus said in Matthew 17:20: "If you have faith as small as a mustard seed, you can say to this mountain, 'Move from here to there,' and it will move. Nothing will be impossible for you." Starting a church might seem like moving a mountain, but with faith in God and the tools you'll learn here, you can do it!

This manual is designed to be friendly and easy to understand. We've broken everything down into bite-sized pieces so you won't feel overwhelmed. It's like eating a delicious meal – you take one bite at a time, and before you know it, you've enjoyed the whole thing!

Here's what you can expect in each module:

1. A friendly introduction that explains what you'll learn
2. Fun activities that help you practice what you're learning
3. Bible verses that remind us of God's guidance
4. Real-life examples that show how others have planted churches
5. A checklist of things to do before moving to the next module

We'll cover everything from understanding your community to solving problems that might come up when starting a church. It's like we're building a house – we'll start with the foundation and work our way up until we have a beautiful, strong church that can weather any storm. Remember, you're not alone on this journey. Just like the disciples had each other and Jesus had his twelve, you have a whole community of support behind you. Your Church leaders, fellow church planters, and most importantly, God Himself, are all cheering you on! As we go through this manual together, keep in mind the words of the apostle Paul in Philippians 1:6: "Being confident of this, that he who began a good work in you will carry it on to completion until the day of Christ Jesus." God has called you to this important work, and He will be with you every step of the way.

So, are you ready to start this exciting journey of church planting? Grab your Bible, a notebook, and your sense of adventure. Let's dive in and discover how you can plant a church that will bring hope, love, and transformation to your community. Together, with God's help, we're going to do something amazing. Let's get started!

How to Use This Manual

1. **In-Person Training:** Follow the lesson plans sequentially, engaging in discussions, activities, and assessments as a group.
2. **Modular Learning:** Work through each module independently, completing readings, reflections, and assignments at your own pace.
3. **Blended Approach:** Combine self-study with periodic group sessions for discussion and collaborative activities.

Each module includes:

- Introduction
- Learning Outcomes
- Preparation
- Lectures, Activities, Panel Discussions, and Workshops
- Reflection Questions
- Case Studies
- Checklist
- Assessment

Module 1: Understanding Your Community

In this first module, we're going to learn all about understanding your community. It's like being a detective, but instead of solving crimes, you're discovering what makes your neighborhood special!

Jesus always knew the people He was talking to. Remember when He met the Samaritan woman at the well? He understood her situation and spoke to her heart. That's what we want to do too!

In this module, you'll learn how to:

1. Conduct a community needs assessment (Watch and listen to what's happening around you);
2. Apply effective information gathering techniques (Talk to different people in your community);
3. Analyze and interpret community data (Find out what your neighbors really need);
4. Demonstrate cultural sensitivity in community research (Discover the special things about where you live).

By the end, you'll know your community like the back of your hand. Isn't that exciting? Let's get started on this adventure together!

Day 1: Introduction to Community Research (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Discussion	Assignment
<p>Opening Prayer and Reflection (15 minutes)</p> <p>Read Matthew 9:35-36</p> <p>Discuss: How did Jesus demonstrate understanding of community needs?</p>	<p>Importance of Community Understanding (45 minutes)</p> <p>Define community needs assessment</p> <p>Explain the role of research in effective church planting</p> <p>Discuss biblical examples of community engagement</p>	<p>Community Mapping (60 minutes)</p> <p>In small groups, create a visual map of your local community</p> <p>Identify key landmarks, resources, and potential needs</p>	<p>Sharing Insights (30 minutes)</p> <p>Groups present their community maps</p> <p>Identify common themes and unique observations</p>	<p>Research on survey design and interview techniques</p> <p>Make 10 questions for a community survey</p>

Day 2: Information Gathering Techniques (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Assignment
Review and Prayer (15 minutes) Recap previous session Read John 4:7-26 and discuss Jesus' approach to gathering information	Survey and Interview Techniques (45 minutes) Types of surveys: online, inperson, phone Crafting effective questions Active listening skills for interviews	Interview Practice (60 minutes) In pairs, practice conducting interviews using drafted questions Provide peer feedback on questioning and listening skills	Refining Survey Questions (45 minutes) As a group, review and refine community survey questions Discuss ethical considerations in community research	Conduct 5 practice surveys or interviews with friends/family Write a brief reflection on the experience
Day 3: Data Analysis and Cultural Sensitivity (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Activity	Assignment
Opening Prayer and Sharing (20 minutes) Share experiences from homework interviews	Understanding Community Data (45 minutes) Basic data analysis techniques Identifying patterns and trends Avoiding bias in interpretation	Case Study Analysis (60 minutes) In small groups, analyze a provided case study of community data Present findings and recommendations to the larger group	Cultural Sensitivity (45 minutes) Read Ephesians 4:32 Discuss the importance of kindness and respect in community research Share experiences of cultural misunderstandings and lessons learned	Final Reflection and Planning (30 minutes) Individual reflection: Write a personal plan for conducting community research Share plans with a partner for feedback

Case Study: The Barangay Outreach Challenge

Rev. Maria Santos, a newly appointed church worker, arrived in a small rural community in Pangasinan. Eager to start a new church plant, she immediately began conducting surveys and interviews with local residents. However, she quickly realized that many community members were hesitant to speak with her, and some even seemed suspicious of her intentions.

After reflection and prayer, Rev. Santos decided to take a step back and immerse herself in community life before continuing her formal research. She started attending local events, volunteering at the community center, and simply spending time in public spaces to observe daily life. Through this approach, she gradually built relationships and gained insights into the community's needs and dynamics that weren't apparent from her initial surveys.

Key lessons:

1. The importance of building trust before conducting formal research
2. The value of participant observation in understanding community dynamics
3. The need for flexibility and patience in community engagement

Checklist:

- Spend at least 30 minutes observing daily life in a public space (e.g., market, plaza, or park) and record your observations.
- Conduct informal conversations with 3 community members from different demographics (e.g., youth, elderly, professionals, stay-at-home parents).
- Attend a local community event (e.g., fiesta, barangay meeting, school program) and reflect on its significance.
- Create a hand-drawn map of the community, highlighting key landmarks, gathering places, and resources.
- Identify and interview 1 community leader (e.g., barangay captain, school principal, respected elder) about local needs and challenges.

Module 2: Living and Working in Your Community

Welcome back, friend! Now that you know your community, it's time to really become a part of it. This module is all about living and working right where God has placed you.

Think about Jesus. He didn't just visit Earth; He became one of us! The Bible says, "The Word became flesh and made his dwelling among us" (John 1:14). That's what we're going to do too – really live among the people we want to serve.

In this module, you'll learn how to:

1. Make friends with your neighbors
2. Get involved in local activities
3. Understand the way people think and live
4. Show God's love in practical ways

It's going to be fun, and sometimes a bit challenging. But don't worry – we'll go through it together. Are you ready to dive in and become a real part of your community? Let's go!

Day 1: Immersion in Community Life (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Panel Discussion	Activity	Assignment
<p>Opening Prayer and Reflection (15 minutes)</p> <p>Read John 1:14</p> <p>Discuss: What does it mean to "dwell among" the people we serve?</p>	<p>Principles of Community Immersion (45 minutes)</p> <p>Importance of longterm presence</p> <p>Balancing participation and observation</p> <p>Ethical considerations in community involvement</p>	<p>Community Engagement Experiences (60 minutes)</p> <p>Invite 23 experienced community workers or longterm missionaries</p> <p>Q&A session on challenges and best practices</p>	<p>Community Engagement Planning (45 minutes)</p> <p>In small groups, brainstorm ways to engage with different community segments (youth, elderly, professionals, etc.)</p> <p>Create a weekly schedule of community activities to participate in</p>	<p>Begin a "Community Engagement Journal" to document observations and reflections</p>

Day 2: Understanding Community Dynamics (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity 1	Activity 2	Assignment
<p>Review and Prayer (15 minutes) Share insights from Community Engagement Journals</p>	<p>Social Structures and Community Dynamics (45 minutes) Key sociological concepts relevant to community work Identifying formal and informal leadership structures Understanding cultural norms and values</p>	<p>Community Mapping Revisited (60 minutes) Return to community maps from Module 1 Add layers of social connections, power structures, and cultural elements</p>	<p>Case Study Analysis (45 minutes) In groups, analyze a complex community scenario Present strategies for navigating the social landscape effectively</p>	<p>Conduct an informal interview with a community leader Reflect on how their insights align with or challenge your observations</p>
Day 3: Teamwork and Collaboration (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Assignment
<p>Opening Prayer and Sharing (20 minutes) Discuss insights from community leader interviews</p>	<p>Biblical Principles of Teamwork (45 minutes) Examine Paul's model of ministry teams Discuss the importance of diverse gifts (1 Corinthians 12) Strategies for conflict resolution and unity</p>	<p>Team Building Exercise (60 minutes) Engage in a collaborative problemsolving task Debrief on team dynamics, communication, and leadership</p>	<p>Creating a Collaborative Ministry Plan (45 minutes) In groups, draft a plan for a communitybased ministry initiative Focus on roles, communication, and leveraging community partnerships</p>	<p>Final Reflection and Commitment (30 minutes) Individual reflection: Write a personal commitment to community engagement Share commitments with the group and pray for each other</p>

Case Study: Bridging Cultural Gaps in Baguio City

Pastor James Cruz was sent to plant a church in a diverse neighborhood of Baguio City. The area was home to a mix of long-time residents, university students, and migrant workers from various regions of the Philippines. Initially, Pastor Cruz struggled to connect with the different groups, as his ministry approach was based on his experiences in his home province. He found that his sermon illustrations often fell flat, and community outreach events were poorly attended. Recognizing the need to adapt, Pastor Cruz initiated a series of "cultural exchange" dinners, inviting members from different community segments to share their food, stories, and traditions. Through these gatherings, he gained valuable insights into the diverse needs and perspectives within the community. Over time, Pastor Cruz adjusted his preaching style, incorporated diverse cultural elements into worship services, and tailored outreach programs to address specific community needs. As a result, the church began to grow and became known as a welcoming space for people from all backgrounds.

Key lessons:

1. The importance of cultural sensitivity and adaptability in diverse communities
2. The value of creating spaces for intercultural dialogue and understanding
3. The need to tailor ministry approaches to specific community contexts

Checklist:

- Volunteer for a day with a local organization or community project.
- Share a meal with 2 different families from the community, listening to their stories and experiences.
- Learn and use 5 common phrases in the local dialect or language.
- Participate in a local cultural tradition or practice (e.g., traditional craft, dance, or cooking method).
- Keep a daily journal for one week, reflecting on your experiences and interactions in the community.

Module 3: The Basics of Starting a Church

Hello again! Are you getting excited? We're about to learn the basics of starting a church. Don't worry if it sounds big and scary – we'll break it down into easy steps.

Remember when Jesus sent out His disciples? He gave them clear instructions on what to do. We're going to do the same thing. The Bible says, "Go and make disciples of all nations" (Matthew 28:19), and that's exactly what we're preparing to do!

In this module, you'll learn about:

1. What a church really is (hint: it's not just a building!)
2. How to start small and grow
3. Teaching others about Jesus
4. Creating a welcoming place for everyone

By the end of this module, you'll have a good idea of what it takes to start a church. It's a big job, but with God's help, you can do it. Let's get started on this amazing journey!

Day 1: Biblical Foundations of Church Planting (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Scripture Study	Activity	Assignment
<p>Opening Prayer and Reflection (15 minutes)</p> <p>Read Acts 2:42-47</p> <p>Discuss: What characteristics of the early church should we emulate today?</p>	<p>Church Planting in the New Testament (45 minutes)</p> <p>Survey of church planting in Acts</p> <p>Paul's church planting strategies</p> <p>Theological foundations for church multiplication</p>	<p>In small groups, examine key passages related to church growth (e.g., Acts 13:14, 1 Thessalonians 1)</p> <p>Present insights to the larger group</p>	<p>Mapping Paul's Church Planting Journeys (45 minutes)</p> <p>Create a visual representation of Paul's missionary journeys</p> <p>Identify key strategies and principles employed</p>	<p>Reflect on how biblical principles can be applied in your context</p>

Day 2: The Great Commission and Modern Church Planting (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity 1	Activity 2	Final Activity
<p>Review and Prayer (15 minutes) Share reflections on biblical principles in contemporary contexts</p>	<p>Unpacking the Great Commission (45 minutes) Exegesis of Matthew 28:19-20 The role of baptism and teaching in church planting Contextualization of the Great Commission</p>	<p>Applying the Great Commission Today (60 minutes) Invite 23 experienced church planters or missiologists Q&A session on challenges and opportunities in fulfilling the Great Commission</p>	<p>Creating a Collaborative Ministry Plan (45 minutes) In groups, draft a plan for a communitybased ministry initiative Focus on roles, communication, and leveraging community partnerships</p>	<p>Final Reflection and Commitment (30 minutes) Individual reflection: Write a personal commitment to community engagement Share commitments with the group and pray for each other</p>
Day 3: Discipleship and Church Planting Action Plans (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Assignment
<p>Opening Prayer and Sharing (20 minutes) Share personal Great Commission statements</p>	<p>Discipleship in New Churches (45 minutes) Principles of effective discipleship Adapting discipleship methods to new believers Creating a culture of multiplication</p>	<p>Designing a Discipleship Pathway (60 minutes) In small groups, create a stepbystep discipleship plan for a new church Include resources, timelines, and assessment methods</p>	<p>Drafting Church Planting Action Plans (45 minutes) Individually, begin drafting a basic action plan for a church plant Include vision, goals, strategies, and timelines</p>	<p>Final Reflection and Prayer (30 minutes) Share key elements of your action plan with a partner Pray for each other's church planting visions</p>

Case Study: From Home Group to Thriving Congregation

Lay leader Antonio Reyes felt called to start a new congregation in his hometown of Vigan, Ilocos Sur. With the support of his district superintendent, Antonio began by hosting a weekly Bible study in his living room. The group quickly grew from 5 to 15 regular attendees. As the group expanded, Antonio faced several challenges:

1. Finding a larger meeting space;
2. Developing a structured discipleship program;
3. Balancing his full-time job with growing ministry responsibilities;
4. Navigating the formal process of becoming a recognized church plant.

With guidance from his mentor, a seasoned church planter, Antonio developed a phased growth plan. He rented a small commercial space for Sunday gatherings, recruited and trained additional leaders from within the group, and implemented a simple but effective discipleship pathway. After a year, the group had grown to 50 regular attendees and was officially recognized as a United Methodist mission congregation. Antonio's success inspired other lay leaders in the district to consider church planting initiatives.

Key lessons:

1. The power of starting small and growing organically
2. The importance of mentorship and denominational support in church planting
3. The need for intentional leadership development and structure as a church grows

Checklist:

- Lead a small group Bible study or prayer meeting for at least 4 consecutive weeks.**
- Create a draft mission statement and core values for your potential church plant.**
- Develop a basic outline for a 3-month discipleship program.**
- Identify and mentor 2 potential leaders, meeting with them regularly for a month.**
- Plan and execute a community outreach event (e.g., children's program, health seminar, or cleanup drive).**

Module 4: Wesleyan Church Planting

Hi there! Ready to dive into something special? This module is all about Wesleyan church planting. Don't let the big words scare you – it's really about following Jesus the way John Wesley taught. Wesley was a preacher who lived a long time ago, but his ideas are still super important today. He believed in growing closer to God and helping others. That's what we want to do too!

In this module, we'll talk about:

1. Loving God with all our heart (and helping others do the same)
2. Making sure everyone feels welcome in our church
3. Helping people in practical ways
4. Studying the Bible together

The Bible says, "Faith without works is dead" (James 2:26). Wesley took this seriously, and so will we! Get ready to learn how to plant a church that really makes a difference in people's lives. Let's get started!

Day 1: Introduction to Wesleyan Theology (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Scripture Study	Activity	Assignment
Opening Prayer and Reflection (15 minutes) Read Ephesians 2:8-10 Discuss: How does this passage reflect Wesleyan understanding of grace?	Foundations of Wesleyan Theology (45 minutes) John Wesley's life and ministry Key Wesleyan doctrines: prevenient grace, justification, sanctification The importance of "heart religion" in Wesleyan thought	In small groups, examine passages related to Wesleyan themes (e.g., Romans 5:15, 1 Thessalonians 5:23-24) Present insights to the larger group	Wesleyan Hymn Analysis (45 minutes) Analyze Charles Wesley's hymns for theological content Discuss the role of music in teaching Wesleyan theology	Read selected sermons by John Wesley Reflect on how Wesleyan theology might shape church planting practices

Day 2: The Wesleyan Quadrilateral (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Assignment
<p>Review and Prayer (15 minutes) Share reflections on Wesley's sermons</p>	<p>Understanding the Wesleyan Quadrilateral (45 minutes) Scripture, Tradition, Reason, and Experience explained Historical development and contemporary applications Critiques and defenses of the Quadrilateral approach</p>	<p>Case Study Analysis (60 minutes) In groups, apply the Wesleyan Quadrilateral to a contemporary church issue Present findings and discuss implications for church planting</p>	<p>Applying the Quadrilateral in Church Planting (45 minutes) Develop strategies for using the Quadrilateral in decisionmaking processes Roleplay scenarios where the Quadrilateral guides church planting choices</p>	<p>Write a reflection on how you might use the Wesleyan Quadrilateral in your ministry context Begin drafting a "Wesleyan vision" for your church plant</p>
Day 3: Wesleyan Spirituality and Social Holiness (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Assignment
<p>Opening Prayer and Sharing (20 minutes) Share Wesleyan Quadrilateral reflections</p>	<p>Wesleyan Spirituality and Social Holiness (45 minutes) Personal and social aspects of holiness in Wesleyan thought The role of small groups and accountability in spiritual growth Wesleyan approaches to social justice and community transformation</p>	<p>Designing Wesleyan Small Groups (60 minutes) In small groups, create a plan for implementing Wesleyanstyle class meetings in a new church Include accountability questions, meeting structure, and leadership development</p>	<p>Integrating Social Holiness in Church Planting (45 minutes) Brainstorm ways to address community needs through church ministries Develop a plan for balancing personal discipleship with social engagement</p>	<p>Final Reflection and Action Planning (30 minutes) Individually, finalize your "Wesleyan vision" for church planting Share key points with a partner and pray for each other's ministry</p>

Case Study: Revitalizing Ministry Through Wesleyan Principles

Rev. Clara Domingo inherited a struggling congregation in a working-class neighborhood of Dagupan City. Church attendance had been declining for years, and the remaining members were mostly elderly. Determined to breathe new life into the church, Rev. Domingo decided to revisit core Wesleyan principles. She introduced a series of class meetings, focusing on personal spiritual growth and accountability. She also initiated community service projects, emphasizing Wesley's concept of social holiness. Initially, some long-time members resisted the changes. However, as they engaged with Wesleyan practices like the "means of grace" and experienced spiritual renewal, their enthusiasm grew. The church's renewed focus on both personal piety and social action began to attract younger families and professionals from the community. Within two years, the congregation had doubled in size and become known for its vibrant small group ministry and impactful community outreach programs.

Key lessons:

1. The relevance of Wesleyan theology and practices in contemporary ministry
2. The balance between personal spiritual growth and social engagement in Wesleyan tradition
3. The potential for denominational distinctives to drive church revitalization and growth

Checklist:

- Lead a Wesleyan-style Bible Study.
- Organize and participate in a "Holy Club" style accountability group for a week.
- Plan and lead a worship service incorporating distinctly Wesleyan elements.
- Conduct a community service project that addresses both spiritual and social needs.
- Write and deliver a sermon that incorporates Wesleyan theology and its application to contemporary life.

Module 5: Planning Your New Church

Welcome back, church planter! Now we're getting to the nitty-gritty – planning your new church. It might sound like a lot of work, but don't worry. We'll take it step by step, and it'll be fun!

The Bible tells us, "Suppose one of you wants to build a tower. Won't you first sit down and estimate the cost?" (Luke 14:28). That's what we're doing – making a good plan so our church can grow strong.

In this module, we'll cover:

- Dreaming big about what your church could be
- Figuring out what you need to make it happen
- Planning activities that will help people grow closer to God
- Thinking about where your church will meet

By the end of this module, you'll have a clear plan for your new church. It's like drawing a map for an exciting journey. Are you ready to start planning? Let's go!

Day 1: Strategic Church Planting Planning (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Assignment
<p>Opening Prayer and Reflection (15 minutes) Read Luke 14:28-30 Discuss: How does this passage relate to church planting planning?</p>	<p>Principles of Strategic Planning (45 minutes) Elements of a church planting plan Setting SMART goals for church growth Importance of flexibility and adaptability in planning</p>	<p>Case Study Analysis (60 minutes) In groups, review successful church planting case studies Identify key planning elements that contributed to success</p>	<p>Drafting Your Church Planting Plan (45 minutes) Begin outlining a comprehensive plan for your church plant Include vision, mission, core values, and initial goals</p>	<p>Continue developing your church planting plan Research demographic data for your target area</p>

Day 2: Urban vs. Rural Church Planting (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Panel Discussion	Activity	Assignment
<p>Review and Prayer (15 minutes) Share initial thoughts on church planting plans</p>	<p>Contextual Differences in Church Planting (45 minutes) Characteristics of urban and rural environments Unique challenges and opportunities in each context Adapting strategies for different settings</p>	<p>Urban and Rural Church Planters (60 minutes) Invite experienced planters from both contexts Q&A session on contextual challenges and best practices</p>	<p>Context Analysis (45 minutes) In groups, analyze provided scenarios (urban and rural) Develop contextspecific strategies for each scenario</p>	<p>Refine your church planting plan based on your specific context Prepare a brief presentation on your contextual analysis</p>
Day 3: Inclusive Planning and Resource Management (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture 1	Workshop	Lecture 2	Final Activity
<p>Opening Prayer and Sharing (20 minutes) Present contextual analyses</p>	<p>Creating Inclusive Church Communities (45 minutes) Biblical foundations for diversity and inclusion Strategies for reaching diverse populations Addressing cultural and socioeconomic barriers</p>	<p>Inclusive Church Planning (60 minutes) Review and adapt church planting plans to ensure inclusivity Develop specific outreach strategies for diverse groups</p>	<p>Resource Management in Church Planting (45 minutes) Budgeting for church plants Fundraising strategies and financial stewardship Managing volunteers and developing leaders</p>	<p>Pitch Your Church Plant (30 minutes) In pairs, present your refined church planting plan Offer constructive feedback to your partner</p>

Case Study: Adapting Plans for an Evolving Community

Lay leader Maria Cruz felt called to plant a church in a rapidly developing area on the outskirts of Laoag City. She spent months developing a detailed church planting plan based on her initial community analysis, which showed a growing population of young families. However, six months into the church plant, Maria noticed that her carefully crafted plans weren't yielding the expected results. Attendance at family-oriented events was low, and the church struggled to retain visitors. Upon conducting a new community analysis, Maria discovered that the area's demographics had shifted significantly. Instead of young families, the new housing developments were attracting mostly retirees and overseas Filipino workers (OFWs) investing in properties. Realizing the need to adapt, Maria revised her church planting plan. She shifted focus to create programs that addressed the needs of retirees and OFW families, such as:

1. A ministry for grandparents raising grandchildren
2. Financial stewardship classes for returning OFWs
3. English conversation groups to help retirees connect with their overseas grandchildren

The revised approach resonated with the community, and the church began to grow steadily.

Key lessons:

1. The importance of ongoing community analysis and adaptability in church planting
2. The need for flexible planning that can respond to changing demographics
3. The value of tailoring ministry programs to specific community needs

Checklist:

- Develop a 12-month strategic plan for your church plant, including goals and action steps.**
- Create a budget proposal for the first year of your church plant.**
- Design a logo and basic branding materials for your potential church.**
- Outline a plan for 3 different ministry programs tailored to your community's needs.**
- Identify and visit 3 potential locations for your church plant, evaluating their pros and cons.**

Module 6: Helping Your Community Through Your Church

Hey there, friend! This module is super exciting because it's all about how your new church can help make your community better. Isn't that awesome?

Jesus didn't just preach – He fed people, healed them, and cared for their needs. He told us to "Love your neighbor as yourself" (Mark 12:31). That's exactly what we're going to learn to do through our church.

In this module, we'll explore:

1. Finding out what your community really needs
2. Coming up with fun ways to help people
3. Getting others excited about serving
4. Showing God's love in practical ways

By the end, you'll have great ideas for how your church can make a real difference. It's not just about Sunday services – it's about loving and serving every day of the week. Ready to learn how to change your community? Let's dive in!

Day 1: Foundations of Community Ministry (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Assignment
<p>Opening Prayer and Reflection (15 minutes) Read Matthew 25:31-40 Discuss: How does this passage inform our approach to community ministry?</p>	<p>Biblical Basis for Community Engagement (45 minutes) Old and New Testament examples of community care Jesus' model of holistic ministry The church's role in community transformation</p>	<p>Case Study Analysis (60 minutes) In groups, examine successful churchbased community initiatives Identify key principles and best practices</p>	<p>Community Needs Assessment Review (45 minutes) Revisit community needs assessments from Module 1 Begin brainstorming potential ministry responses to identified needs</p>	<p>Research existing community services in your area Identify gaps that your church plant could potentially fill</p>

Day 2: Volunteer Engagement and Project Planning (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Assignment
<p>Review and Prayer (15 minutes) Share insights from community service research</p>	<p>Principles of Volunteer Management (45 minutes) Recruiting and training volunteers Creating meaningful volunteer experiences Sustaining volunteer engagement longterm</p>	<p>Volunteer Program Design (60 minutes) In small groups, design a volunteer program for a specific community need Include recruitment, training, and retention strategies</p>	<p>Community Project Planning (45 minutes) Begin planning a specific community service project Focus on goals, resources needed, and potential partnerships</p>	<p>Refine your community project plan Prepare a brief presentation on your proposed project</p>
Day 3: Integrating Outreach and Church Growth (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Panel Discussion	Workshop	Final Activity
<p>Opening Prayer and Project Presentations (30 minutes) Share community project plans</p>	<p>Balancing Outreach and Church Development (45 minutes) Strategies for turning service into discipleship opportunities Building relationships through community engagement Measuring the impact of community ministry</p>	<p>Community Ministry Practitioners (60 minutes) Invite leaders of successful churchbased community programs Q&A session on challenges, successes, and lessons learned</p>	<p>Integrated Ministry Planning (30 minutes) Revise church planting plans to fully integrate community outreach Develop strategies for connecting service participants to the church</p>	<p>Final Reflection and Commitment (30 minutes) Write a personal commitment to communityfocused ministry Share commitments with the group and pray for each other</p>

Case Study: Responding to Disaster with Compassion

Pastor Roberto Aquino had recently planted a small congregation in a coastal town in Zambales. The church was still in its early stages when a powerful typhoon struck the region, causing significant damage and displacement. Despite limited resources, Pastor Roberto felt compelled to respond to the community's needs. He rallied his small congregation and took the following steps:

1. Converted the church building into a temporary shelter
2. Organized volunteers to distribute relief goods
3. Partnered with other local churches and NGOs to maximize impact
4. Provided pastoral care and counseling to affected families

The church's swift and compassionate response earned the respect and gratitude of the community. Many people who had never considered attending church before began to engage with the congregation. As the immediate crisis passed, Pastor Roberto guided the church in developing long-term community support initiatives, including:

1. A job skills training program for those who lost livelihoods
2. A support group for trauma survivors
3. Advocacy for better disaster preparedness in the community

The church's commitment to holistic ministry led to significant growth and deep community impact.

Key lessons:

1. The opportunity for churches to demonstrate Christ's love through community service
2. The importance of collaboration with other organizations in community outreach
3. The potential for community-focused ministry to drive church growth and relevance

Checklist:

- Conduct a needs assessment by surveying at least 5 community members.**
- Develop and implement a small-scale community service project based on identified needs.**
- Build partnerships with 1 local organization or business for community outreach.**
- Create a volunteer recruitment and training plan for community service initiatives.**
- Design a follow-up system to connect community service participants with church activities.**

Module 7: Choosing the Right Place for Your Church

Welcome back! Now we're going to talk about something really important – finding the perfect spot for your new church. It's kind of like finding the best place to plant a seed so it can grow into a big, strong tree.

In the Bible, Paul often chose strategic places to start churches. He went where people gathered and where the message could spread. We're going to do the same thing!

In this module, we'll learn about:

1. Looking at different places in your community
2. Thinking about where people live and work
3. Finding a place that's easy for everyone to get to
4. Making sure the place fits with your church's goals

By the end, you'll know how to pick a great spot for your church. It's an important decision, but don't worry – we'll figure it out together. Ready to go location hunting? Let's get started!

Day 1: Principles of Location Selection (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Assignment
<p>Opening Prayer and Reflection (15 minutes)</p> <p>Read Acts 16:6-10</p> <p>Discuss: How did Paul make decisions about where to plant churches?</p>	<p>Strategic Considerations in Church Location (45 minutes)</p> <p>Factors influencing church location (demographics, accessibility, visibility)</p> <p>The impact of location on church growth and community engagement</p> <p>Balancing spiritual guidance and practical considerations</p>	<p>Case Study Analysis (60 minutes)</p> <p>In groups, examine case studies of successful and unsuccessful church locations</p> <p>Identify key factors that contributed to success or failure</p>	<p>Initial Location Assessment (45 minutes)</p> <p>Begin a SWOT analysis for potential locations in your target area</p> <p>Consider both spiritual and practical factors</p>	<p>Research demographic data for your target area</p> <p>Begin drafting criteria for ideal church locations</p>

Day 2: Community Analysis and Cultural Understanding (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Assignment
<p>Review and Prayer (15 minutes) Share insights from demographic research</p>	<p>Understanding Community Dynamics (45 minutes) Analyzing population trends and migration patterns Identifying cultural and socioeconomic factors The importance of cultural exegesis in location selection</p>	<p>Community Lifestyle Mapping (60 minutes) Create visual representations of daily life in your target community Identify key gathering places, travel patterns, and cultural centers</p>	<p>Cultural Exegesis (45 minutes) Analyze the cultural landscape of your target area Develop strategies for contextualizing your church plant</p>	<p>Conduct informal interviews with community members about their neighborhood Reflect on how these insights might influence church location</p>
Day 3: Mapping and Final Location Strategies (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Workshop	Activity	Final Activity
<p>Opening Prayer and Sharing (20 minutes) Share key insights from community interviews</p>	<p>Utilizing Mapping Tools for Church Planting (45 minutes) Introduction to GIS and other mapping technologies Using maps to visualize demographic data and community needs Strategies for identifying underserved areas</p>	<p>Digital Mapping (60 minutes) Use provided software to create digital maps of your target area Plot existing churches, community resources, and potential locations</p>	<p>Location Proposal Development (45 minutes) In small groups, develop proposals for specific church locations Include rationale based on demographic data, community needs, and strategic considerations</p>	<p>Final Presentation and Discussion (30 minutes) Present location proposals to the larger group Offer constructive feedback and discuss next steps</p>

Case Study: Finding the Sweet Spot in Subic Bay

Rev. Eduardo Santos was tasked with planting a church in the Subic Bay area. The region presented unique challenges due to its diverse population, including local residents, former US military personnel, and expatriates working in the Subic Bay Freeport Zone. Rev. Santos conducted a thorough area study, which revealed several potential locations:

1. A residential area with many young Filipino families
2. A commercial district popular with expatriates
3. A neighborhood with a mix of local residents and former US military families

Initially, Rev. Santos was drawn to the residential area due to its growing population of young families. However, upon deeper analysis and consultation with local leaders, he realized that this area was already well-served by existing churches. The commercial district seemed promising due to its visibility, but high rental costs and parking limitations made it less feasible. Ultimately, Rev. Santos chose the mixed neighborhood for several reasons:

1. It was an underserved area in terms of faith communities
2. The diverse population aligned with the United Methodist Church's commitment to inclusivity
3. There was potential for unique ministry opportunities bridging cultural gaps
4. An affordable property was available that could be renovated for church use

The choice proved successful, as the church was able to attract a diverse congregation and develop ministries that fostered cross-cultural understanding and community integration.

Key lessons:

1. The importance of thorough research and analysis in choosing a church location
2. The need to consider factors beyond just population demographics
3. The potential for strategic location choices to shape a church's ministry focus and impact

Checklist:

- Create a demographic map of your target area using available data and personal observations.**
- Visit and analyze 5 different potential locations for your church plant.**
- Conduct a SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) for your top 3 location choices.**
- Interview 3 local business owners or residents near your preferred location about the area's characteristics.**
- Develop a proposal for your chosen location, including rationale, potential challenges, and growth opportunities.**

Module 8: Solving Problems When Starting a Church

Hey there, church planter! This last module is super important. We're going to talk about solving problems that might come up when you're starting your church. Don't worry – every church planter faces challenges, but God is always there to help!

The Bible says, "I can do all this through him who gives me strength" (Philippians 4:13). That's our motto for this module. No problem is too big when God is on our side!

In this module, we'll cover:

1. Dealing with money matters
2. Helping people get along when they disagree
3. Taking care of yourself so you don't get too tired
4. Trusting God when things get tough

By the end of this module, you'll feel ready to face any challenge that comes your way. It's like learning to be a problem-solving superhero for your church! Are you ready to become a master problem solver? Let's jump in!

Day 1: Anticipating and Addressing Common Challenges (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Panel Discussion	Workshop	Assignment
<p>Opening Prayer and Reflection (15 minutes)</p> <p>Read 2 Corinthians 11:23-28</p> <p>Discuss: What challenges did Paul face in his ministry, and how did he overcome them?</p>	<p>Common Pitfalls in Church Planting (45 minutes)</p> <p>Overview of typical challenges (financial, relational, spiritual)</p> <p>Case studies of church planting difficulties and successes</p> <p>Importance of preparation and adaptability</p>	<p>Experienced Church Planters (60 minutes)</p> <p>Invite church planters to share their experiences</p> <p>Q&A session on overcoming obstacles</p>	<p>Problem Anticipation and Planning (45 minutes)</p> <p>In groups, brainstorm potential challenges for your church plants</p> <p>Begin developing contingency plans for identified issues</p>	<p>Reflect on personal strengths and weaknesses in facing challenges</p> <p>Research additional church planting case studies</p>

Day 2: Resource Management and Conflict Resolution (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Assignment
Review and Prayer (15 minutes) Share insights from personal reflections	Financial Stewardship in Church Planting (45 minutes) Principles of biblical financial management Fundraising strategies for new churches Budgeting and resource allocation	Fundraising Plan Development (60 minutes) Create a basic fundraising plan for your church plant Include multiple strategies and timelines	Conflict Resolution Scenarios (45 minutes) Roleplay common conflict situations in new churches Practice applying biblical conflict resolution principles	Develop a personal conflict resolution strategy Begin drafting a financial management plan for your church plant
Day 3: Team Building and SelfCare (3 hours)				
Preparation	Lecture	Activity	Workshop	Final Activity
Opening Prayer and Sharing (20 minutes) Share key points from conflict resolution strategies	Building and Maintaining Healthy Ministry Teams (45 minutes) Principles of effective team leadership Strategies for volunteer recruitment and retention Fostering a culture of collaboration and mutual support	Team Building Exercise (60 minutes) Engage in practical teambuilding activities Debrief on lessons learned and application to church planting	SelfCare and Burnout Prevention (45 minutes) Discuss the importance of selfcare in ministry Develop personal and team strategies for maintaining spiritual, emotional, and physical health	Final Reflection and Action Planning (30 minutes) Create a personal action plan for problemsolving and selfcare Share commitments with a partner and pray for each other

Case Study: Overcoming Financial and Leadership Challenges

Lay leader Anna Reyes started a house church in her apartment in Quezon City. The group grew quickly, and within a year, they needed to find a larger space. However, Anna soon faced a series of challenges:

1. **Financial Strain:** The cost of renting a suitable space was beyond the young congregation's means.
2. **Leadership Burnout:** Anna was juggling full-time work, family responsibilities, and church leadership, leading to exhaustion.
3. **Interpersonal Conflicts:** As the church grew, disagreements arose over ministry direction and use of resources.
4. **Spiritual Warfare:** Some members reported feeling discouraged and spiritually attacked.

Anna took the following steps to address these issues:

1. **Financial Management:**
 - Implemented a financial literacy course for members
 - Developed a transparent budgeting process
 - Explored creative space-sharing options with other community organizations
2. **Leadership Development:**
 - Identified and mentored potential leaders within the congregation
 - Delegated responsibilities to prevent burnout
 - Sought personal mentoring from an experienced pastor
3. **Conflict Resolution:**
 - Organized a workshop on biblical conflict resolution
 - Established clear communication channels and decision-making processes
 - Encouraged a culture of grace and forgiveness
4. **Spiritual Nurture:**
 - Instituted a prayer ministry focused on spiritual protection and growth
 - Organized a spiritual retreat for core leaders
 - Incorporated teaching on spiritual warfare into the discipleship curriculum

Through persistent prayer, strategic problem-solving, and reliance on the wider United Methodist connection, Anna and her team navigated these challenges. The experience strengthened the church's foundation and prepared them for future growth.

Key lessons:

1. The importance of proactive problem-solving in church planting
2. The need for personal spiritual health and support systems for church planters
3. The value of transparency and shared leadership in overcoming church challenges

Checklist:

- Create a personal self-care plan and follow it for at least 2 weeks.
- Develop a conflict resolution protocol for your future church leadership team.
- Design and lead a team-building exercise for a group of potential church leaders.
- Create a risk management plan addressing potential challenges (e.g., financial, legal, interpersonal).
- Establish a prayer support network of at least 10 people committed to praying for your church planting journey.

Assessment Tool: Rubric Evaluation

For the rubric evaluation in this training material, specifically for training church leaders in church planting, I recommend using a Holistic Rubric. This type of rubric is well-suited for evaluating complex tasks like those found in church planting, where the focus is on assessing the overall performance or mastery of key components rather than isolating individual skills. The holistic rubric will provide an overall rating based on a description that captures varying levels of performance across multiple criteria.

Suggested Rubric Evaluation Criteria:

- 1. Understanding and Application of Biblical Principles (30%)**
 - **Excellent (90-100%):** Demonstrates deep understanding and effectively integrates biblical principles into all aspects of church planting.
 - **Good (75-89%):** Shows good understanding and applies biblical principles in most areas.
 - **Satisfactory (60-74%):** Basic understanding with some application of biblical principles.
 - **Needs Improvement (Below 60%):** Limited understanding and application of biblical principles.

- 2. Community Engagement and Cultural Sensitivity (25%)**
 - **Excellent (90-100%):** Engages deeply with the community, showing high cultural sensitivity and adaptability.
 - **Good (75-89%):** Engages well with the community with moderate cultural sensitivity.
 - **Satisfactory (60-74%):** Some engagement and cultural awareness, but limited in scope.
 - **Needs Improvement (Below 60%):** Minimal community engagement and lack of cultural sensitivity.

- 3. Strategic Planning and Implementation (20%)**
 - **Excellent (90-100%):** Develops and implements highly effective strategic plans for church planting.
 - **Good (75-89%):** Strategic planning is effective, though some areas may need improvement.
 - **Satisfactory (60-74%):** Basic strategic planning with adequate implementation.
 - **Needs Improvement (Below 60%):** Lacks effective strategic planning and implementation.

4. Leadership and Teamwork (15%)

- **Excellent (90-100%):** Demonstrates outstanding leadership and fosters strong teamwork.
- **Good (75-89%):** Shows good leadership skills with effective team collaboration.
- **Satisfactory (60-74%):** Adequate leadership with some teamwork challenges.
- **Needs Improvement (Below 60%):** Struggles with leadership and teamwork dynamics.

5. Innovative and Adaptive Approaches (10%)

- **Excellent (90-100%):** Highly innovative and adaptive in responding to challenges and opportunities.
- **Good (75-89%):** Shows good innovation and adaptability, though not consistently.
- **Satisfactory (60-74%):** Some innovation and adaptability, but limited.
- **Needs Improvement (Below 60%):** Minimal innovation and resistance to adapting to new situations.

Explanation for Choosing Holistic Rubric:

I have chosen this because it aligns well with the complex nature of church planting, where leaders need to incorporate various skills and knowledge areas into a coordinated practice. Church planting requires not only technical skills but also a deep understanding of cultural dynamics, leadership, and strategic planning. A holistic rubric captures the overall effectiveness and impact of the leader's performance, which is important in evaluating their readiness to lead a church planting mission.

This type of rubric also allows for flexibility in assessment, which is important in church leadership training, where different leaders might excel in different areas but still meet the overall criteria for success.

FINAL WORDS

Wow! You've learned so much about starting new churches. That's amazing!

You now know how to understand your community, live among the people, and start a church from scratch. You've also figured out how to help your neighbors and pick the perfect spot for your church. And you're ready to solve problems when they pop up.

But here's the cool part - you're not just learning stuff from a book. You're getting ready to go out and make a real difference in people's lives! How awesome is that?

Remember, starting a church isn't always easy. There will be times when you feel tired or unsure. But don't give up! God is with you every step of the way. He'll guide you and give you strength when you need it most.

So, are you ready for your next big adventure? It's time to take everything you've learned and put it into action. Your community is waiting for you to bring hope, love, and the good news of Jesus.

What will your first step be? Maybe you'll start by talking to people in your neighborhood. Or you might begin planning your first church service. Whatever you choose, go for it with all your heart!

Just think - your new church could change someone's life forever. That's pretty powerful stuff!

So, let's get out there and start planting churches. The world needs what you have to offer. Are you up for the challenge? I bet you are!

Remember, with God's help, you can do amazing things. Now go and make it happen! In Jesus' name I declare empowerment as He use You to win more souls for Him, amen!

Interview Questions

1. What is your demographic profile in terms of: (RQ 1.5.1)
 - a. Membership Category;
 - b. UMC Previous Leadership Role;
 - c. UMC Current Leadership Role;
2. What is the importance of developing a church planting curriculum in NWPAC? Why? (RQ 1.5.2.1)
3. What do you think are the needs to develop a church planting curriculum for NWPAC? Why? (RQ 1.5.2.1)
4. Do you have any biblical and theological bases on the church planting mission? Can you share them to me? Why? (RQ 1.5.2.2)
5. What is your idea of integrating Wesleyan Identity (Scripture, Tradition, Experience, and Reason) in the development of church planting mission curriculum? Why? (RQ 1.5.2.3)
6. What do you think are the practical ways including methods and strategies, in implementing a church planting mission curriculum in NWPAC? Why? (RQ 1.5.2.4)
7. Are there any gaps or limitations in your current role regarding church planting mission? How so? (RQ 1.5.2.5)
8. How would you describe your ideal solution to make a more effective church planting mission program? Why? (RQ 1.5.2.4)
9. What other recommendations would you propose in the development of a church planting curriculum? Why? (RQ 1.5.2.4)

Appendix 2. Interview Questions

Cesar T. Reyes Jr.
121 Provincial Road, Nancayasan
Urdaneta City, Pangasinan

June 13, 2024

Lay Leader
Ilocos District

Greetings Sir !

I am writing to request your time and presence for an interview regarding my dissertation entitled, "SOWING THE SEEDS OF FAITH: TOWARDS DEVELOPMENT OF A WESLEYAN IDENTITY OF CHURCH PLANTING MISSION CURRICULUM." There are three (3) respondents per district; (1) Incumbent District Superintendent; (2) a Church Worker with successful experience on planting a church; and (3) the district lay leader.

Date of Interviews: Zoom: June 14-23, 2024
Face to Face: June 18-23, 2024

The interview can be on a face to face basis or online via Zoom application whichever is your most convenient way. I am also requesting that the interview be recorded so that I can transcribe with the most accuracy possible. The language and dialect will not be limited to English alone, and you may speak on either English, Filipino, Ilocano, or mixed. You may also write the answers and read throughout the interview. In addition, can you kindly suggest me the names and contact of the church worker involved in church planting and the district lay leader of your district?

Below are the interview questions:

1. What is the importance of developing a church planting curriculum in NWPAC? Why?
Ania ti pateg ti panangbukel iti kurikulum ti panagmula iti simbaan iti NWPAC? Apay? Ano ang kahalagahan ng pagbuo ng kurikulum sa pagtatanim ng simbahan sa NWPAC? Bakit?
2. What do you think are the needs to develop a church planting curriculum for NWPAC? Why?
Ania ti pagarupyo a kasapulan tapno maaramid ti church planting curriculum para iti NWPAC? Apay? Ano sa palagay mo ang mga pangangailangan upang bumuo ng kurikulum ng pagtatanim ng simbahan para sa NWPAC? Bakit?
3. Do you have any biblical and theological bases on church planting mission? Can you share them to me? Why?
Adda kadi biblikal ken teolohikal a pagbatayan iti mision a panagmula iti iglesia? Mabalín kadi nga ibinglaymo dagitoy kaniak? Apay? Mayroon ka bang mga batayan sa Bibliya at teolohiko sa mision ng pagtatanim ng simbahan? Maaari mo bang ibahagi ang mga ito sa akin? Bakit?
4. What is your idea of integrating Wesleyan Identity (Scripture, Tradition, Experience, and Reason) in the development of church planting mission curriculum? Why?
Ania ti kapanunotan a mangitipon iti Wesleyan Identity (Kasuratan, Tradision, Kapadasan, ken Rason) iti pannaakaparang-ay ti kurikulum ti mision iti panagmula iti iglesia? Apay? Ano ang iyong ideya ng pagsasama ng Wesleyan Identity (Banal, Tradisyon, Karanasan, at Dahilan) sa pagbuo ng kurikulum ng mision sa pagtatanim ng simbahan? Bakit?
5. What do you think are the practical ways including methods and strategies, in implementing a church planting mission curriculum in NWPAC? Why?
Ania ti pagarupyo a praktikal a wagas a pakairamanan dagiti pamayan ken estratehia, iti panangipatangpal iti kurikulum ti mision a panagmula iti simbaan iti NWPAC? Apay? Ano sa palagay mo ang mga praktikal na paraan kasama ang mga pamamaraan at estratehiya, sa pagpapatupad ng kurikulum ng mision sa pagtatanim ng simbahan sa NWPAC? Bakit?

Appendix 3. Interview Letter

Waiver for Dissertation Interview Participation

I, JA [REDACTED] A [REDACTED] (print name), hereby agree to participate in the dissertation research interview conducted by Rev. Cesar Taqueban Reyes Jr. (Researcher's name).

By signing this waiver, I acknowledge and agree to the following:

1. Recording of Interview: I understand that the interview will be recorded to ensure data accuracy. I give my consent for the interview to be video-recorded.
2. Access to Recordings: I am aware that the recorded interview sessions may be accessed by various individuals for validation and checking purposes, as part of the research process.
3. Limited Personal Information: I understand that the interview does not include personal questions beyond demographic information regarding Membership Categorization and past and present Leadership Roles in the UMC (United Methodist Church).
4. Confidentiality: I acknowledge that code names (e.g., R1, R2) will be used to protect my identity in all research materials and publications resulting from this study.
5. Voluntary Participation: My participation in this interview is entirely voluntary, and I have the right to withdraw at any time without penalty.
6. Use of Data: I grant permission for the information I provide during the interview to be used for the purposes of this dissertation research and any related academic publications or presentations.
7. Questions and Concerns: I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the research and my participation, and all my questions have been answered to my satisfaction.

By signing below, I certify that I have read and understood this waiver, and I voluntarily agree to participate in this research study under the conditions described above.

JA [REDACTED] A [REDACTED] - July 1, 2024
Signature Over Printed Name & Date

[REDACTED] JULY 1, 2024
REYES, CESAR JR. T.
Researcher's Signature Over Printed Name & Date

Open Coding

What is the importance of developing a church planting curriculum in NWPAC? Why?	Open Coding
<p>R1:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ti pateg ang kahalagahan ng curriculum sa pagtanim ng simbahan sa nwpac ay para sa akin ay ito yung basehan o tungtungan. Daytoy ti pasaran wenno pundasyon tapno maadal. 2. I mean no awan ti basehan iti panagadal anyan ti servi dagiti aramiden tay. 3. kas pangarigan koma iti eskwelaan isu ada curriculum tapno nalakada nga ipatungpal iti panangadal dagitoy nga estudyante 4. ket no ada met curriculum iti panagmula kdagiti simsimbaan nalaklaka nga kitaen ken amoen no anya ti kasapulan iti panagmula iti simsimbaan ti nwpac. Kasdyay laeng ti kapanunutak. 5. Isu nga napateg ti curriculum anya man nga institution anya man nga grupo wenno asosasyon ti curriculum ket dakkal a banag 6. ta isu daytoy ti mangisuro ken mangidalan no anya iti direksyon nga turungen. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Curriculum as the framework of Church Planting 2. The curriculum as the guiding principle in doing the church planting mission 3. The curriculum as a learning material 4. The curriculum as a need determinant 5. The curriculum as a universal framework 6. The curriculum as a teaching manual
<p>R2:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. The value of making a curriculum in church planting like achieving a goal. 8. Kung gusto mong magtanim ng iglesia ay dapat may plano ka at ang pagkaintindi ko sa curriculum eh parang plano na rin yan para ma-attain mo iyong isang goal. 9. Gusto mong magtanim ng simbahan pero wala kang plan, wala kang maa-attain so very important po iyang curriculum. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. The curriculum as an objective tool 8. The curriculum as framework 9. The curriculum as a necessity
<p>R3:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. Kaniak napateg ti panangbukel iti curriculum iti panagmula tapno adda sursuroten, adda blue print nga sursuruten iti panagmula panagpaado iti iglesia ditoy NWPAC. 11. Tano awan ti curriculum nga sursuroten wenno plano nga sursuruten tayo ay ket a naginat. 12. Napinpintas no adda dagidiay nga nabukel nga plano nga curriculum tapno napasaspas ti trabaho. 13. No iyarid tayo iti maysa nga panagbangon iti maysa nga balay masapol nga adda plano nga sursuroten tapno napintas ti panakabukel na. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. Curriculum as a manual for church planting 11. The curriculum as a necessity 12. The curriculum as a guiding principle for efficient church planting mission 13. The curriculum as a framework 14. The curriculum as a manual

<p>14. napasaspas ti pannakaaramid na, namaymayat pay ti resulta na.</p> <p>15. Ti panagpayso na iti NWPAC gapu ta awan iti daydiay plano</p> <p>16. maymasa kuma nga plano nga blueprint nga sursuroten ti nadumaduma nga distrito wenno local chuch napasaspas koma.</p>	<p>15. The curriculum as a necessity</p> <p>16. The curriculum as a universal system for church planting endeavors</p>
<p>R4:</p> <p>17. Para sa akin, ang kahalagahan ng pagdevelop ng curriculum ng church planting sa nwpac ay yung pagkakaroon ng concretong basehan una at</p> <p>18. maayos na patutunguhan ang hangaring pagtatanim ng church ditto sa lupa.</p> <p>19. Kasi kung wala tayong pinagababsehan hindi antin makikita yung tamang daan kumbaga sa curriculum na yan ay sobrang napakahalaga</p> <p>20. kasi hindi na tayo kailangang maghanap pa sa iba</p> <p>21. kundi mismong dito na sa NWPAC sa sarili niyang gawa na naayon sa sarili niyang konteksto. Iyon po yung nakitang kong kahalagaan ng pagdevelop ng curriculum ng church planting sa NWPAC</p>	<p>17. The curriculum as framework</p> <p>18. The curriculum as a guiding principle</p> <p>19. The curriculum as a necessity</p> <p>20. The curriculum as an internal resource material</p> <p>21. A contextualized curriculum</p>
<p>R5:</p> <p>22. Unang una, ang kahalagahan nito ay magiging guidelines ng isang Iglesia</p> <p>23. tungo sa pagpapalago at pag papalakas sa misyon ng ating Iglesia.</p> <p>24. Pangalawa, ito po ay nagbibigay sa bawat Iglesia ng direksyon doon po sa kagustuhan ng ating Panginoong Hesukristo.</p> <p>25. Direksyon na lumago, dumami, at higit sa lahat, ang magiging alagad ni Kristo, ang mga tao na dito sa ibabaw ng mundo.</p>	<p>22. The curriculum as framework</p> <p>23. The curriculum emphasizing Church growth and mission</p> <p>24. The curriculum as a guiding principle aligned with the Biblical teaching</p> <p>25. Emphasizing Evangelism and discipleship</p>
<p>R6:</p> <p>26. Yung importance of curriculum kasi ang alam ko diyan, It is a well-planned</p> <p>27. or structured learning by which a church planter maybe a Pastor or Lay would engage on that in initiative</p> <p>28. ay magkaroon siya ng magandang experience, hindi lang sa learning pati on their actual experience with going to church planting.</p> <p>29. By the power of God, and surrendering themselves will be used by God is such initiative ng church planting.</p> <p>30. So, parang gusto kong makita yung, napagplanuhan, structured.</p>	<p>26. Detailed curriculum</p> <p>27. Engaging</p> <p>28. Experiential learning</p> <p>29. Emphasizing commitment</p> <p>30. Detailed curriculum</p> <p>31. Joyous learning</p> <p>32. Strengthening of church leaders</p>

31. Habang ginagamit mo, nag eenjoy ka. Hindi ka lang nag lelearn, nag eenjoy ka at nagagamit ka.
32. So, ito ay magiging source of empowerment ng both the clergy and lay sa initiative ng church planting within NWPAC.

R7:
33. Where there is no vision, the people will perish sabi nga sa Proverbs 29:18.
34. Napateg iti church planting, iti curriculum agsipud ta daytoy iti sanggir ti misyon tayo.
35. No awan iti suruten tayo nga curriculum, bassit iti prosyento nga agballigi iti church planting.
36. No awan iti suruten tayo nga pagrukudan, bassit iti porsyento nga agballigi tayo no panay bara-bara laeng iti ikasta tayo, nga ag church planting.

R8:
37. Ti kinapateg na, panagmula eti simbaan eti NWPAC ket of course manayunan dagiti kakabsat nga mamati kenni Apo tayo nga Hesu Kristo
38. kas daytoy met ti kinabaunan tayo eti misyon, ag-misyon because we are, we care for the souls.
39. And of course yan naman yong pinuntahan ng ating Panginoong Hesu Kristo pumunta siya dito sa mundo dahil concern siya sa ating mga kaluluwa.
40. Kaya ang pag-develop, yong kahalagahan ng pagde-develop ng curriculum ng church planting of course nandiyang yong pag-a-adjust lalo na't yong panahon natin ngayon ay more on digital, halos mga tao ngayon ay may mga cellphones kasi nga ito na yong panahon natin.
41. At maaari nating e-adapt ito doon sa curriculum bilang pagdevelop, mas ano pa ito siguro mas madali tayong maka-hikayat we can easily spread goodnews to people not only in our area, not only in our nation but also to the other nations.

R9:
42. Para kaniyak sir ket napateg nga adda mabukel nga korrikulum.
43. Ta daytoy ngamin korrikulum, isu ngamin daytoy iti agserbi nga guide tapno adda nga makabukel tayo, wenna makapag mula tayo nga nasaysayaat kadagiti simbaan.
44. Daytoy, ijay distrito mi, sir. Daytoy gamin curriculum... ti kinapateg daytoy mabukel nga korrikulum, isu't mangi pakaawat. Mangi pakaawat

33. The vision as the guiding principle
34. The curriculum as the foundation of church planting mission
35. The necessity of the church planting curriculum
36. The curriculum as a framework

37. The curriculum emphasizing evangelism
38. The curriculum guided by the biblical principles of mission
39. A curriculum emphasizing Christ's mission

40. A curriculum that is technologically integrated
41. A curriculum utilizing technological advancements to increase efficiency and effectivity

42. Necessity of the curriculum
43. The curriculum as a framework of church planting mission
44. The curriculum as a manual for guidance and implementation
45. Result oriented or output-based curriculum

kadagiti miyembro dagijay guidelines nu kasatno dagiti proseso, tapno nasaysayaat dayjay kuna tayo nga pannaka implementar na, at the same time, pannaka ilippas na.

45. Daytoy korrikulum nga maaramid, panagkitak ket haan met lang nga patingga dayjay pannaka irugi ajay panagmula kadagiti simbaan, nu di ketdi adda jay ending na nga talaga nga makita dayjay bunga na.

46. Isu daytoy ti pintas na kanyak apo sir daytoy korrikulum, nga masapul nga para kanyak ket nasisita, adda mabukel kuma nga korrikulum para iti Northwest Philippines Annual Conference wenno NWPAC.

46. Necessity of the curriculum

R10:

47. It is a vital a importance to develop a church planting curricular because in former days the purposes with churches without a well set plan

48. it was only by the motivation to develop churches for church growth it was more of a church growth program and the curriculum was not so much given importance

49. as the enthusiasm of those who would want to go and plant churches it's because of the zeal of members to be able to do mission

50. and they call it mission churches at the start and they just do bible studies, visitations

51. they have no set curriculum actually they don't follow any curriculum.

47. The need for a detailed curriculum

48. Limited structure of church planting programs due to lack of curriculum

49. Lay empowerment and involvement in church planting

50. Engagement in missional activities

51. The need for a detailed curriculum

R11:

52. Napakahalaga na pag usapan ang church planting curriculum din or magkaroon ng curriculum para sa church planting.

53. I-isipin nag bible study tayo o nakakaroon ng Sunday School,

54. ito'y patungkol sa pagpapalago ng spiritwal na buhay ng isang tao.

55. Minsan lagi, tayong nakatuon kaya ngayon atin namang tignan na magkaroon sana ng curriculum patungkol sa church planting dahil ito ay tumutukoy sa paglago, pag paparami o pagbabahagi nang salita ng Diyos para atleast mas marami pa ang maliligtas.

56. Ang layunin ng simbahan ay hindi lang katulad ng Acts, na nagpaparami ng maliligtas.

57. Sa aking obserbasyon, karamihan sa ating simbahan ay nagiging kontento na na magsimba uwi or simbabuwe sabi nga po nila, Kung hindi naman say they

52. Curriculum as a necessity

53. Missional activities

54. Spiritual growth and empowerment

55. Biblically aligned curriculum, evangelism, discipleship, and growth as a community of God

56. A curriculum not just limited to soul winning

57. There should be an active ministry involved in the lives of the faithful believers.

58. Curriculum as a necessity

are maintaining only the status ko okay na yun sa kanila,
58. kaya iyon napakahalaga na magkaroon ng curriculum in terms of church planting.

R12:

59. Napateg ti panakabukel ti curriculum ti panagmula ti simbaan tapno maaddaan eti awagan tayo nga desinyo a suruten
60. tapno ditoy a maibinsa-binsa dagiti pamay-an, rubbeng nga aramiden ken pang-pangruna agsipod ta maysa eti calling ti naayaban nga agserbi ti Apo,
61. eti mangidanon ti damag ti sasao ni Apo Diyos ken kasta met ti pannakamuli da nga agbalin nga Kristyano ken mamati kenni Apo Diyos.

59. The curriculum as a framework
60. The curriculum as a manual in guiding, equipping and training the church leaders
61. Training in evangelism and soul winning

R13:

62. Mahalaga talaga ang pagtatanim ng para ma develops ang pag pagpupunla ng mga iglesia dito sa NWPAC.
63. Ang NWPAC kasi lalo na dito sa Southeast Pangasinan District hindi pa masyado natamnan ng United Methodist Church sa mga kabayanan dito,
64. kung meron man ang mga iglesia karamihan dito ay small church madalang lang yung big church mga ilan lang mga dalawa lang siguro ganun, pero karamihan niyan ay small church,
65. ang dalawang church ang gumagawa ay isang pastor,
66. kaya napaka importante ang curriculum sa pagtatanim ng mga iglesia sa lalong lalo na sa distritong ito na sakop ng NWPAC

62. The curriculum as a necessity
63. The need for more church planting mission endeavors
64. Lack of church planting mission
65. Lack of manpower
66. The curriculum as a necessity

R14:

67. Isang bagay na ating nakikita ang kahalagahan ng pagbuo ng curriculum sapagkat ang ating simbahan lalong-lalo na sa ang ating konferensya para may mas maayos na pagpapatupad at may isang hangarin
68. at patutunguhan para sa naayon at naangkop sa pangangailangan ng isang simbahan o isang komunidad.
69. Yon po ang nakikita ko na kadahilanan kung bakit mahalaga yong pagbuo ng curriculum para may order
70. kung ano yong mas importante na pangangailangan
71. hanggang mas mapalalim pa at madagdagan pa ang kaalaman nila.

67. The curriculum as universal system for church planting mission for goal orientation and implementation
68. Contextual and corresponds to the needs
69. Systematically organized curriculum
70. Need determination
71. The curriculum as a learning tool

R15:

72. Sa tingin ko ang kahalagahan ng isang kurikulum sa pagtatanim ng simbahan ay pag may sinusundan ka meron kang basehan,

73. kunwari ako nag te-take advantage akong mag aral ng christian education nasa puso ko kasi ang paglilingkod, ang pag mi-ministry

74. ay hindi kasi sapat na nasa puso mo lang yun kaya dapat may mga susundan kang mga basehan para alam mo kung papaano mo siya gagawin,

75. parang dito sa pagtatanim ng simbahan hindi lang kasi building ito so ang simbahan ay mga tao so dapat dun sa lugar na pagtataniman mo ito mapag aaralan mo kung papaano yung magiging approach mo sa ibat ibang klaseng personalidad ng tao and then yung approach kasi napakaimportante lalo na sa panahon ngayon kasi hindi pare pareho yung approach natin sa mga lugar.

76. Naniniwala ako napaka importante ito para may susundan tayo may magiging basehan tayo, hindi naman agad successful pero napakaimportante na may matibay tayo na pundasyon at ito yung mga kurikulum na magiging pundasyon natin sa pagdating ng simbahan.

72. The curriculum as a guide

73. Commitment driven curriculum

74. The curriculum as framework

75. Context determination, strategizing, and studying the people

76. The curriculum as framework

R16:

77. Sa pagka jntindi ko, pastor. Ang kahalagahan nito, kasi ang curriculum ang pagkakaintindi ko magseset na isang standard o kaya procedure.

78. Ang procedure na 'to ay para magkaroon ng curriculum para sa church planting curriculum para sa Northwest Philippines Annual Conference.

79. Ang nakikita ko rito, 'yong para ma sustain 'yong pagkakaroon ng ano... pag sprout o 'yong mga pag tubo ng mga churches. Ibig sabihin, hindi titigil 'yong pag-lago ng Northwest Philippjnes Annual Conference.

80. Ibig sabihin, kapag nasustain natin 'yong very existence ng NWPAC ay mag tutuloy-tuloy siya. Hjndi siya mawawala, iyon 'yong naintindihan ko po, pastor doon sa... ewan ko lang po kung tama pero that's what I understand po doon sa pagsasaliksik din kung ano ba 'yong ano niya...

81. kaya kailangang magkaroon din siya ng church planting curriculum para ayun nga, may sinusundan.

82. May sinusundan 'yong konferensya natjn, kung paano tayo gagalaw para sa pagpaplanting ng ating simbahan nating bago. Iyon po, pastor.

77. Systematically organized curriculum

78. A curriculum that will serve as a guide for church planting mission endeavors

79. Sustainability and continuous growth in spiritual formation and mission

80. Sustainability and structural integrity

81. Importance of curriculum as a guide

82. The curriculum as a framework for church planting mission programs

R17:

- 83. The importance of developing a church planting curriculum is for the church planting team.
- 84. So I am presuming that we have a team to be equipped with knowledge and skills,
- 85. so they could be prepared to know the how and the Why's the actually the 4 W's of the starting in your church community. It is beneficial for the team to know the why, what, who and where of church planting
- 86. that would become a roadmap of the church's mission
- 87. to reach people to believe in our Savior.
- 88. They have to be given enough knowledge as to how and the 4 W's would be answered
- 89. as they go on with this curriculum to be used for church planting .

- 83. Developing a committee to specifically handle church planting mission
- 84. Importance of group of expert people
- 85. Needs assessment, contextual and situational analyses
- 86. Concrete planning and strategizing
- 87. Soul winning
- 88. Training and equipping
- 89. The importance of curriculum in church planting mission

R18:

- 90. Ang nakikita kong importance nito ay meron tayong model, ayun kasi ang wala satin yung pag nagmission tayo o pag nagchu-church planting tayo ay sabog,
- 91. kasi kung saan saan tayo namimili, although maganda din naman parang sa kindergarten eclectic sabi namin yung magandang approach dito i-adopt mo pero kung purely satin siya purely methodist ang gumawa napakaganda na may model tayo
- 92. kasi magseserve siya na guide o magseserve siya ng guide parang sa mga corporate, pag sa corporate meron silang tinatawag na benchmark mga ganun.
- 93. Ako naexcite ako nung nabasa ko itong mga tanong mo, naexcite ako kasi matanda na ko parang wala akong naencounter na iisang ganun kurikulum sana sa church planting na atin talaga na UMC.
- 94. So, para sa kin magandang simula pag ka magawa mo ito hindi lang siya dahil magkakaroon ka ng uniform na guide,
- 95. although magkakaiba tayo ng culture kahit sabihin nating si isang conference tayo we have different cultures din like in Pangasinan, iba din ang sa ilocos pero in a way meron there is something common in us na taga NWPAC. Maganda ito pag matuloy na matapos mo ito very hopeful siya promising.

- 90. Framework
- 91. Contextual
- 92. Framework
- 93. Church planting curriculum in Wesleyan identity
- 94. Framework
- 95. Contextual and situational

<p>What do you think are the needs to develop a church planting curriculum for NWPAC? Why?</p>	<p>Open Coding</p>
<p>R1:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Kasapulan siguro iti kwa para kaniak ket kasapulan iti panangadal ti sitwasyon konteksto iti nwpac nga mismo 2. tapno maipakat no anya nga talaga iti subject wenno adalen iti nadumaduma nga paset iti nwpac. 3. Wen sitwasyon ken context kasi hindi natin hindi tayo makabuo ng curriculum kung hindi natin alam ang situation o context ng isang lugar lalong lalo na ang nwpac alam natin ang nwpac pero hindi natin alam ang sitwasyon at konteksto kung ano talaga ang dapat na buuin na pagaaral sa kabuuan ng nwpac. 4. Halimbawa yung curriculum ng scyd ano dapat ang kailangan nila di ba? Yung pinagusapan natin na caravaners yung hakbang ang kailangan nila 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Contextual study of NWPAC and situational analysis 2. Needs assessment 3. Contextual study of NWPAC and situational analysis 4. Determination of specific curriculum to assess the needs
<p>R2:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Ti ammok nga kasapulan tapno maaramid ti curriculum nga nabilligi ket awisen yo dagiti adda kapadasan na iti church planting. 6. Ngamin no awisen yo dagiti handa nga napadasan, theological laeng wenno theory laeng, baka nga agbalin nga theory laeng didiay simbaan 7. no wenno agawis kayo dagiti adda kapadasan na ay ket maibaga da no kasatno. So dagiti experiensyado. 8. Kung kailangang mangopya eh di kopyahin pero contextual naman na pangongopya. Wen kasdyan ti maisuggest ko nga kwa sumbat ko ti maikadwa apo. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Involvement of experienced church planters in the curriculum 6. Limitations of non-experienced church planters in actual practice 7. Involvement of experienced church planters in the curriculum 8. resourcefulness
<p>R3:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Ti ammok nga kasapulan isu didiay a careful nga ummuna didiay panagsurvey kadagiti mabalin nga panangipatakderan ti panagmulaan iti church iti panagpatakder iti local church 10. haan nga basta basta nga mapan ka magpatakder nu di kitdi masapol ti careful survey nu anya da nga potential nga kamkameng. 11. What are the potential members nga mabalin nga agkamkameng to iti dayta nga mapatakder nga simbaan 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Feasibility study / situational analysis 10. Conduct area surveys for church planting / site assessment 11. Identification of potential members 12. Needs assessment 13. The need for manpower 14. Planning with expert people 15. Financial needs

<p>12. tapno mai-input tayo diay plano no anya da dagiti masapol tayo.</p> <p>13. Syempre masapol tayo dagiti nadumaduma nangruna iti manpower, panagtrabaho uray to laeng ti panagplano dagiti mauna nga maibaon ti panagsurvey dagiti potential nga lugar nga pangipanan.</p> <p>14. Iti pannakaaramid ti church planting curriculum syempre kasapulan tayo met dagitay technocrats ditay nalaing met ah nga agplano tapno nasayaat met dadiay maaramid nga church planting curriculum. Daytoy siguro ti sapsapulen.</p> <p>15. Masapul met ti pinansyal nga suporta.</p>	
<p>R4:</p> <p>16. Unang una pagdating sa pangangailangan ano yung kailangan nating magawa syempre una sa lahat na gagawin natin diyan kailangan nating kilalanin ang NWPAC.</p> <p>17. Sa paanong paraan? Kumbaga meron tayong sinasabing learning situation.</p> <p>18. Una sa lahat yung capacity mo bilang church kung yung sitwasyon mo ba ay kaya na niyang magchurch planting o yung church naman</p> <p>19. community naman ay nakilala mo ba yung sitwasyon nila, ano yung pangangailangan nila?</p> <p>20. Kumbaga learning your situation, their situation and the whole situation</p> <p>21. para sa gayon ay magkaroon ka ng maliwanag na yung visions mo tsaka missions mo ano bang gagawin natin.</p> <p>22. So napakahalaga po yung bagay na ito para sa akin na kailangan nating madevelop lalo na yung kumbaga yung data gathering especially the</p> <p>23. geographical situation ano yung mga kultura konteksto nila</p> <p>24. kasi nga ito yung pagbabasehan natin kung ano yung mga possibility na pwede nating gawin na naayon sa kanila para sa ganoon ay mas akma yung mga pwede nating gawin. Yun yung nakikitang ko na kailangan nating gawin</p>	<p>16. Knowing the context of nwpac</p> <p>17. Situational analysis</p> <p>18. Determination of church capacity to handle church planting mission</p> <p>19. Survey and Assessment of community background and needs</p> <p>20. Assessment of overall needs including the church planter, the community, and the people involved</p> <p>21. Clarity of vision and mission</p> <p>22. The need for data and information gathering</p> <p>23. Determining the geographical and contextual situations</p> <p>24. Action based on context, situation, and need</p>
<p>R5:</p> <p>25. To develop the church planting curriculum, kailangan ang collaboration ng Lay people at tsaka yung mga Pastors, na collaboration na yan, mas Maganda.</p>	<p>25. Collaborative work between the church workers and the lay people</p> <p>26. Information sharing</p>

<p>26. Pangalawa, magkaroon ng best sharing practices ng mga lokal na Iglesia</p> <p>27. upang ito ay sandigan o magiging basic yung development ng ating tinatawag na church planting curriculum,</p> <p>28. kasi doon ang pinaka importante na malaman natin ang best practices</p> <p>29. at ganun din ang mga Layko kung ano yung pananaw nila patungkol doon sa church planting curriculum ng ating Iglesia.</p>	<p>27. Basis for church planting curriculum development</p> <p>28. Determination of effective methods</p> <p>29. Knowing the perspective of the lay people</p>
<p>R6:</p> <p>30. Sa tingin ko kasi, dapat maunawaan na, yung nature ng church. Ano ang nature ng church?</p> <p>31. Dapat makita niya sa kanyang sarili na innate sa kanya, intrinsic sa kanya yung church planting para gawin niya yun.</p> <p>32. Nag start yun sa preaching of the word, preaching the Gospel. So, the message should bring the Gospel to people.</p> <p>33. Pag yung tao nagrespond, those who would listen to the Gospel, nag respond yun, kailangan mo silang dalhin kasi sa isang community para doon sila mag grow, mag develop, manurture. Sa tingin ko, ganun. It could start in a small group, tapos doon sa larger na community sa church yun.</p> <p>34. Kasi kung church planting, 'di dalhin mo talaga doon sa mas malaki. So, parang there's an ecclesiola in ecclesia termino. Parang small church within the larger church, the ecclesia parang ganun yung nakikita ko.</p> <p>35. Mayroong need kasi nga, nature yung church na yun. Pag pinabayaan nung church, yun yung intrinsic nature niya, innate sa kanya, internal sa kanya yung nature niya na yun, hindi siya mag eexist na church. Tingin ko parang maging ordinary organization siya pagka ganun. Nawawala yung mandate niya kasi yung commissioning niya as a church.</p>	<p>30. Understanding the identity of the church</p> <p>31. A clear understanding of oneness with the church</p> <p>32. Evangelism</p> <p>33. Spiritual formation of the community</p> <p>34. Congregational building</p> <p>35. The church's identity of bringing people to God</p>
<p>R7:</p> <p>36. Masapol nga mabukel ti maysa a committee,</p> <p>37. ta daytoy iti mangtaming iti daytoy nga kunkuna tayo a curriculum.</p> <p>38. Kumbaga, special task force or committee,</p> <p>39. buklen daytoy dagiti Pastor, Layko, Diakonesa ken representative manipud kadagiti Lay Organizations</p>	<p>36. Organizational Structure</p> <p>37. Specific team for implementation</p> <p>38. Focus team</p> <p>39. Inclusive team members</p> <p>40. Needs assessment</p>

<p>40. ta isu da iti adadda a maka awat iti kasapulan dagiti tattao.</p>	
<p>R8: 41. Yes, kasapulan laeng nga adda ti motivations. 42. We have to adapt, we have to learn and also unlearn things, kasi baka may mga strategies noon na hindi applicable ngayon. 43. So, by knowing the needs of people who are really living in a digital way 44. maybe mag-a-adjust tayo as church in a way that we develop yong pangangailangan 45. na mapa-igting at mas maganda ang kalalabasan ng curriculum for church planting.</p>	<p>41. The need for motivation 42. Continuous education and adaptation 43. Contextual relevance 44. Organizational adaptability 45. Improvement of the curriculum</p>
<p>R9: 46. Para kanyak daytoy, pagarup ko. Haan nga kasla kana nga, teolohiya laeng ti pangibasaran tapno nu, ana daytoy kasi church planting daytoy eh. 47. Haan nga dayjay vision mo ket napintas idjay, kunkuna tayo latta nga kitkitaenen. Masapul nga adda dayjay panangadal kadayjay nga lugar. 48. Tapno, adda dayjay kuna tayo nga, dayjay haan laeng nga makapag mula tayo iti simbaan nu di ketdi, agmula tayo iti simbaan nga adda dagijay tattao. So, masapul nga kitaen dayjay nga lugar. Agmula ka ngarod iti simbaan, awan met tao! 49. So, masapul nga adda dayjay kuna tayo nga panang surbey kadayjay nga area 50. ken makita jay kasapulan da tapno nu dajigay... 51. Isuda ket maaddressan ngamin, nya tapno immuna ka nga nagpatakder iti simbaan, sir. Tapos, haan gayam nga... nagadayo gayam dagijay tattao. And then haan gayam dayjay iti.. kasta, kasla needs da. So, siguro mapasamak daytoy dayjay mapatakder nga simbaan ijay. 52. Uray kuna mon nakapinpintas, matay nga matay. Matay nga matay kasi, haan tay nga inadal nga nalang dayjay nga area. Dayjay lang ti pagarup ko nga makitak dijay nga saludsod, sir.</p>	<p>46. Actual practice 47. Strategic planning 48. Community presence and location feasibility 49. Situational assessment of a community 50. Community needs assessment 51. Addressing the needs of the community in a relevant manner 52. Importance of studying the community</p>
<p>R10: 53. Well, it is important to have a curriculum because in the first place you train those who will plant churches they know the goals and aims an objective.</p>	<p>53. Training and equipping 54. Systematic approach 55. Effective strategies and methods on church planting</p>

<p>54. And of course, to be more systematic in doing it.</p> <p>55. It's like well sorry for the reference, it's like the Iglesia ni Kristo's when they plant a church they have launch how to do it like, let's say first thing, second thing, third thing curriculum, also the Mormons they plant churches, they decide, it will be by pairs and then the curriculum they have at hand how to approach people.</p> <p>56. And so the response is more effective because they have a curriculum to follow</p> <p>57. and then that curriculum guide hindi motivation lang kailangan yong motivation magkaroon ng laman at iyon isa-sa-katuparan and it will happen because of it.</p>	<p>endeavors including implementation</p> <p>56. Importance of having a curriculum for guidance and strategy</p> <p>57. Practical application</p>
<p>R11:</p> <p>58. Napakahalaga na naman, na hindi lamang nakatuon ito sa mga pastor,</p> <p>59. we give importance to involve the laity,</p> <p>60. or we should develop or strengthen specific program for church planting such caravan training,</p> <p>61. why? We church workers cannot do it alone or hindi natin nagagampanan lahat ng mga trabaho, mas maraming magawa kung andyan ang mga layko na kailangang idevelop, we need to have a passion with heart in doing church planting.</p> <p>62. Tama, pastor tayo may mga layko natin sa simbahan pero minsan yung the passion of heart in doing church planting iyon yung hinahanap sana.</p>	<p>58. Inclusivity</p> <p>59. Lay empowerment</p> <p>60. Program development for specific needs</p> <p>61. Collaborative effort between the church workers and the lay people</p> <p>62. Passionate and committed people for church planting mission</p>
<p>R12:</p> <p>63. Tapno makabukel eti church planting curriculum masapol nga e-consider tayo ti human resources</p> <p>64. kas kadagiti ti tattao nga adda calling na daytoy a trabaho</p> <p>65. Pastor man wenno Layko</p> <p>66. ken kasta met eti financial nga aspeto</p> <p>67. agsipod ta pagsasao a kunada "You can not give what you cannot have." Haan mo maipaay diyay awan kenka kadagiti sabsabali.</p> <p>68. Sunga, no man kastoy ti mapasamak masapol ngarod nga ipaay diyay adda kenka</p> <p>69. tapno eti kasta ket ag-materialize diyay maysa nga banag a kayat tayo nga aramiden.</p>	<p>63. Inclusivity and openness to others</p> <p>64. Encouraging the spiritually gifted people to join the cause</p> <p>65. Inclusivity and openness to others</p> <p>66. Addressing financial needs</p> <p>67. Being resourceful</p> <p>68. Utilize available resources</p> <p>69. Realization of goals and objectives</p>
<p>R13:</p>	<p>70. Need for manpower</p> <p>71. Lack of manpower</p>

70. Ang pangangailangan talaga workers, nangangailangan tayo ng mga pastor lalo na ngayon, ang report ng board of ordain ministry at saka DCOM, zero ang candidate to ministry. Ang mga naordinahan diyan ay isa lang sa entire NWPAC at iisa din yata yung makomisyonan.

71. So nakita nating ang scarcity ng mga pastor, kung ganun posibilidad yan magiging tatlo na ang iglesiang hawakan ng isang pastor mahirap na yun kaya kailangan talaga ang mga workers, although sa iglesia ko naman may tatlo akong kinausap na miyembro prospect,

72. sa tatlong yon walang nagbuluntaryo although ang feeling nila gusto naman nila pero pag dating sa seryosohan na magkakandidito sana sa DCOM o pupunta sa BOOM, hindi nila macommit ang sarili nila,

73. yung isa nga ay nasa abroad na at yung isa naman ay asawa na ng attorney sabi medyo magandang buhay nurse naman siya pero involve sila sa church aktibo naman sila sa church nakakasama ko sila sa church. Kaya yun ang basehan ko kung bakit para sa kanila ang pagpapastor pero yun nga mahirap naman na pipilitin mo baka mamaya bigla namang aalis, yan kailangan talaga ng mga workers sa pag develop ng mga workers.

72. Fear of greater responsibility

73. Recruitment efforts to become church workers

R14:

74. Sa palagay ko ang mga pangangailangan upang bumuo ng curriculum sa pagpapatayo ng simbahan sa ating konferensya. Yan ang nakikita kasi may iba't-ibang katuruan ng mga iba't-ibang simbahan kaya mas maganda kung ano yong stand or doktrina o katuruan ng ating simbahan yon ang kailangan para may iisang format.

75. Yon ang nakikita ko bilang Metodista para makita natin na metodista tayo hindi baka mamaya mayroon silang marining though alam natin na open, pero bilang metodista sa ating konferensya dapat may iisa lang yong stand natin, katuruan natin.

76. Hindi yong, okay narinig ko ito pero dapat ano bang totoo yon yong nakikita ko na kailangan dito.

74. Need for a unified curriculum

75. Ensuring the united methodist identity

76. Pursuing the right doctrine and biblical teaching

R15:

77. Recruiting the right manpower

77. Unang una kailangan, pero hindi ko alam kung tama yung term ko na makita o makahanap yung mga tamang tao,
78. kasi lahat naman tayo ay may calling na tinatawag pero ibat iba kasi yung calling natin so meron.
79. ang unang una nating kailangan dito is yung tamang tao,
80. napakahirap anuhin yung pangangailangan kasi dito lang sa distrito namin pag sinabi nilang pangangailangan pagdating ng simbahan kasi hindi siya ganun kadali,
81. dapat dito hindi lang nasa puso mo yung ginagawa mo, napakaimportante na committed ka kasi pag nasa puso mo tapos committed ka susunod na dun yung gusto mong pag aralan lahat para maitanim mo yung simbahan na yun. Basta ang sa tingin kong nakikita ko na pangangailangan upang mabuo ang kurikulum. Hindi naman kasi madalas na kurikulum kasi, pag sinabi nating kurikulum {sabi mo nga kanina po subject yun di ba tama?} pero may mga tao kasing i-aano mo sila ng mga, ganyan sabi kurikulum pero kung wala sa puso nila yung ginagawa nila tas hindi sila committed pano sila magtanim ng simbahan lang sa tingin ko, oo kasi ang daming napapansin ko based on my experience ang daming mga members na meron talaga sila kaisipan pero pero kinukulang sila sa puso,
82. kaya parang feeling ko kung meron kang kaisipan, kaalaman, puso at hindi ka committed parang walang saysay.
83. Mas maganda kung meron kang puso tas committed ka tas may kaisipan ka, yun ang nakikita kong talagang pangangailangan para makapag tanim ng simbahan
84. so parang magtrain po tayo ng mga tao na magiging committed tas yung parang makikita nila,
85. ang sabi ko nga kanina ibat iba kasi yung calling natin pero kung yung calling na yun parang yung kabataan po natin kanina so naintindihan ko yung point niya may iba iba po tayong mga calling or talent pero mas okay kung may mas maglalabas nun sa kanila.

78. Assessment of spiritual gifts
79. Recruiting the right manpower
80. Addressing the needs
81. Emphasizing commitment in doing ministry
82. The importance of commitment
83. Combination of desire, commitment, and knowledge as a holistic need
84. Understanding commitment as integral part of manpower
85. Assessment of spiritual gifts

R16:

86. Saakin, pastor. Magbibigay lang ako ng dalawa. Ang una ano, ang isang pastor ay magkaroon siya ng clear preaching o klarong, paglalahad o pagpapaliwanag tungkol sa ano natin, paniniwala natin bilang isang metodista.

87. Iyong isa, dahil nakikita ko na kapag maintindihan ng mga bagong... 'yong mga hinihikayat nating maging miyembro.

88. Napaka importanteng nakikita nilang maganda 'yong layunin ng local church o kaya ng isang church natin,

89. kaya nung katulad nga ng pastor na nagprepreach ay mas nakikita kong mas madaling mahikayat 'yong mga gusto nating maging kasapi sa pagiging metodista. Iyon ang una, pastor.

90. Iyong pangalawa ay magkaroon ng sapat na training, 'yong mga tutulong o kaya ibig sabihin 'yong gaganap o makikijoin.

91. Ibig sabihin, kapag nag church planting activities, sila 'yong mga taong character doon sa pag church planting activity.

92. Kailangan sila'y ano, magkaroon sila ng... bawa't isa ay may sapat na training lalo na sa leadership training para maski sino sakanila ay puwedeng sila ang tumayo para simulan 'yong church planting curriculum.

93. Iyon siguro 'yong dalawang nakikita kong importante para saakin kung ano 'yong needs para makapag simula.

94. Kasi, kapag magaling ang isang pastor na nagpapaliwanag, naniniwala ako na mas marami siyang mahihikayat.

95. Pangalawa, syempre sabi ko nga, sa pagiging magaling na pastor ay kailangan din siyang marunong mag lead. Ayun lang po, pastor ang maiincontribute ko doon sa pangalawang tanong.

R17:

96. In developing church planting curriculum for NWPAC, we definitely need a pool of writers who have a passion

97. that would promote deep spirituality

98. to have a clear vision towards church mission.

99. It helps also, if there is a specific committee

86. Importance of training in biblical and UMC doctrines, and evangelism

87. Training in evangelism

88. Clarity of the church's goal, vision and mission

89. Membership growth, invitation, and soul winning

90. Inclusiveness and training of manpower

91. Importance of manpower

92. Leadership trainings for task delegation

93. Needs determination

94. Importance of training in biblical and UMC doctrines, and evangelism

95. Leadership training for church leaders

96. Importance of committed experts who will help and contribute in the church planting curriculum

97. Spiritual empowerment

98. Clarity of vision and mission

99. Organizational structure

100. to plan and handle the needs of church planting mission of the church.

100. Concrete planning and needs determination

R18:

101. Para sakin, importante din yung alamin natin yung context ng mga churches natin specially by district, kagaya dito samin sa Cordillera iba yung approach dito ng pagmimisyon iba din ang approach diyan sa Pangasinan for sure iba din sa Ilocos. Napakaganda na malaman natin yung context ng mga lugar at mga tao,

101. Contextual and situational analyses
102. Strategic planning

102. tapos church mapping, kasi pag may church mapping tayo alam mo kung kanino mo siya iaangkla hindi kasi pwede yung magtanim tayo ng church tapos ang layo layo pala nung mag nu-nurture sa kanya, so eventually nangyayari ito dahil naging experience namin dito sa Baguio, marami kaming misyon na sobrang layo, meron kami as far as sa Dupax, nagchurch plan kami doon pero baguio ang mother church niya. Maganda na nasimulan naming ng ganun pero ang nakakalungkot dahil hindi siya nasustain dahil sa sobrang layo, so sabi ko mahalaga yung mag church mapping tayo, kunwari kung nakapag tanim kana doon alam mo kung sino ang magnu-nurture sa kanya at kung sino yung magpapatuloy, hindi kasi pwede talaga yung napakalayo pang church ang pupunta dun dahil hindi niya yun magagawa weekly,

103. Importance of consistent actions in mission programs
104. Intentional disciple ministries
105. Social ministry programs
106. Sustainability and consistency
107. Importance of follow up

103. mawawala yung consistency

104. tapos importante din yung mas strengthen yung discipleship ministries talaga ng church natin lalo na yung church na nangangarap talagang gawin ito, di pwede ngayon yung “intay ag mission!” ganun

105. tapos ayun na may medical dental at kung anu-ano nang uri ng way na ginagamit nating strategies

106. na ginagawa tas yun parang hindi siya nasustain so sayang yun para ka lang yung parable of the sower na de sabog, nagsabog lang siya ng seeds tapos iniwan na.

107. Siguro naman kasi ang salita ng Diyos ay very alive yan pero syempre pag walang nagfollow up ay sayang siya.

Do you have any biblical and theological bases on church planting mission? Can you share them to me? Why?

Open Coding

R1:
 1. Nasa isip ko palaging ang tungtungang biblical sa pagmimisyon at pageevangelize ay yung matthew na sinabi ni hesus na humayo kayo matthew 28 the great commission yung ipangaral ninyo.
 2. yun naman ang batayan ng pagmimisyon
 3. na kahit sino kahit saan ang mahalaga ay ipangaral ang salita ng Diyos sa ibang tao.
 4. Yung ang tinatawag nilang great commission. Marami pa pero ito ang mas tumpak sa pagmimisyon at pagtanim ng iglesia. Kasi kung biblical foundation, ito talaga ang hinahanap nila eh bakit tayo mag mimisyon bakit tayo magchuchurch planting dahil ba sa sabi ni ptr pot? Hindi eh dahil ganito ang command ng Diyos magmisyon tayo at mangaral ng Kanyang salita.
 5. Isa pa yung acts 1:8. Yun.

1. The great commission matthew 28:16-20
2. The great commission as the basis for mission
3. Sharing the gospel or evangelism
4. Prioritizing the great commission as the foundation of church planting mission
5. Acts 1:8 as additional basis for church planting mission

R2:
 6. Turning point met ti church tayo nga dapat maawatan dagiti miembro. Daytoy matthew 28:18-20,
 7. daytoy ti ibagbaga ni apo Dios nga masapol nga maaddaan to compelling vision for intentional disciple making. It is a must. Ngamin no haanka nga agkaroon ti vision nga agpayso, iti major task ti simbaan ket mapukaw ka a. and no naaddan koma iti church ito intentional discipleship process
 8. ket amin koma ang aktibidad wenno program ket subservient ito daytoy. They must be supportive to this vision. And this vision should become the reason why the church wakes up in the morning or
 9. the lay people plan or think. Dadiay koma ti nangnangrona.
 10. Clear vision for intentional discipleship must be written out and
 11. make church planting taught. Kasdyay kakabsat. Ti maysa nga akayat ko nga ibaga. And then masapol nga ma-inculcate met ti values for intentional discipleship.

6. Understanding of The great commission Matthew 28:18-20 as the turning point of church planting mission
7. Importance of vision and intentional discipleship as a response to the great commission
8. The church activities must be in line to the great commission and should be implemented
9. Involvement of the lay people
10. Systematic and clear approach on discipleship programs
11. Educating the church leaders
12. Goal oriented and output-based training programs for church leaders
13. Leadership training in line with biblical doctrines

12. Kasla koma dadiay saludsod nga “Are we building discipleship making programs or are we building a disciple making culture? Dadiay saludsod nga “What kind of disciples are we producing? Are we producing principled leaders? Kas mapasamak iti church tayo tatta.

13. Kasla da nga principled ta mabalin met kanon ti agasawa ti lalake-lalake. So masapul nga inPLACE kuma daytoy values nga nangnangrona iti panagaramid ti discipleship

14. ken masapul sa nga balbaliwan tayo ti Sistema eksakto met ketdi a bro ngamin no ag-regionalization tayonton mabalin tayo nga pusipusen no kasano ni system tayo ti uneg ti church on how to make disciples and and later on plant churches.

15. Isu nga importante dayta values ken ti maudi masapol nga inPLACE dagiti vehicles for intentional discipleship kasla koma strategies for winning souls. Kasano ngay nga ag-evangelize tayo, after evangelism kasano ngay nga i-build tayo isuda?

16. Kas koma transformation dagiti events nga ken programsen. Dapat kuma ket agikabil tayo ti transformational processes like care groups, small groups.

17. And then adda kuma ti systema met ngay nga trust strategy nga we send them, we deploy them. Tapno no haan nga maaramid ti kasta, awan ngay ti maimula nga simbaan nga agpayso.

18. So kasta lang ti makunak ti kunkuna ni Apo Dios nga Go and make disciples, dapat intentional po tayo.

19. Mabalin siguro nga mabaliwan tayo diay Sistema nga minsan puro events tayo ngamin ngay. Siguro mapansin mo bro met dayta. Events and programs not transformational processes nga isumet ti Makita tayo tatta. Daydiay bro ti nababa nga theological nga kwak ti matthew 28.

R3:

20. Daydiay nga general nga great commission, matthew 28. Daydiay ti maysak nga makitkitak. No daytoy met nga theological nga pagbatayan tayo nagadu met.

21. Maysa nga kwa ti iglesiya tayo daytoy mission program tano nakapuy ti mission

14. Adapt and realign mission programs according to the contextual needs

15. Recruitment and training of manpower in biblical doctrines

16. Adapt and realign mission programs according to the contextual needs

17. Goal oriented and output-based training programs for church leaders

18. Importance of vision and intentional discipleship as a response to the great commission

19. Adapt and realign mission programs according to the contextual needs

20. The great commission matthew 28 16:20 as the theological basis and foundation of church planting mission

21. Establishment of program and mission

program strategy tayo nakapsut met ti panagmula ti iglesiya,
22. no kwa dadduma dagitoy support mission support kinagpayso na, nagmission kami didiay pasuquin ti kwa nga church nga nagmission ti pasuquin ket ti church ti bugnay, wen ilocos north.
23. Bugnay ti nangrungruna dayta nga mission. No away daydiay nga commitment dagiti kamkameng dagiti iglesiya haan ka nga agprosper.
24. Isu nga dadiay iglesiya tayo idia pasuquin, nagibabbaon kami ti agtutubo nga napan.
25. Immuna ti VCS, pagkatapos napan ti mission worker tayo didiay.
26. Idi naammoan mi nga addu ti prospect, nagstrategize to bugnay umc, dakamin nga leader ti napan.

strategies to strengthen church planting mission endeavors
22. Strengthening of missional support from other churches. Establishment of support system
23. Importance of commitment of those who will be involved in the support system
24. Involvement of lay people
25. Implementation of bible-based programs
26. Improvement and enhancement mission programs

R4:
27. Normal naman sa atin yon yung sa matthew 28 yung go and make disciples of all nations baptizing them teach them.
28. Yun ay hindi request ito ay command kaya nga sabi nila we are commissioned, ibig sabihin nun partner tayo ng Diyos so it is beyond our responsibilities and duties.
29. Ibig sabihin niya ditto intentional kailangan nating gawin yun yung dapat nating gawin. Ano pa ba yung pwede nating gawin pag magiging kristiano? Wala na tayong ibang pwedeng gawin because we are commissioned partners tayo ng Panginoon na itutuloy ang misyon.
30. Sa number 1 sa pagpapalaganap ng kanyang salita its all about His grace at tsaka yung pagmamahal. Yan ang isasagot ko sayo.

27. The great commission matthew 28 16:20 as the theological basis and foundation of church planting mission
28. Action based ministries and programs
29. Intentional mission programs
30. Importance of evangelism and knowledge of the bible

R5:
31. Ito yung pinaka maganda Pastor, itong Biblical Theological. Para saakin, in my point of view, I would like to share with you yung Matthew 28: 19-20. Pwede na basahin ko sayo itong teksto na ito na matatagpuan sa Matthew upang bigyan ko ng kahalagahan. Mula po sa lenggwaheng Ilocano, Matthew 28: 19-20. Daytoy to pagpintasan na Pastor: "Inkay ngarud kadagiti amin a tattao iti amin a lugar, ket pagbalinenyo ida nga adalak: buniaganyo ida iti

31. The great commission matthew 28:19-20 as the biblical foundation and basis of church planting mission
32. Action based ministries and programs
33. Evangelism
34. Community building
35. The great commission Matthew 28:19-20 as the

nagan ti Ama, ti Anak ken ti Espiritu Santo, ken isuroyo ida nga agtungpal kadagiti amin nga imbilinko kadakayo. Laglagipenyo nga addaakto nga agnanayon kadakayo agingga iti panungpalan ti lubong.” So from this Pastor, ito talaga yung pinaka biblical para saakin.

32. Dahil ito ay utos ng ating Panginoon. Nasaan mang dako ng mundo, puntahan natin

33. upang ipangaral ang salita ng Diyos.

34. Habang maraming mga tao dun na tumatanggap sa salita ng Diyos, ibig sabihin talagang mayroong Iglesia na maipapatayo sa bawal lugar.

35. Ito yung pinaka basic para sa akin na pundasyon ng tinatawag nating church planting curriculum.

biblical foundation and basis of church planting mission

R6:

36. Sa akin, mas doon pa sa Acts 2:1, Pentecost, yung reference natin sa Pentecost. Basta yung chapter two ng Acts, it could be the whole chapter or kung pupwedeng hanggang doon one to ano bang verse yan, basta yung coming of the spirit, considered to be the birthday kasi of the the church yan.

37. Maraming nagsasabi na komentarista sa biblia or even scholars of the bible na, yung chapter two ng Acts, ay birth of the church. Ako marami na rin akong times na ginamit ko ito pag iniinvite ako na maging anniversary speaker. So yung verse ng church.

38. Parang doon sa chapter one ng Acts. Acts 1:4, ganito sinasabi diyan: “And while staying with them he ordered them not to depart from Jerusalem, but wait for the promise of the Father which He said,” you heard from me.

39. For John baptized with water, but you will be baptized with the Holy Spirit so not many days from now.” So, antayin niyo yung promise na ang Holy Spirit, yung the day of Pentecos, you wait for the day of Pentecos. Parang ito yung commissioning ng bawat disciples, sa tingin ko. Kasi wala pa naman yatang nakikitang established pa na church dito noon kung tutuusin. Kasi after resurrection pa ito, yung post resurrection community ng mga natatakot na. Pero with the spirit counts, ito yung

36. Acts 2 as biblical and theological basis for church planting mission

37. The birth of the church started in Acts

38. The importance of the empowerment of the Holy Spirit

39. The Holy Spirit as the helper in all mission endeavors

40. The Holy Spirit provides the gifts and provision for missional purposes

41. Acts 2 as biblical and theological basis for church planting mission

42. Evangelism without borders

43. Action based faith, ministries, and programs

empowerment nila. Ito yung commissioning nila, so the disciples were set aside to do particular task of ministry. Yung proclamation of the word. Doon sa chapter two verse eight, verse eleven.

40. Basta yung chapter two kasi, when they received the Holy Spirit, na empower sila. Ano yung empowerment nila, they were able to speak in other languages, different languages. Ano laman ng message nila? Yung mighty works of God. Sabi nila, Bakit sila Galileans? Bakit tayo iba-iba yung pananalita natin? Pero naririnig natin sila nagsasalita sa mother language natin. And we heard them telling in our own tongues, the mighty works of God. So, they were able to testify because of the empowerment of Spirit, testify in people's language.

41. Yung sa akin, parang mas ganun pa. Mas doon ko tinitignan na ang pinaka pupwede sa akin na bersikulo nito, biblical reference ng church planting yun.

42. So, ibig sabihin nun, yung proclamation natin it goes beyond language barrier atsaka yung cultural barrier.

43. Kasi yung ano, pag language barrier kasi, kasama yung kultura. Yung language kasi makikita mo anong kultura ang meron diyan. Ibig sabihin nun, kahit anong kultura mo, kahit anong panahon mo, kapanahunan mo, kahit na sino ka, yung pagiging sino ka man, o anong lahi mo, ano pa yung magiging pananampalataya mo, talagang obligado tayo bilang church na proclaim the mighty works of God, and Jesus Christ. Specifically, center yung Gospel.

R7:

44. *Romans 10: 14-15, sinasabi doon "How then will they call on him in whom they have not believed? And how are they to believe in him of whom they have never heard? And how are they to hear without someone preaching? And how are they to preach unless they are sent? As it is written, "How beautiful are the feet of those who preach the good news!"*

45. Evangelism is key to extending the kingdom but is often neglected,

46. when there is a lot going on within the workings of the church.

44. Romans 10:14-15 as the biblical and theological basis for church planting mission

45. The importance of evangelism as ministry

46. Importance of manpower

47. Spirit-filled people for church planting mission endeavors

48. Evangelism and preaching

47. But church plants, infused the body with momentum and energy. Though, church planting takes a lot of resources and energy to put in motion.

48. Always remember, that your endeavors will need that someone else or many hear the word of God.

49. Daytoy siguro iti makunak met nga teolohikal nga pagbatayan iti misyon iti Iglesia.

50. Masapol kas kuna iti Romans 10: 14-15, mapan ka nga umuna, ammoem iti kasapulan dagiti tattao, isu iti ibingay mo kada kuwada.

R8:

51. Ito naman na yong very familiar sa atin as United Methodist Church na lagi nating naririnig the great commission in Matthew 28:19-20 Therefore, go and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father and of the Son and of the Holy Spirit. And teaching them to obey everything I have commanded you and surely I am with you always to the very end of age.

52. So, it's actually the mandates of our Lord Jesus Christ.

53. Bagama't ito ay Theological speaking ito ay intended for the Israelites. Kasi yong kausap ng ating Panginoong Hesu Kristo rito ay ang mga hudyo. So, part of our Bible is nariyan na ang apostle Paul na naging Apostol ng mga hentil. And we Filipinos ay hindi naman mga Jews, so yong parang naging apostol ng mga hentil ay si apostol Paul dahil sa kaniyang na reveal yong mystery na nai-a-apply para lang sa mga gentiles na pwede rin namang manampalataya ang mga hudyo rito at yong mga hudyo ay magiging, kaya nga may talatang sinasabi si apostol Paul na pinag-isa na niya yong dalawang grupo the Israelite's or the Jews and the Gentiles.

54. So, the Israelite's, the Jews can believe on the product of salvation, the life, death and resurrection of our Lord Jesus Christ na kung sila ay mananampalataya doon and then they could obtain salvation

55. na yon yong napapanahon para sa mga gentiles so wala ng, sabi ulit ni Apostol Paul wala ng mga babae, walang lalaki, wala ng hentil, wala

49. Romans 10:14-15 as the biblical and theological basis for church planting mission

50. Biblical mandate on the determination and addressing of needs

51. The great commission Matthew 28:19-20 as the basis for church planting mission endeavors

52. The goal of mission

53. Different context but one faith. Unity in diversity

54. Core beliefs of faith

55. Inclusivity, non-discriminating faith, and openness to all

56. Evangelism and response

57. Theological framework of church planting mission

ng Israel kasi pinag-isa na sa pamamagitan ng ating magandang balita ng kaligtasan sa pamamagitan ng anak ng Diyos.

56. So, yon na yong misyon ng church maipalaganap ito at ang mga hudyo hindi converted as Christians na tayo rin naman naging Christianized nation.

57. At regarding doon sa church planting or church planting nation ito yong pinanghahawakan natin bagama't ini-uugnay natin ito doon din sa sinasabi ni San Pablo.

R9:

58. Masapul ngamin nga kitaen tayo met laeng jay pagbatayan iti ibagbaga ti bibliya. Umuna iti amin, dayjay 'great comission'.

59. Ibagbaga na ijay nga, "baptizing them" ngem haan nga agpatingga idjay jay 'baptizing them' eh.

60. Jay maikaduwa nga ibagbaga na idjay ket, 'train or isurom ida'.

61. So, makitkitak ditoy nga teolohiya dayjay, nga kalpaskan nga pinagbalin mo nga adalan isuda. Masapul nga adda dayjay nurture isu dayjay kunana nga, nu kitaen tay dayjay great comission ket, "baptizing them in the name of the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit". And, isurom ida! Isu dayjay. Ken maysa pay dayjay, maysa nga teohiya na daytoy kasi kuna...

62. uray kuna ni Apo Jesus jay Marcos nga, "bay-an yo nga umay kanyak dagiti ubbing". Bagbaga na met lang idjay nga maibilang nga dagijay nga tattao, nga haan da pay nga totally nga namati. Ibilang da nga kas iti katigorya na ubbing nga masapul nga, anaen isuda nga sursur..

63. nga, ipakaawat kanyada ti kinapateg ti panamati kinni Apo Diyos. Awaten da ti nasantoan nga bendi... bautismo.

64. And then, haan lang nga agpatingga idjay met. Inawat da lattan, nu di ketdi adda dayjay kuna tayo nga sumaruno nga hakbang wenno aramiden tayo tapno talaga nga masursuro da, aramiden da jay task a kas maysa nga kristyano. Dayjay met laeng, sir.

R10:

65. Well, of hand, the one thing that I have in mind is when Jesus saw the crowds, He looked at

58. The great commission Matthew 28:16-20 as the basis for church planting mission

59. Soul winning by letting them respond to the good news of God

60. Intentional discipleship and mentoring

61. Emphasis on Christian growth

62. Inclusivity and openness

63. Christian education

64. Intentional discipleship and mentoring

65. The importance of manpower as workforce to God's mission

<p>them like sheep without a shepherd and He said the harvest is plentiful but the laborers are few.</p> <p>66. I think in our own day you can state the same way that the harvest is plentiful but the laborers are few.</p> <p>67. In fact, it's getting fewer and fewer and so the need for, the church planting curriculum will at the same time revive, revive the faith of members and aside from their zeal.</p> <p>68. And you know, they'll feel motivated and then they will see the like Jesus they see the crowds like sheep without a shepherd.</p> <p>69. Well, I, for me that's a very, that image is very strong image of the need for church planting.</p> <p>70. When I heard church there are more of communities of faith I don't see church as individual conversions. I see church as a community transformation.</p>	<p>66. Recruitment and training programs</p> <p>67. The importance of church planting curriculum in addressing the needs of the church</p> <p>68. The curriculum will bring hope and motivation to the people to participate in God's mission</p> <p>69. Emphasizing the importance of church planting curriculum</p> <p>70. The curriculum as a transformative endeavor inclusive and open to all</p>
<p>R11:</p> <p>71. Yes, we have a mainly biblical basis, but I would like to share it to you the biblical basis taken from the books of Acts 8:4, napapaloob dito, "but the believers who were scattered preach the good news about Jesus wherever they went",</p> <p>72. sino ba ang unang nag plant ng seed noong nabuwag ang mga believers sa Jerusalem? Edi mga layko, ito yung mga layko</p> <p>73. na they are filled with the holy spirit</p> <p>74. kaya kailangan natin ipanalangin</p> <p>75. na magkaroon ng matatayang na layko maging ang mga pastor matatayang na kung saan yung espiritong ng katapangan sa pag pagpapalago or doing church planting ay nasa kanila.</p> <p>76. Tignan natin itong verses na ito ay mga layko, take note! mga layko sila hindi sila pastor, pero natutunan nila narinig nila ang salita, kahit hindi mo sinasabi ay talagang ginawa nila ang church planting para mismo ipagsigawan nila ng kabutihan ng Diyos sa kanilang buhay kung paano iniligtas ang Diyos ang buhay nila.</p>	<p>71. Acts 8:4 as the biblical and theological basis of church planting mission</p> <p>72. Lay involvement in mission activities</p> <p>73. Spiritual empowerment</p> <p>74. Devotional life</p> <p>75. Spiritual empowerment</p> <p>76. Lay empowerment</p>
<p>R12:</p> <p>77. No eti panagbasbasak eti bibliya no eti kastoy nga salusod manipod eti Ma-Ikaduwa ti Timoteo kunana</p>	<p>77. The letter of Paul to Timothy as biblical and theological basis for church planting mission</p> <p>78. Evangelism</p>

78. "E-komit mo kadagiti tattao a pagtalkan dagiti panursoro a nangngeg mo nga inkasabak ed sangwanan eti addo a saksi
79. isudan to met ti mangisuro kadagiti sabsabali."
80. Sunga, daytoy ket maysa nga banag tapno adda eti naballaigi a pannakaidanon
81. ken panangbingay ti sasao ni Apo Diyos nga agbunga eti pannakabukel eti grupo dagiti mamati a mangbukel ti Iglesya lokal kaniya tayo.

79. Discipleship
80. Systematic and orderly implementation
81. Result based mission programs

R13:
82. Wala namang espesipikong sabi niya na magtanim kayo ng iglesia para sa akin, so surprise yung tanong na yun.
83. Ang maalala lang yung sabi ni Jesus Christ kay Pedro "I will give you the keys of the kingdom of heaven; whatever you bind on earth will be bound in heaven, and whatever you loose on earth will be loosed in heaven."
84. so ibig sabihin nun ay the authority to anyone will receive the gospel, ang sabi ng panginoon ay "i will build my church" para sa kanila "and the gates of hell shall not prevail against it."
85. Yung mga sulat lang naman ni Pablo ay sa book of Romans na may church doon at sa book of Corinthians, Galatians at Ephesians, yun naman ang ebidensyang may mga churches na mga ganun
86. at saka yung bilin ng panginoon na "Go ye into all the world and preach the gospel to every creature"
87. pero hindi niya sinabi doon na church,
88. basta "go ye" "na ipangaral ang mga salita ko sa lahat ng sulok ng mundo.
89. Not necessarily you will build a church there. Ganun lang sa akin lang yun.

82. The biblical and theological basis of church planting in a holistic approach
83. A Christian mandate for doing church planting mission
84. Mission of God
85. Church planting of early churches in the 1st century AD
86. The great commission Matthew 28:16-19 as the biblical basis of church planting
87. Emphasis on evangelism rather than intensive church planting mission
88. Christian education through evangelism
89. Emphasis on evangelism rather than intensive church planting mission

R14:
90. Well, alam naman natin yong sa familiar na biblical verse yong Matthew 28:18-20 yong great commission
91. dahil tayo'y inatasan at binigyan ng karapatan or power
92. para magbahagi ng salita ng Diyos saan mang lugar

90. The Great commission Matthew 28:18-20 as the biblical and theological basis of church planting mission
91. A Christian mandate for doing church planting mission
92. Evangelism
93. Spiritual empowerment
94. Soul winning

93. na sa pamamagitan ng kapangyarihan ng banal na espirito at sa tulong ng panginoong Diyos
94. para sa ganoon ay mapalapit sila sa ating panginoong Hesus
95. at ang utos na ito ni Hesus sa kaniyang mga disipolo na gawing alagad ang mga disipolo para sa sanlibutan.
96. Lahat ito ay iniutos ni Hesus na natural na nangangailangan ng pagtatayo ng mga lokal na komunidad ng pananampalataya o mga simbahan.
97. Humayo kayo Go and make them disciples so parang lahat tayo ay binibigyan niya ng oportunidad
98. at alam ko na hindi lamang mga pastor ang binigyan nito pati mga lyco.
99. Yon po yong nakikita ko sa great commission na binigay ng ating panginoong Hesus.

95. Discipleship and mentorship
96. A Christian mandate for doing church planting mission
97. Discipleship and mentorship
98. Lay involvement
99. The Great commission Matthew 28:18-20 as the biblical and theological basis of church planting mission

R15:
100. Ngayon kung eto pong tanong natin ito ay wala pa akong nabasa o naging batayan sa bibliya sa pagtanim ng simbahan. Meron akong anak four year old kaya habang lumalaki po yun hinahayaan ko lang po siyang kahit maglilikut yan diyan sa harap ng altar, naalala ko po yung yung verse na yun o yung ano na yun sa bible,
101. kasi yung anak ko po dahil hinahayaan ko siya sa altar four year old pa lang yung hindi ko siya binabawalan kahit sinasabi nilang makulit hindi ko siya binabawalan dahil ah nakakatuwa dahil ngayon po four year old siya
102. pero pag tumugtog yung prison worship naming kahit mabigat yung base guitar bubuhatin niya po yan at tutugtog siya ng may ano kaya alam niyo po nakakatuwa po yung ganun lalo na po sa mga bata natin
103. siguro dito sa pagtanim, kasi ang pagtanim hindi lang naman po yan i think diyan sa mga young people oo mas maganda pong nauumpisahan natin yan habang bata pa sila
104. kasi hayaan po natin sila kahit maglaro sila sa altar ang importante ay paunti unti po habang maliliit sila makilala po nila kung sino si Hesus kasi unti unti nilang maaano yan

100. Matthew 19:14 as the biblical and theological basis for mission
101. Openness to possibilities
102. Taking action on certain conditions
103. Inclusiveness and openness
104. Letting them learn and discover something
105. Preparation, initiation, and taking responsibility

<p>105. hanggang pagdating ng araw sila po yung magiging church natin yung mga bata na yan. Ayun po maraming salamat po.</p>	
<p>R16: 106. Ang saakin, pastor. Binalikan ko ‘yong isang verse na parang related dito. Iyong Mateo 28:18-19, 107. ang sinasabi sa english “And Jesus came and said to them, all authority in heaven and on earth has been given to me. 108. Go, therefore, and make disciple of all nations. Baptizing them in the name of the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit.” 109. So I think, dito nagsisimula ‘yong pag church planting curriculum. 110. Dahil dito, inutos nga ng ating Panginoon Hesus na dumami ‘yong mga discipulo niya. 111. Discipulo na naniniwala at ikalat. 112. Dahil nga, ang gusto ng ating Panginoong Hesus ay kung puwede, lahat ay ma save. Hindi po ba? 113. At magkaroon ng buhay na walang hanggan. Iyon po ang pagkakaintindi ko po, pastor sa pangatlong tanong.</p>	<p>106. The Great commission Matthew 28:18-20 as the biblical and theological basis of church planting mission 107. The kingship of Jesus 108. A Christian mandate for doing church planting mission 109. The Great commission Matthew 28:18-20 as the biblical and theological basis of church planting mission 110. A Christian mandate for doing church planting mission 111. Action oriented mission 112. Soul winning 113. Reward</p>
<p>R17: 114. The great commission found in Matthew 28: 16-20, 115. speaks of following Jesus’ mandate to go and seek people to know Christ, 116. baptizing and teaching them to obey commandments. 117. I also believe on what is written in 1 Corinthians 12:8-10 118. it speaks about spiritual gifts to use. 119. So that we could be part of the church planting mission. 120. Some are gifted with wisdom, with knowledge of faith, the gifts of healing and doing miracles, gift of prophecy and more. 121. These gifts are needed to reach people and establish new churches 122. that shall spread the gospel and build communities of believers.</p>	<p>114. The Great commission Matthew 28:18-20 as the biblical and theological basis of church planting mission 115. A Christian mandate for doing church planting mission 116. Christian Education 117. 1 Corinthians 12:8-12 as biblical and theological basis for church planting mission 118. God’s provision for the mission work 119. Inclusiveness in doing God’s missional work 120. Diversity of spiritual gifts to be utilized in God’s mission 121. Emphasis on the importance of having spiritual gifts 122. Evangelism and community building</p>

R18:

123. Nung unang una akong bago pa ako mag deaconess is di ko makakalimutan yung word sakin ng DS namin, ang DS namin nun ay si Pastor Federico Valelo, sabi niya sa isang sermon niya nung bagong deaconess pa ako, christ commission is our lifetime mission sabi niya, ano ba yung commission satin ni God o ni Christ? di ba yung sa Matthew 28: 18-20

124. “go and make disciples of all nations...”

125. sabi niya, di nga sinabing sa isang lugar lang “of all nations” ibig sabihin pag of all nations wala tayong pipiliin walang pipiliing tao walang pipiliing lugar kung saan may kailangan doon.

126. So, para sakin yun yung pinakabasic, kasi nga ang ultimate na way natin of loving, worshipping, serving and glorifying him.

127. Syempre yung ano ninyong mga Kabataan “to know Christ and make him known”.

128. How we do that at paano natin siya gagawin? yun na yung isheshare natin siya at ipapaalam natin yung pagmamahal niya sa ibang tao and that is to make disciples of Jesus Christ.

123. Great commission

Matthew 28:18-20

124. Discipleship

125. Inclusive approach

126. Devotional

127. Evangelism

128. Discipleship

<p>What is your idea of integrating Wesleyan Identity (Scripture, Tradition, Experience, and Reason) in the development of church planting mission curriculum? Why?</p>	<p>Open Coding</p>	
<p>R1:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Gaya ng sinabi ko kanina yung Wesleyan spirit hindi leap eh ibig kong sabihin lumagto. 2. Halimbawa yung tradition na isang magandang tungtungan para hindi basta basta gawin ang isang bagay kasi nagbibigay ito ng inspirasyon kung ano ang tradition noon na ginawa ni John Wesley 3. Hanggang ngayon ay ito pa rin ang ginagamit natin sa pagbuo ng mga bagay bagay ito ay tinatawag na quadrilateral. 4. Yung scripture ito yung primary source kasi kailangan talaga ang scripture sa pagtanim ng simbahan. Gaya ng sabi ko ito ang primary source na batayan ng ating pananampalataya 5. at yong tradisyon 6. at yung karanasan malaking bagay yung karanasan para yung first hand kasi hindi mo hindi ka lang magsasalita ng isang bagay mas maganda yung talagang naranasan mo gaya ng mga tao sa bibliya hindi lang sila nagsasalita na nagmumula sa kinasirib nila pero nagsasalita at gumagawa sila dahil natutunan at naranasan nila mismo. Pati rin sa atin ang sabi nga nila eh experience is the best teacher. 7. Yung reason naman maganda itong reason para makapagtanong tayo diba makapagdagdag tayo ng idea makapagsalita tayo at makapagtanong tayo kung ano talaga ang nararapat sa atin. Yun talaga kung bakit may reason para Makita natin ang isang bagay at makapagbigay tayo ng ideas o makapagtanong tayo kung ano pa ang nais nating gawin na mas nararapat sa pagbuo ng isang curriculum o pagbuo ng iglesia sa nwpac 8. kaya matagal tagal na rin ito pero hanggang ngayon ang quadrilateral ng umc ay ito pa rin ang ating ginagawa sa mga bagay bagay dahil Malaki ang naitutulong at Malaki ang kanyang part sa ating buhay 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Importance of Wesleyan identity 2. Importance of tradition as basis for inspiration and planning of missional programs 3. The Wesleyan identity as framework for program planning and implementation 4. The scripture as authority and foundational basis 5. Importance of tradition as basis for inspiration and planning of missional programs 6. Experiential learning and teaching 7. Critical thinking and reflection to enhance the curriculum in church planting mission 8. Importance of Wesleyan identity 	
<p>R2:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Isubli tayo man pay ti tradisyon dagiti Umunna nga metodista. Malagip Dagiti panag- 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Importance of the Methodist tradition as model in church growth 	

expand ti Methodist ti history. Ti kasta da nga nagexpand very simple lang met.

10. Dagiti societies, dagiti bands. Dagiti classes. Daydiay movement ngay.
11. Diay lay movement ni John Wesley na trace ko ket didiay inararamid da uray di napan da idiay Amerika ket inararamid da dagidiay nagexpand diay conferences immadu.
12. Ngem idi immay ti Amerika napukaw metten dadiay ngay nga tradisyon nagbalin metten nga committees kada committees.
13. Awanen nagswek ti church planting ti Methodism inggana nga bumattit ti bumattit.
14. Isu nga masapol nga irengreng tayo ken maisubli tayo kuma ti kasla kuma nga reinventing the Methodist classes, bands, societies.
15. Gamin daytoy didiay small group nga kinokopya dagiti Pentecost Kenya tayo e. Small group classes,
16. church planting process ngay nga very practical.
17. Sapay koma ta maisubli tayo daytoy.

10. Organization and community building
11. Involvement of lay people in church planting mission
12. Organizational restructuring
13. Importance of organizing and strategic planning
14. Importance of the Methodist tradition as model in church growth
15. Importance of group ministries like small groups, covenant discipleship groups
16. Practicality of doing church planting mission
17. Importance of the Methodist tradition as model in church growth

R3:

18. Kinagpayso na daytoy nga Wesleyan identity usto nga kwa met daytoy isu met ti inadadal tayo pay dagitoy nga agtutubo. datoy ni maipanggep ti kinapateg iti bibliya bible kasuratan ken daytoy tradition, tradition ti metodista tradition ti Wesley, ken dagiti experience na, ken dagiti experience tayo.
19. Masapol nga interconnected dagitoy tapno mapapigsa tayo iti daydiay church planting program wenna church planting mission ti church.
20. Isu met ti sursoroten tayo maipanggep datoy Wesleyan identity iti panakapapigsa koma dagitoy identity tayo.
21. Masapol nga kasapulan nga kwaen tayo met ti nasantoan a kasuratan, dagiti kapadasan dagiti amamma, mailawsiw kadagiti agtutubo tatta kabataan dagiti experience da masapol nga experience ni John Wesley maisuro ken daydiay rason wenna reason no apay nga masapol nga agkasapulan tayo.
22. Uppat nga Wesleyan identity no dapat nga interconnected dagitoy tapno napinpinta napigpigsa daydiay aramiden tayo nga curriculum. Mayatak

18. Importance of the Wesleyan Identity in guiding the church practices
19. Wesleyan identity as framework for church planting mission endeavors
20. Emphasis on Wesleyan identity education among the church leaders
21. Importance of the Wesleyan Identity in guiding the church practices
22. Wesleyan identity as framework for church planting mission endeavors

ket daytoy. Saan tayo nga liplipatan dayta. Masapol ti maintegrate diay aramiden tayo nga curriculum tapno napigpigma ti pannakaaramid pannakasimpa na daytoy nga kwa. Napintas daytoy tapno adda suruten tayo, step by step ti pagmission tayo para ti panagtakder ti mission church.

R4:
23. Napakahalaga. Kasi kung tignan ninyo yung ginawa ni John Wesley pagdating sa quadrilateral kasi pininpoint niya lahat yung mga aspeto sa buhay ng tao na kailangan nating iconsider bago natin gawin yung isang bagay o bago natin iconfirm.
24. So napakahalaga po ang scripture dahil lalong lalo nay an yung pinakauna at last na basehan natin talaga pagdating sa ating Gawain.
25. At pangalawa yung tradition eh kailangan nating malaman yan kasi kung anong tradition nila ay hindi basta basta yung tradition mo ang masusunod instead of their tradition so we need to consider them. Hindi pwedeng mawala yun sa pagdevelop ng curriculum para sa church planting
26. lalong lalo na yung experience. Sabi nila experience is the best teacher so ano yung experience nila kailangan nating malaman yung dati at current experience para mas madali nating maaddress yung maibigay yung mafill- in yung kailangan nating dapat nilang mapasakanila lalo na sa misyon
27. at tsaka kung yung reason rin nating malaman kung reasonable ba tong gagawin natin o hindi.
28. So iconsider po nating yan sa akin ito yung isa sa pinakacore na kailangan nating iconsider sa paggawa ng curriculum at nakahalaga na doon natin ibabase lahat ng mga strategies natin o reasonable ba ito okay ba to sa experience sa tradition okay ba to tsaka yung scripture nandoon na iyon kaya sa akin para sa akin ay napakahalaga po na iintegrate natin lalo na sa paggawa ng curriculum at paggawa ng mga models pagdating sa church planting. Yun.

23. Importance of the Wesleyan Identity in guiding the church practices
24. The scripture as authority and foundational basis in missional work
25. Importance of the Methodist tradition as model in church growth
26. Experiential learning and teaching
27. Critical thinking and reflection
28. Wesleyan identity as framework for church planting mission endeavors

R5:
29. Hindi ko alam kung ito ay nawawala na sa mga lahat ng Pastor. Hindi lang curriculum yan, pati din sa mga sermon.
30. Sa pag sesermon natin, nakabase dun sa apat na identity po natin, upang ito ay huwag nating kalimutan ang ating tradisyon. Kasi dito po nag

29. Emphasizing the importance of utilizing the Wesleyan identity in missional work
30. Tradition as guiding principle in understanding the word of God

base ang ating pag interpret ng salita ng Diyos. Itong tradisyong ito, kailangan natin ito sa curriculum, hindi lang sa curriculum. Kahit doon po sa sermon po natin at lalo't higit sa ating panahon ngayon.

31. We need itong Wesleyan Identity na ito, lalong lalo na sa mga isyu ng gender identity niya. We need that. In our interpretation, lahat ng mga bagay, kailangan natin ito as the basic foundation sa sermon, sa interpretation,

32. at higit sa lahat, itong curriculum na ito dahil kapag sinabi nating curriculum, ay maibibigay natin sa Iglesia na ito po ang gagamitin nila sa Sunday school. At doon sa Sunday school, hindi lamang ang mga matatanda kundi itong mga bata, na mula sa mga bata na ito. Pag Maganda yung foundation ng curriculum ng church planting. Paglaki nila, talagang hindi nila iiwanan yan. Yan ang magiging prinsipyo nila at ang basehan din nila at makikita nila itong apat na identity po natin ay Maganda sa pundasyon, hindi lamang sa mga Kabataan, at lalo't higit sa mga bata na susunod sa atin.

31. the Wesleyan identity as framework in understanding the biblical and methodist doctrine

32. the importance of the curriculum utilizing the Wesleyan identity as a resource material for church ministry programs in educating and for Christian growth

R6:

33. Ibig sabihin nito, daldahin talaga natin yung Wesleyan na pananaw sa pag develop ng curriculum dala-dala niya yung pagka Wesleyan niya. Kasi pagka sinabi mong quadrilateral, Wesleyan yan.

34. Pero other church, quadrilateral din eh. Sila, halimabawa, Wesleyan Church, tanggap nila yung quadrilateral.

35. Maganda kasi yung works of spirit.

36. Doon sa Three Graces na yun, yung one grace lang pero it is expressed in three graces. Prevenient Grace, Justifying Grace at saka Sanctifying Grace. Makikita mo doon eh.

37. When you proclaim, parang sabi natin, dahil Prevenient yan di mauuna yung Espiritu Santo na magsalita doon sa tao na pag poproclaiman mo ng good news. So, the Spirit of God works in that person to prepare her or his heart to listen, to discern, and eventually to accept Jesus Christ as Lord.

38. So, importante yun na maunawaan at nag aaral sa scripture. Kasi malalaman niya, kasi sa good news kasi sa Justifying Grace kasi si Jesus

33. Emphasizing the importance of Wesleyan identity in the development of church planting curriculum

34. Inclusiveness of the Wesleyan identity

35. Spiritual empowerment

36. Profound meaning of Wesleyan identity

37. God's mission of salvation

38. The scripture as the primary basis for understanding God's grace and redeeming action

39. A faith that transforms lives

40. God's mission of salvation

41. Importance of experience

<p>namatay sa krus, nagpakasakit, namatay, nabuhay, na nalibing, na nabuhay na muli.</p> <p>39. Tapos yung sa hindi lang doon, dahil nung mananampalataya kailangan niya nang pagtransform ng kanyan sarili.</p> <p>40. So, the Spirit works pa din yun. So, makikita natin yung works of the Spirit.</p> <p>41. Then doon sa STER (Scripture, Tradition, Experience, Reason) I mean yung sabi, sa atin kasi, mahalaga yung experience sa mga Metodista. Hindi lang head knowledge, it involves the heart, the experience.</p> <p>42. Pag head knowledge kasi, reason. Pero dapat naunawaan na tama yung Scripture for your reason, at navavalidate din yan sa karanasan. So, mahalaga yun sa tingin ko</p> <p>43. dahil kung halimbawa nga, ultimately or going to plant a church, Wesleyan din ang itanim. Metodista din yung church plant mo. Yun yung nakikita ko. Tapos nga yung pinaka core ng curriculum, Wesleyan. Wesleyan yun. Kaya pati yung pananaw mo doon sa Gospel, Wesleyan din hindi sa reform, hindi sa Calvinist o kung ano pa na pananaw sa hindi Wesleyan.</p>	<p>42. The framework of the Wesleyan identity as a guide in understanding faith</p> <p>43. Emphasizing the importance of Wesleyan identity in the development of church planting curriculum</p>
<p>R7:</p> <p>44. Para kanyak, simple laeng. Na labi't nasaysayyud pannirriggan iti daytoy ket aksyon. Saan a teorya laeng.</p> <p>45. Kitaen kuma ti mangbukel iti curriculum ket adda pudno a kapadasan na iti church planting,</p> <p>46. a saan a puro teorya laeng.</p> <p>47. Kaspangarigan kuma kadakayo, no ag interview kayo iti maipanggep iti church planting, data'y adda kapadasan na nga talaga iti church planting. No ibagam kuma, damagem kuma no naimas iti ice cream. Syempre, diay nakapadas a nangan iti ice cream. Ganoon din sa church planting,</p> <p>48. tungkol sa Wesleyan Identity, yung talagang ginagawa nila ito at naiaapply nila ito, naiapply da iti biag da.</p>	<p>44. Action oriented Wesleyan identity</p> <p>45. Importance of experience in church planting mission</p> <p>46. Action oriented Wesleyan identity</p> <p>47. Importance of experience in church planting mission</p> <p>48. Praxis (action-reflection) model of Wesleyan Identity</p>
<p>R8:</p> <p>49. Haan laeng nga dayjay scripture eti pagtaktakderan tayo when it comes to church planting.</p>	<p>49. Strategic planning</p> <p>50. Contextual analysis</p> <p>51. Emphasizing the importance of Wesleyan</p>

50. We adapt the life of the people. Isang illustration lang na maaari kong gamitin ay yong four wheels yong sasakyan na may apat na gulong. Bagama't may mga sasakyan na may tatlong gulong, may dalawang gulong, may sinasabi na solar scriptura siguro iisang gulong lang yon pero at least may pag-abante but what I mean is mas stable yong apat na gulong. Ganoon din sa pagluluto gamit ng kahoy maglalagay diyan ng siguro kahit apat na bato rin tapos puwede ilagay doon yong kaldero para mas stable.

51. So, ganito rin ang sinasabi tungkol sa scripture, tradition, experience and the reason parang napi-picture natin kung

52. ano ba yong kalagayan ng sangkatauhan hindi rin lang naman tayo limitado sa isa sa mga ito.

53. While we are using one of them we cannot deny that we can experience the good news of God, we have the reason to worship, we are created in his image. So, we are created to worship God.

54. May mga bagay-bagay tayo na puwede nating stand natin, maging rason kung bakit tayo nanampalataya sa Diyos

55. nandiyan din yong sinasabi natin na tradition,

56. we have the unity of spirit.

57. Nag-iiba-iba yong pananalig ng ating Iglesya.

58. So, sa pamamagitan nito bagama't ang bibliya, ang scripture ang ating guide at nagiging praktikal ang buhay ng ating pananampalataya dahil sa mga ito when it comes to church planting again about dito sa curriculum for church planting mission, we cannot really diminished and we cannot also contain the grace of God and we sometimes, we are just wondering bakit ko nagagawa ito, dahil din ito ay naniniwala tayo na tinutulungan tayo ng Diyos.

identity as a framework in missional work

52. Using Wesleyan Identity as a lens for situational analysis

53. The Wesleyan identity as a means of grace to experience and worship God

54. Critical thinking and reflection

55. Importance of tradition

56. Spiritual empowerment

57. Diversity

58. Emphasizing the importance of Wesleyan identity in the development of church planting curriculum

R9:
59. Kanyak nga byang nu para daytoy ket napintas nga adda dayjay kuna tayo nga, maintergrate dayjay 'wesleyan identity' kasdayjay nga pag misyonan.

59. Importance of Wesleyan Identity in church planting curriculum

60. The scripture as the primary basis

61. Contextual analysis

60. Kuna tayo amin jay kasuratan, ibagbaga na ittoy isu dayjay sasao ni Apo Diyos.

61. Ngem nu mapan ka idjay, adda tay kuna tayo nga agduduma nga tradisyon.

62. Masapul nga, haan tayo nga ireject kuma. Jay tradisyon nga dinanun mo ijay, masapul nga respetuwem. Haan nga dayjay tradisyon mo nga naggapo iti baba or naggapo iti sabsabali nga lugar isu't ipakaawat mo ijay, no. Nu di ketdi, dayjay tradisyon nga dinanun mo idjay ken dayjay tradisyon mo, haan nga mabalin nga aglaban nu di ketdi iti maaramid na ijay ta dayjay, panag respeto.

63. Tapno nu, awan iti mapasamak nga, jay kuna tayo nga misunderstanding. Adu ngamin dagiti tradisyon tayo. So, para iti met experience, mabalin nga dayjay experience mo.

64. Nang nangruna kadaytoy, jay founder tayo adu ti experience na nga nangted iti motivation kadagiti tattao. Mabalin tayo met nga eintegrate kasi as your maysa nga trabahador, jay kapadasam ken jay kapadasan da, nu mapagtitipon dagitoy dakkel iti maitulong na para iti panag misyon. Kasi dayjay kapadasam, haan na napadasan. Jay kapadasam, mangngegan da. Jay kapadasan na, mangngegan da. "Ay, kasjay gayam" daytoy maysa ket namati, daytoy maysa.. ngem still nga ag gargaraw latta gayam iti kinaimbag ni Apo Diyos. Wen, isu dayjay.

65. Toy met maikatlo, daytoy kunana dito nga rason. Mabalin nga daytoy nga rason, dagitoy kuna tayon nga kapadasanen, isu daytoy iti mangtitipon nga "uy, kastoy gayam ti aramiden tayo tapno napinpintas iti bunga na."

66. Isu nga napintas nga maintegrate dagiti misyon tayo, dagiti naipatakder nga simbaan tayo, ken dagiti wesleyan identity tayo. Dayjay laeng.

62. Emphasis on the importance of the experience of others

63. Adjustment and teachability

64. Emphasis on the importance of the experience of others

65. Critical thinking and reflection

66. Importance of Wesleyan Identity in church planting curriculum

R10:

67. You know, when you say scripture tradition experience and reason it just says the theological basis or grounding of Wesleyan's or Methodist

68. is it's not simply scripture and it's not simply individualistic.

69. The tradition is strong. And traditions are more established by communities; they are heritage; they are cultural so even the experience

67. The Wesleyan identity as framework for theological understanding

68. The Wesleyan Identity as a system

69. Emphasizing the importance of experience

and reason they are not simply individual experience, they can be a community experience.

70. And even the reason is the wisdom of the ages. You know, that comes along with it and speaks of future social change.

71. So, the church planting curriculum is important to have these in mind because it should be with the times. You know, dapat na napanahon.

72. Pangalawa, the approaches would be in accord with; like for example are this millennials, and this Generation Z. So, the curriculum should integrate the kind of experience that people are experiencing now. So that, the approach will be relevant and the curriculum itself will be appealing.

70. Emphasizing the importance of reason as an agent of transformation

71. The importance of Wesleyan Identity as the framework of the church planting curriculum

72. Contextual, situational, and relevant

R11:

73. Una, scripture basis tayo kung walang scripture hindi mabubuo ang tradisyon experience at reason. Sa scripture nagsisimula ang lahat,

74. kung ang rason natin ay walang kaugnayan sa bibliya ito ay questionable. Sa bibliya ginagamit natin ang bibliya para sa kagustuhan, minsan ginagamit actually natin yung bibliya para lang sa kagustuhan natin naghahanap tayo ng mga verses na sumasang ayon sa atin minsan kinakalimutan natin yung scripture gusto natin lang yung reason only para ang nangyayari ay inililinyahan natin ang kagustuhan natin doon sa bibliya hindi yung salita ng Diyos ay dapat siya yung magtuwid sa atin, kaya unang una scripture basis tayo,

75. tama may kanya kanya naman tayong karanasan at dito napapatunayan na kumikilos ang Diyos sa bawat isa, upang maramdaman natin na siya ang personal na Diyos, hindi lamang Diyos nang iilan o pangkaramihan pero personal na Diyos.

76. Mas pinagtibay pa kasi natin ito sa pamamagitan ng pagtotoo ng sinaunang believers, ito na yung pumapasok yung tradisyon pero gaya ni John Wesley, ang karanasan ni John Wesley ay kung tutuusin base rin yan doon sa bibliya. Minsan nahahambing ang karanasan nila sa

73. The scripture as the foundation

74. The importance of the scripture as the primary source

75. Experiencing God in a personal basis

76. Experiential teaching and learning

karanasan natin sa ngayon, dito natin makikita na ang Diyos noon ay siya rin ang Diyos sa ngayon.

R12:

77. Ti pannaka-itipon ti Wesleyan identity ket maysa a napateg nga e-konsider agsipod ta kas paset a desinyo ti curriculum dagitoy ti agbalin nga pundasyon wenno basehan kas agbalin a curriculum materials wenno resouces tayo.

77. The importance of integrating Wesleyan Identity into the church planting curriculum as a resource material for church planting mission endeavors

R13:

78. Simple lang naman kasi ang pagbuo ng iglesia,
79. hindi naman tayo talaga ang bubuo ng iglesia ang panginoon at Diyos, siya talaga ang dahilan,
80. nagkakaroon lang tayo ng idea na ganun kasi binibigay ng diyos sa puso natin and nagpapatayo tayo ng iglesia,
81. pero sa mga doktrina ng metodista ganun na, Wesleyan heritage, tradition, reason, pero medyo mataas na masyado yan,
82. pero sa pagtanim ng iglesia siguro ay simple lang, hindi mo kailangan ng matataas,
83. pag lumalalim ka siguro sa pananampalataya ganyan.
84. what is reason what is an experience tradition and scriptures ganun lang naman siguro.
85. Yun lang ang sa akin, simple lang you just preach the gospel,
86. train your members and if they ask you will answer questions.

78. Emphasis on practicality and simplicity
79. Understanding God's missional work
80. Calling to do mission with God
81. Education on Wesleyan Identity
82. Emphasis on practicality and simplicity
83. Christian education
84. Education on Wesleyan Identity
85. Evangelism
86. Discipleship

R14:

87. Ito yong kagandahan natin bilang Metodista at bilang naniniwala sa katuruan ng ating founder na si John Wesly tunay nga po na isang magandang ibinibigay na kagandahan ng pagbubuo ng ating curriculum yong batayan na mayroon tayong scripture, mayroon tayong tradition, mayroon tayong experience at mayroon tayong reason.
88. Ito po yong parang bumabalot, bumubuo saan nakabatay yong ating paninindigan sa ating pananampalataya na naaayon kung ano yong karanasan natin,
89. kung ano yong kultura natin. Kasi ang kultura, ito'y isang bagay na nakakatulong kung saan tayo
90. lalago at yong paano natin e-reason-out yong ating mga bagay-bagay na ating naiintindihan o nauunawaan bilang Kristiyano.

87. Emphasizing the importance of Wesleyan identity as a framework in missional work
88. The Wesleyan identity as a guide in understanding faith through experience
89. Wesleyan identity as a lens contextual analysis
90. Critical thinking and reflection
91. Emphasizing the importance of Wesleyan identity as a framework in missional work

91. Ang kagandahan dito sa pagbuo ng curriculum, Ito kasi yong nakikita ko na identity ng Methodist yong mayroon tayong quadrilateral na scripture, tradition, and experience and reason.

92. Dahil sabi ko nga parang ito yong buod ng ating batayan ng ating paglago ng ating pananampalataya bilang tagasunod ng ating panginoong Hesus at isang follower ng ating simbahan. Yon lang po ang aking nakikita na para dito sa Wesleyan identity.

R15:

93. Actually ito pong sa Wesleyan quadrilateral na ito, pag pinagsama sama po natin kasama yung mga karanasan natin at kadahilanan, sa tingin ko okay naman siya kasi dun po talaga tayo madalas na nagbabase, maliban po sa ating banal na kasulatan so ang kagandahan po kasi nito ay parang sa Wesleyan quadrilateral yan po dahil may pinagbabasehan din po tayo katulad ni John Wesley, 94. so nakita po natin kung pano siya namuhay, kaya po tayo sigurong mga methodist ay napaka generous kasi ang isa po sa mga naging tumatak sakin is kung papaano si John Wesley po is napakamatulungin at kahit po walang matira sa kanya tapos at kung gaano niya iniisip po yung mga tao na nahirapan sa labas

95. yung parang ang nakikita ko po na talagang tumatatak sakin is yung ang pagiging methodist natin at dito po sa mga banal na kasulatan, tradisyon, karanasan at dahilan. Dito po kasi natutunan ko na hindi naman po talaga magparami. Ang ating mission ay kundi makatulong po sa community which is yun po yung talaga sinusundan at nakasulat din po yun sa banal nakasulatan at nararanasan ko po yun kasi ako po personally hindi po importante kasi kung anong posisyon mo, yun yung tinitingnan ko dahil ang Wesleyan quadrilateral ay gusto niya magserve tayo sa community sa labas ganun din yung sinasabi ng banal na kasulatan, gusto ng panginoon. So bilang tao po bilang miyembro po ganun din po yung gusto kong gawin so yun po yung pinagbabasehan ko.

R16:

96. Iyon ang medyo hindi ko ano... pero, ang nakikita ko jaan pastor. From the word 'Methodist' kasi, diba dahil sa word na 'method'. Siguro, nakita

92. The Wesleyan identity as a guide in understanding faith through experience

93. Emphasizing the importance of Wesleyan identity as a framework in missional work

94. Learning from tradition and experience of others

95. Emphasizing the importance of Wesleyan identity as a framework in missional work

96. The Wesleyan Identity as a system

97. Emphasizing the importance of Wesleyan

<p>nila na ‘yon nga, sa wesleyan identity. Mayro’n na siyang method kung paano gawin ito.</p> <p>97. So, isa nga ‘yong apat na binanggit mo, pastor. Pero ang pinaka importante saakin ay ‘yon nga, nakita naman nila na... although, hindi tayo ‘yong malaking religious sector pero tignan mo, isa tayo sa may pinaka magandang reputasyon na religious sector. So, ‘yon siguro, pastor ang nakikita ko doon. Tsaka sabi ko nga, from the word ‘methodist’ parang kilala lang na ‘yong methodology. In preaching or pag mmission ay napaka laking bagay nun para maging successful ‘yong church planting. Ayun lang po, medyo maliit lang ‘yong alam ko po roon. Minsan hindi ko rin alam kung totoo ba o kung tama pa ba ‘yong sinasabi ko tungkol doon sa ano na ‘yon, pastor.</p>	<p>identity as a framework in missional work</p>
<p>R17:</p> <p>98. I strongly believe that we need to uphold the Holy Scripture as the sole and primary source of God’s revelation to us. So hindi natin siya puwedeng isantabi.</p> <p>99. And the Tradition, Experience and Reason are also integral in developing a curriculum because they have something to do with our Christian faith and maturity.</p>	<p>98. The importance of the scripture as the primary source</p> <p>99. The Wesleyan identity as a guide in understanding faith and Christian growth</p>
<p>R18:</p> <p>100. I think kasi yung Wesleyan identity natin ay very biblical,</p> <p>101. wholesome</p> <p>102. at tsaka consistent siya</p> <p>103. hindi siya nagbabago kahit na nagbabago yung panahon pag pinag aaralan nga yan sa sa panahon natin ngayon pag nagtuturo ako ng confirmation class sa mga bata hindi mo siya ngay puwedeng baguhin,</p> <p>104. nananatili siyang matatag at patuloy na nangungusap sa kahit na anong uri ng panahon at sa kahit na anong generation so yung pinakabasic na pagkakilanlan sating mga metodista</p> <p>105. at kung ito naintegrate na siya sa kurikulum na na mabubuo sa church planting, bilang worker hindi lang ako magrereview, yung mga tao ding halimbawa meron ng pag aaral sa ganun at ituturo sa mga tao. From the start, parang naka ugat na sila parang sa halaman, para sa pagdating ng panahon hindi lang pang 12 years old na tayo na pag aaralan</p>	<p>100. Scripture based</p> <p>101. Beneficial</p> <p>102. Consistent</p> <p>103. Time proven effectiveness</p> <p>104. Teachability of Wesleyan identity framework</p> <p>105. The Wesleyan identity as a guide in understanding faith and Christian growth</p>

natin siya kung baga agad agad na iintegrate na sa kanila o naiintroduce na sa kanila kung ano yung church meron tayo, so para sa akin napaka importante na kasama siya sa gagawin niyong kurikulum

What do you think are the practical ways including methods and strategies, in implementing a church planting mission curriculum in NWPAC? Why?	Open Coding
<p>R1</p> <p>1. Siguro para sa akin ay kailangan ang visitation kasi kung walang visitation hindi natin malalaman kung ano talaga ang kailangan nila.</p> <p>2. Pangalawa hindi lang visitation kailangan din natin maging practical o gagawa ng mga iba't ibang mga bagay yung gagawa tayo ng medical mission di ba? Gift giving at iba iba pang paraan</p> <p>3. na naayon sa pangangailangan ng mga tao. Kailangan ito kasi sa mga karanasan natin sa pageevangelize, hindi lang tayo nageevengelize kailangan rin nating tumulong kung ano ang kailangan nila.</p> <p>4. Siguro sa akin ah. Baka makakatulong din yon pagbigay ng mga pangangailangan nila sa buhay.</p> <p>5. Kasi naalala konmg nung meeting meeting nung nakaraan mayroon yung ganito ang ginagawa naming ay pupunta sa isang lugar magbisita tapos gumawa din ng sportsfest tapos kung may funding gagawa ng medical mission gift giving at iba pa na makakatulong sa kanila.</p> <p>6. Paano natin magagamit ang curriculum na nagawa natin siguro part din yon ng curriculum para siguro mas effective pa kasi kung nabuo na natin ang curriculum eh alam na natin ang kagamitan o maitutulong</p> <p>7. magagamit sa konteksto o sitwasyon ng isang lugar o isang iglesia. Yun.</p>	<p>1. Importance of conducting visitation</p> <p>2. Social ministry programs</p> <p>3. Need determination</p> <p>4. Addressing the needs of the community</p> <p>5. Social ministry programs</p> <p>6. Integrating different ministry programs in the development of church planting curriculum</p> <p>7. Contextual and situational analysis</p>
<p>R2:</p> <p>8. Dayta ti kunakon mayat nga mangopya tayo kopyaen tayo ni John Wesley didiay bands, societies, classes, holy club values dagidiayen.</p> <p>9. Mayat met nga mangopya tayo ti dadduma bro. agkopya tayo dagiti agbalballigi.</p> <p>10. Nagrigat met gamin nu maminsan nga kunatayo diay lang tradisyon tayo nga Methodist</p> <p>11. ngem nu minsan dagidiay nangopya ti Methodist rumangrangay da met apay nga haan tayo nga kopyaen dagitoy.</p> <p>12. Nasayaat met ti kumopya no i-contextualized tayo latta.</p> <p>13. No kopyaen tayo kasla koma ditoy ccf apay nga rumangrangay da? Apay dagitoy victory? Apay</p>	<p>8. Adapt proven methods and strategies</p> <p>9. Resourcefulness</p> <p>10. Inclusion of external methods and strategies</p> <p>11. Contextualization</p> <p>12. Inclusion of small group ministries like covenant discipleship group</p> <p>13. Adapt proven methods and strategies</p> <p>14. Small Group Ministries</p> <p>15. Lay involvement</p> <p>16. Recruitment and manpower</p>

dagitoy Pentecostal churches? Ket talaga met nga rumangrangay da gapu ta tinulad da met ti tradisyon ti Methodist nga talaga.

14. Small group,
15. lay movement ti sekreto da eh isu nga sikreto ni John Wesley idi.
16. Tatta ket matay ni pastor ta isu met ti aglelead ti bs, isuna aglelead ti cellgroup, matay ton,
17. isu nga dapat sukatan tayo nga developen dagitoy layko tapno isudan ti aglead. Datayon a ti agtrain.
18. Isu ti kungkuna ti ephesians 4:11 nga isu ngarud nga ada pastor, evangelist, teachers ta itrain yo dagiti layko tapno isuda agaramid.
19. Isunga kopyaen tayo dagiti kinopya da Kenya tayo.

17. Training and discipleship
18. diversity of responsibilities
19. Adapt proven methods and strategies

R3:

20. Siguro ti panangkitak ti daytoy haan nga basta i kwa tayo adda point person wenno committee. Dapat ada maibukel nga committee
21. kasla koma tutukan ti point person nga mangipagna daytoy.
22. Daytoy ti problema ti naobserve ko no adda program nga ikwa ti church tayo, no awan to point person wenno committee nga mangitrabaho haan da nga agprosper.
23. Masapol nga adda organize.
24. Masapol nga organisado.
25. Isu nga no maapuan daytoy nga curriculum maibaba iti distrito dapat adda committee nga mantutok ti dayoy.
26. Nu kunatayo nga didiay church planting committee papigsain ti church planting committee. Tapos bumaba ti local church adda met support ditoy local church.
27. Diay point person wenno committee isuda ti maorient nu kasanno ti aramiden da. Maysa pay nga masapol ti piloting. I-pilot mo diay target nga padakkelen nga local church wenno i-organize nga local church
28. tapno isu ti papanan amin ti resources pay resources ti distrito. Tapno haan nga pagmamaysa nga no local church ti nagimplement ti maysa nga local churchen ket awanen narigaten no awan ti support.

20. Organization structure
21. Task delegation
22. Importance of manpower
23. Organization structure
24. Systematic planning
25. Organization structure
26. Support system
27. Training
28. Support system
29. Implementation and evaluation
30. Strategic planning

29. Amin kuma nga no adda didiay piloting nga maaramid wenna laboratory testing kunada met no dadduma ket laboratory coop.

30. Isu nga masapol nga adda daydiayen identifieden diay koman dagiti resources nga aggapo iti local churches tapno makabuo ti maysa nga mission church.

R4:

31. Yung mga practical ways and strategies meron na tayo niyan so ang tanong niyan ay ito ba naayon sa kanila.

32. So we have so many practical... sa akin kailangan nating gumawa ng sarili nating model we need to make our own model strategies para kasi tayo ang nakakaalam kung sino tayo sa NWPAC.

33. Ako meron na akong ginagamit dati pagdating sa mission models. Una ginagamit ko yung ways ng mga sundalo pag sila'y pumupunta sa misyon. So triny ko kaya nga yung SMEAC yung ginagamit nila sa military.

34. Yung S yung situation kaya nga bago sila pumunta sa isang bundok o sa kalaban kailangan nilang pagaralan yung buo.

35. Saan ba yung daanan nila kaya safe sila safety first and then magiging ang number one maging successful yung mission. Ang tanging puhunan doon ay yung situationer.

36. Then yung pangalawa ay yung mission kailangan maliwanag. Ano bang mission natin sa church planting? Basta nalang ba tayong magtatanim? Kailangan maliwanag sa atin yung misyon natin para kahit anong mangyari hindi tayo mawawala kasi sa puso natin alam nating yung misyon eh

37. and then makwan din natin yung letter E yung execution kailangan nating mapagaralan kung paano natin eexecute ito after learning the situation hearing what the whole mission

38. and then yung execution paano natin gagawin according to our capacity and then yung capacity ng pupuntahan natin

39. and then kailangan din nating iconsider yung letter A administration. O alam na natin kung paano iexecute ngayon hindi sapat na alam lang natin paano natin i-administer ngayon so after doing all the ways na how to administer

31. Contextual strategies

32. Contextual church planting curriculum

33. Inclusion of external methods and strategies

34. Situational analysis

35. Area survey

36. Clarity of vision, mission, and goals

37. Execution and implementation strategies

38. Strategic planning

39. Organizational planning and structure

40. Execution and implementation

41. Inclusion of external methods and strategies

<p>40. and then doon nalang sa kwan natin yung letter C nagaantay nalang ng command OK.</p> <p>41. Okay na kasi naihanda na natin ang lahat. Yun yung isa sa mga models na napagaralan ko na narinig ko rin sa isang kaibigan para sa pag... epektibong strategies and models kasi maicoconsider lahat. Yun ho.</p>	
<p>R5:</p> <p>42. Masapol ti involvement dagiti Lay, Agtutuboken Ubbing for these strategies. Kasi pag ininvolve sila dun sa pag gawa ng curriculum po natin, ano man ang mga bagay na makikita natin yung needs kung papaano yung mga strategy kasi hindi lang tayo nakatuon sa isang audience, pero multi-audience.</p> <p>43. Para sa akin, ito yung kailangan po natin, involvement. Masapol ti involvement dagiti Lay, Young People, even those Children,</p> <p>44. kailangan natin mapakinggan ang din kanilang perspective.</p>	<p>42. Lay involvement and participation</p> <p>43. Manpower recruitment</p> <p>44. Lay people initiative</p>
<p>R6:</p> <p>45. Practical ways. Kasi kung titignan mo ang NWPAC, mayroong rural areas, mayroon ding urbanize areas o mayroon ding rural siya pero going to urbanization, meron ganun.</p> <p>46. Magkakaiba yung mga approaches din siguro dito practical ways na halimbawa, City. Candon, Urdaneta, San Fernando, Baguio City, Laoag, Vigan. Kung titignan mo halimbawa, saan mo dadalhin yung church planting initiative? Kung sa City yan, o pwede rin yung approach na pupuntahan ng bahay-bahay o pupwede rin yung, meron kasing growing development yung sa mga communities, subdivisions ganyan. Kailangan nila ng community din ng mga iyon,</p> <p>47. baka pupwedeng tignan, tignan sila na potential na venue ng church planting.</p> <p>48. Magkakaiba yung practical ways niyan. May naikwento nga ako sayo kanina na, yung nakaranasan ng ibang fellowship na naging church. Yung pumupunta sa mga businesses. Yung kinakausap yung mga business establishment na magstart ng devotion and prayer sa mga empleyado.</p> <p>49. Actually, doon lang yung pinanggalingan ng kanilang mga church members doon. Kasi</p>	<p>45. Contextual and situational analysis. Difference of rural and urban areas.</p> <p>46. Strategic planning depending on the area of focus</p> <p>47. Conduct area surveys for possible location of church planting mission</p> <p>48. Strategic planning depending on the area of focus</p> <p>49. Contextual and situational analysis. Difference of rural and urban areas.</p> <p>50. Strategic planning depending on the area of focus</p> <p>51. Familiarization</p> <p>52. Information gathering</p> <p>53. Importance of the tribe or family elder in establishing church planting mission</p>

mayroong nag dedesire to grow in the faith, di take the initiative na sila na yun, yung core ng ano nila ng pagpunta. Yun yung magiging initial na church members nila.

50. At naging effective yan kasi sa Metro Manila din, di ko lang masabi o mabanggit kung anong eksakto na fellowship kung ano yan pero, mayroon kasing nakasama sa mga worship conference na dinaluhan namin, ganun daw yung karanasan. Hindi sila nag start muna ng church, nasa parang parking lot lang ng isang establishment, ipinahiram, Pag Sunday, close. Ginagamit nila yun. Doon sila nag gagather hanggang lumaki sila. They are able now to rent a modest place nag ano na sila ng hall, ganyan. Pero nag start sila ng ganun sa church planting nila. Kung ano, eskwelahan ang pinupuntahan nila. Di ko alam din kung sa rural.

51. Sa karanasan ko naman, pumunta ako sa Bario, yung kwento ko nga sa Natividad sa Bachelor, nag start talaga na hinanap talaga yung mga Metodista.

52. Hindi sila nadadala sa simabahan at mahalaga rin siguro sa karanasan ko yung malaman kung sino yung head ng family.

53. Ang pinakamatanda sa family na kinikilala sa Bario, sa Rural. Malakas pa rin iyon, yung leadership ng pinakamatanda doon sa clan. Malakas ang hatak pag siya ang nagtawag nun, darating sila. So, mayroon kang captive audience din pagka bible study.

54. So, yung karanasan ko din yung iba-barangay profile mo o community profile. That was long ago, it was long ago. Sa Church of Nazarene, nag attend ako ng kanilang church planting project ng training. Isa yun yung ano nila, tignan mo yung, ipoprofile mo yung barangay, ibig sabihin nun halimbawa ipoprofile mo,

55. alamin mo yung, ano yung religious isolation nung mga tao, ano yung mga trabaho ng mga tao, largely yung mga magsasaka ba iyan o empleyado rin karamihan. Saan yung workplace nila, ano yung churches na andoon. Pero sa kanila kasi, training namin noon, kung walang church, mas Maganda. Wala kang kakompetensya. Tapos yung

54. Area profiling
55. Information gathering
56. Area profiling
57. Importance of courtesy call to the leaders of the area
58. Approach households by knocking and looking for those who will accept bible studies, devotions, and prayer ministries
59. Adapt proven methods and strategies from other denomination
60. Skill in approaching unfamiliar territories
61. Evangelism

paano idedetermine yung receptivity ng tao sa Gospel o sa scripture.

56. Sabi nila, doon sa training ko with the Nazarene noon, kapagka nandiyan daw yung mga kulto, binilang nila mga kulto, jackseneo ganyan, pag andoon daw yun receptive kasi kahit nga kulto tinatanggap eh, mas yun pa kaya yung pure Gospel yung ano mo, yun yung sabi nila noon doon sa training namin. So, practical yun yung malaman mo yung nature nung lugar. Sino yung mga leader, syempre. Mga leader yan, hanapin mo ganyan,tapos doon ka mag start.

57. Kung sa praktikalidad, kung papaano mo uumpisahan. Syempre yung pagpunta mo sa kung mag poprofile ka sa Bario, magpaalam sa leaders ng mga Barangay.

58. Na kwento ko kanina kung paano nag start yung mga mission sa manila nung nasa seminaryo pa kami, dati kasi walang Methodist sa mga probinsya ng Laguna, Rizal, Cavite. Yung ginawa yung katok. Kakatok sa mga bahay, kung tatanggapin ka, mag dedevotion ka hanggang dito mag develop ka ng bible studies mo, yung ituturo mo.

59. Hindi ko lang alam kung anong curriculum na ginamit yan basta ganun ang systema.

60. Pag bahay-bahay, kakatok. Kung sinong tatanggap, uumpisahan nila doon. Basic na faith sharing about kay Jesus Christ.

61. Yung sa Nazarene naman, ang pinag aaralan naming doon, meron silang neighborhood evangelistic bible study. Hindi ko alam, kung ilan bang lesson yun, mga walo yata. Di ko na matandaan pero, baka pwede pa nating ma retrieve yung mga materials nila doon, matanong sa mga Pastor na kaibigan.

R7:

62. No mabukel iti curriculum, maaddaan iti seminar iti Annual Conference session tapno maibingay kadagiti delegado iti dagitoy nga kapanunutan,

63. tapno mabukel iti istrategya iti church planting.

64. Maspol a maibingay met laeng daytoy kadagiti delegado.

62. Information dissemination about the church planting curriculum

63. Involvement of lay and other church workers on strategic planning

64. Information dissemination about the church planting curriculum

R8:

65. Sa NWPAC maraming nababalitaan na churches na yong programa para sa Iglesia na parang nasasayang.

66. So, we can learn from our experiences for us to strategize better for the next church planting.

67. Dahil nga one of the experiences nariyan nga yong mga tao,

68. nariyan din yong programa,

69. kaya kung minsan nawala na yong programa parang nawawala na rin yong tao.

70. Kasi may karanasan din tayo na we partnered with the Korean Brothers sa pag-mi-mission at ang mga korean brothers ay masigasig sila.

71. Magpapatayo agad ng church dahil nakikita nila na may community sa isang lugar sinasabayan nila ng freebies pang-hikayat.

72. Yon nga lang may ano ito parang ito ay strategy doon sa Korea na parang hindi rin maganda ang impact dito sa atin. So, yong nagiging resulta non kung wala na yong freebies mga goodies na lumalabas na parang yon yong ina-after-an ng tao hindi na yong ano sana presence ng pananampalataya.

73. So, nariyan na yong church structure napakaganda yon nga lang uunti na yong mga kaluluwa na naroroon dahil ina-after-an lumalabas ay yong physical yong tangible things nawawala na yong spirituwal ano sana benefits from the spiritual sides

74. so again practically magkakaroon ng parang pag-aaral muna sa community.

75. We can conduct visitations, bible studies before putting up the church.

65. Full utilization of the church planting curriculum

66. Experiential learning and studying

67. Availability of manpower

68. Availability of the program

69. Organizational structuring

70. Support from external sources

71. Inclusion of external methods and strategies from other organization

72. Contextualization

73. Strategic planning

74. Contextual and situational analysis

75. Conducting ministerial activities like visitations and bible studies

R9:

76. Practically speaking kuna tayo, daytoy dayjay kuna tayo nga action nu maaramid tu daytoy nga korrikulum. Haan laeng nga agpatingga kuma nga nalpas nga naiprint, printed nga materials. Nu di ket daytoy kuma, adda dayjay for example, one district. Adda dayjay maiprograma kadagiti distrito

77. nga maiyadal, maiyadal daytoy.

78. Kasi, uray nag pintas dayjay material nga kuna tayo nu madi tayo met nga usaren, useless. Awan iti na isu nga dayjay kayat ko nga maaramid to daytoy nga korrikulum. Adda daytay kuna tayo

76. Implementation and utilization of the church planting curriculum

77. Trainings and lectures about the church planting curriculum

78. Implementation and utilization of the church planting curriculum

79. Information dissemination regarding the church planting curriculum

nga pannaka implementar babaen kadagiti panangi lecture, seminar, kadagitay maseknan lalong lalo na kadagiti umuna siguro, pastor.

79. Umuna siguro nga pannaka implementaran na daytoy. And then, bumaba. Kasi naadal ti bodies ti NWPAC daytoyen, dagiti kuna tayo nga leaders tayo.

80. And then, mang create iti seminar para kadagiti miyembro.

81. Daytoy ti makitkitak nga wagas tapno napintas met laeng nga maimplementar. Ta uray nu napintas, nu haan nga naadal ken haan nga naiyadal baka sabalin tu iti tur-turungenna.

82. Isu masapul nga paipakaawat nga umuna kadagiti maseknan nang nangruna kadagiti pastor.

80. Trainings and lectures about the church planting curriculum

81. Implementation and utilization of the church planting curriculum

82. Trainings and lectures about the church planting curriculum

R10:

83. Well, because you are establishing communities, I think it will be best if it will be done by teams.

84. You know, so that the effect will be more appealing and communal

85. and the strategy should involve in this day and age

86. what are these materials to use like for example; our point things like the graphics and maybe the question should be more of choices.

87. And also, that it should be more interactive

88. and they should elicit practical responses from the recipients

89. and that also it should be collegial they are not look upon as non-Christian or unchurched people it simply as persons.

83. Organization structuring

84. Recruitment of manpower

85. Strategic planning

86. Contextual and situational analysis

87. Engaging and experiential

88. Critical thinking and reflection

89. Inclusivity and openness

R11:

90. Base sa sinaunang mananampalataya sa bibliya ang pinaka epektibo ay ang making friends

91. and offering bible studies or home cell groups ito ay nasa book of Acts. Ang isa sa strategies natin ngayon ay house to house visitation and offering prayers

92. and if we have food to share, we will do it but not necessarily,

93. pagkatapos makikipagkilala ulit tayo yun ang procedure. Anong procedure natin? syempre ilalapit natin yung loob natin sa kanila; hanggang sa makuha natin yung loob nila hindi natin

90. Establishing presence by building relationships

91. Conducting ministerial activities like visitations, bible studies, and prayers

92. Addressing the needs

93. Establishing presence by building relationships

94. Conducting ministerial activities like visitations, bible studies, and prayers

95. Establishing presence by building relationships

ipagsisiksikan kung ano ang gusto natin dapatmakipagkaibigan at hindi lamang po yun
94. pagkatapos nun ay yayain natin sila na ipanalangin,
95. yun ay napakagandang way ng pagplant ng church hindi lang literal napagplant ng church kundi pagplant ng church doon sa puso nila.

R12:
96. Maysa a maipagarop a praktikal a wagas kas kapaliwan a pamay-an ken estratehiya ti pannakaipatungpal ti curriculum ket isu kuma ti pannakabukel ti kunkuna tayo a maysa a grupo babaen ti panangiwawan ken pannangipatungpal ti district committee on evangelism ken local churches
97. a makabael a mangipaay ti suporta
98. kas kuma ti human and
99. financial resources
100. ken kitaen da met kas pilyen da dagiti makita a saan lang a dagiti makabael
101. ngem dagiti adda palasingsingan na calling na eti kastoy a panag-ministryuan.

R13:
102. Ang pamamaraan naman ng pagtanim ng iglesia, you will not do a work by yourself alone, so you need your Lay na kasama sama mo
103. at itre-train.
104. Habang nag pre-preach ka sinasabayan mo din ng buhay
105. hindi ka umaalis sa trabaho mong yan, mahirap talaga ang pagtanim, pioneering ang tawag dyan,
106. wala kang support kung meron man blessings lang, kailangan mo talaga ng persistence at patience,
107. kailangan mo talaga ng mag-sipag, yun talaga ang pangangailangan
108. para sa ganun ay makapagtanim tayo ng iglesia at itrain mo yung mga kasama mo
109. bagamat kailangan ng budget talagang sakripisyo talaga, sasakripisyo pagpunta mo na lang dun kailangan mo ng gasoline isakripisyo talaga yun meron man o wala talagang pupunta ka kasi nga yung burden mo na maipatayo ang iglesia ng ating panginoong Diyos.

96. Organizational structuring
97. Establishment of support system
98. Manpower
99. Addressing financial needs on church planting mission programs
100. Training and lecture on church planting curriculum
101. Manpower recruitment

102. Lay involvement in church planting mission
103. Training and lecture on church planting
104. Practice and initiation
105. Training and lecture on church planting
106. Establishment of support system
107. Recruitment of committed manpower
108. Lay involvement in church planting mission
109. Training and lecture on church planting
110. Time management
111. Recruitment of committed manpower

110. Yun ang mga alam kong estratehiya, kung nakaschedule na pupunta ka dun wag mong bibigyan ng iba pang activity kung hindi ka man makapunta dun dahil may sakit ka ganun, pero kung sa mga okasyon lang ay hindi naman, mas importante pa rin yung trabaho ng panginoon.

111. Yun ang mga estratehiya at doon naman nagpapatunay na nararamdaman yung mga tao na seryoso ang trabaho natin pati din ang ating panginoon ay nakikita niya ang ating sacrifices tinutulungan niya tayo.

R14:

112. Siguro, ang makikita natin bago tayo pupunta sa isang lugar para maka-buo tayo ng magandang curriculum siguro titignan natin yong pangangailangan,

113. siguro kailangan diyan ng survey or feasibility study kung ano yong venue na yan para alam natin kung ano yong nararapat na para kumbaga ang alam natin ito na yong tama pero hindi mo puwede pa lang biglain

114. kundi ito ba yong kumbaga yong immersion kailangan ng

115. immersion hanggang sa unti-unting nakukuha mo na yong pangangailangan nila.

116. Ah ito pala, kasi hindi naman isang iglap lang na pagtingin mo ay yon na yon, di ba? Iba kasi talaga yong naririnig mo kasi bukal sa kanilang puso yong talagang kung ikaw ay immerse mo sa lugar na yon.

117. Diba kung sa mga every summer ng mga seminarian na mayroon silang parang summer (summer immersion). Yon yong nakikita kong puwedeng gawin dito sa tanong na to. Yong kailangan siguro we let a feasibility study, we let also a survey

118. or emerge natin para makasalamuha natin sila makita natin

119. mas lalo doon natin makikita yong pangangailangan nila.

120. Edi-siyempre pag nakuha na natin yon, baka yong paggawa natin ng curriculum baka mas lalo pa nating madagdagan ma-enhance, na parang ah ito mayroon pang kailangang idagdag.

112. Need determination

113. Conduct area survey and information gathering

114. Familiarization, Contextual and situational analysis

115. Addressing the needs

116. Establishing presence by building relationships

117. Conduct area survey and information gathering

118. Establishing presence by building relationships

119. Need determination

120. Familiarization, Contextual and situational analysis

R15:

121. Sa tingin ko ang magiging sagot ko lang dito kung papano siya magiging effective dapat kung makakabuo tayo ng kurikulum napakaimportante na tayo mismong gumawa ng kurikulum na yun
122. at alam nating sundin, napakasimple lang kunwari po sa local church meron po sinasabi diyan na sasabihin nila rules yung isang leader sabi niya ito yung rule sa ganyan pero nababalewala po kasi yung rules na yun pag ikaw mismong leader hindi mo kinikilala yun at hindi mo siya sinusunod so napakaimportante po na kapag gumawa po tayo ng kurikulum at alam natin yung ginawa nating kurikulum na yun at sinusunod natin yun kasi para maging effective po tayo sa pagtanim ng simbahan kasi useless po na magkakaroon tayo ng kurikulum kung hindi po natin kakilala yung kurikulum na yun hindi po natin siya susundin hindi po tayo magiging effective
123. kasi parang yun po kasi yung susundin ng mga members
124. yung magiging church po doon.

121. Church planting curriculum in the context of NWPAC
122. Training and lecture on church planting curriculum
123. The curriculum as a guide
124. The curriculum as framework

R16:

125. Sa mga nababasa ko lang po, pastor. Kung ano 'yong mga practical ways tsaka strategies. Ang pinaka importante saakin, pastor ay 'yong pagdadasal.
126. Kailangan kasi na ano... diba, sa pagdadasal ay alam nating tinutulungan tayo ng ating Panginoon, nanjaan palagi ang Diyos, at sa pagdadasal na 'yong alam nating iguguide niya tayo kung anong dapat nating gawin. So, ayun ang pinaka una. Sabi niya sa mga napag aralan ko rin.
127. Pangalawa, kailangan doon sa lugar kung saan ka mag church planting, kailangan mo ring isurvey 'yong area. Isurvey mo kung strategic ba 'yong lugar para sa gagawin mong church planting. Bakit mo kailangang isurvey,
128. para makita mo roon kung marami pa bang dapat talagang mahikayat doon sa lugar na 'yon.
129. Kung minsan nga kasi, nakikita ko kapag sinurvey mo 'yong area at marami nang nakatayo doon na mga religious sector, parang napaka hirap mo nang kumbinsihin sila para umanib saatin. So, 'yon ang importante na isurvey mo 'yong area at nakita mong iyon ay medyo may mga relihiyon sila

125. Spiritual empowerment through prayer
126. Faith – building curriculum
127. Conduct area survey and information gathering
128. recruitment
129. Conduct area survey and information gathering
130. Recruitment
131. Conduct area survey and information gathering
132. Establishing Presence
133. organization structuring
134. Discipleship
135. training and lectures on church planting mission
136. discipleship
137. Establishing presence by building relationships
138. Social ministries

pero hindi naman sila church goer talaga. Siguro, mas maganda 'yong lugar kung doon ka magkakaroon ng church planting program.

130. Pangalawa, sabi niya... puwede ring mag build ka at mag prepare ka ng grupo. Parang, iprepare mo rin. Hindi ka muna pupunta kaagad, kailangan mong may grupo ka.

131. Na kailangang matuto silang lahat kasi pag punta mo doon sa gagawin na 'yon, 'yong team mo ay alam na nila ang gagawin ng bawa't isa. Kasi 'yon ang pinaka importante roon, pastor. Hindi po ba? Parang nagsisimba rin tayo na may naprepreach, may mag bible study, gano'n po ba? Mayro'n ding mga usherette roon sa lugar na mag guguide rin doon sa tao para ituro kung saan sila uupo kung na set na 'yong ano... hindi po ba?

132. Para ibig sabihin na, iparamdam doon sa mga hihikayatin natin na sila ay welcome na welcome roon sa ginagawa natin. Minsan kasi, sa una pa lang ay naramdaman na nilang parang napaka layo at hindi ka nila maramdaman na isa kang tao ng Diyos, tingin ko mahirap tayong maka kumbinsi.

133. Isa rin po siguro, kailangan din talaga na sa team mo. Kailangan, matuto rin sila lalong lalo na sa... ibig sabihin, parang nagtatrain ka rin ng leader.

134. Parang, mag train ka maging disciple sila para mas maramin alam tungkol sa Panginoon.

135. Ayun din ang isang nakikita ko dahil nga, wala rin naman silbi kung pupunta ka roon sa church planting program mo tapos 'yong mga kasama mo.. paano kung may matanong din sila? Ibig sabihin may mga ready questions din sila na manggagaling din talaga sakanila. Doon sa mga simple question ay kaya nilang sagutin.

136. Tsaka 'yong last po siguro ay disciple.

137. Parang iestablish mo rin 'yong presence mo muna. Bago muna sana yun, pastor. Yung presence ng grupo, hindi mo sila bibiglain kaagad na parang yun bang... maybe, establish a presence,

138. iyong puwede kang mag medical mission doon muna. Medical mission or whatever na para bang pag tulong sa tao. Na sabihin bang medyo mapapa angat 'yong kilay, "ano 'yong ginagawa ng mga 'yon?," "parang okay 'yong grupo na 'yon ah."

139. Strategies and practical ways of implementing the church planting curriculum

<p>139. Mga gano'n, pastor. Ayun po 'yong nakikita kong practical ways para ma establish natin ang church planting curriculum.</p>	
<p>R17: 140. In implementing a church planting mission curriculum, we need different instructions. These are very practical but we need a variety of instructions 141. and adapt to appropriate different learning styles 142. to be able to have engagements from the learners. Hands-on activities, discussions, group work and other interactive ways could be part of the active learning. 143. So assessments are also needed, feedbacks are necessary to know the progress of learning and guide to become our guide to enhance the program or the mission of the church.</p>	<p>140. training and lectures on church planting mission 141. strategic planning 142. engaging and experiential curriculum 143. evaluation and reflection</p>
<p>R18: 144. I think kung maaayos to o mabubuo ito, maganda siya na isama sa program ng conference di ko lang sure pastor kasi diba madami tayong communities and boards pero para sakin maganda siya na kasama siya 145. at implement siya 146. sa pag aaral, 147. pwedeng by district o by cluster kung saan mas madali para sa lahat, 148. then maari din ito na yung pagkakataon na i-gather natin lahat yung mga churches natin kasi somehow meron yang mga tinatawag silang best practices kasi pwedeng yung best practice namin dito sa sa Cordillera hindi effective halimbawa dito pero samin best practice namin, malay mo pag sa iba gamitin baka maging best din, baka mas may maganda pa siyang magagawa sa ibang district. 149. So maganda yun integrate din siya sa conference course of study at yung conference course of study i-offer siya hindi lang sa mga pastor kundi i-offer din siya sa mga layco kasi partner ito, ang church planting hindi iisa lang yung pastor o kaya iisa lang yung deaconess, sino ang talagang magtatrabaho dito? 150. members, layco, so maganda siya na pag aralan both.</p>	<p>144. Integration to annual conference program 145. Implementation and execution 146. Trainings and seminars 147. Information dissemination 148. Contextual and situational 149. Integrate in other ministerial programs 150. Involvement of lay people 151. Integration to annual conference program</p>

151. Ang ganda pag iintegrate natin ito sa conference course of study natin sama na natin ang ating mga layco.

Are there any gaps or limitations in your current role regarding church planting mission? How so?

Open Coding

R1:

1. Siguro yung limitation ay yung time management,
2. paano simulan kasi ang hirap magsimula eh paano iapproach ang mga leaders yun.
3. May resources ba na gagamitin di ba yun ang palaging iniisip natin.
4. Mga bagay na magiging balakid o problema sa pagtanim ng simbaan o pagmimisyon.
5. Kasi kung ikaw lang hindi mo ginagamit yung mga kasama o sa iglesiya hindi ko alam kung magproprosper. Yun limitasyon.
6. Tapos kung minsan pagiging balakid din yung kondisyon ng iyong pangangatawan yung health condition mo, resources yun siguro.
7. Tapos yung takot yung fear minsan eh mayroon kayang makikinig sa atin tapos yung negative na pagtingin ng mga tao lalong lalo na kung kakilala ka nila. Minsan kilala ka naming minsan nagiging balakid din yon.
8. Ganito ka noon, pang huhusga ganoon. Kasi ganoon talaga ang pagiisip ng tao.
9. Katulad ni jonas ayaw talaga niyang pumunta doon dahil matitigas ang ulo nila sa niniveh. Minsan may pagiisip din na dumadating sa atin na makikinig kaya sila ng ganoon?
10. Tapos yung space dikit dikit na eh. Halimbawa itong salcedo, saan ka pa magchuchurch planting dito. Halos lahat ng baranggay ay meron ng umc. Kung minsan yun din ang nagiging problema sa pagmimisyon, wala ng space
11. pero kung iniisip na meron pa doon sa kabila, halimbawa doon sa candon eh nandyan naman ang sto tomas nandyan naman ang candon umc yung space o lugar. Pero halimbawa yung sta cruz may 48 baranggay hindi naman lahat may umc, yun din naman ang iniisip ng iba pero mayroon tayong ethics eh.
12. Wala naman tayong kamaganak doon wala naman tayong miyembro doon paano tayo makakapunta sa isang lugar na wala tayong kamaganak di ba? Dapat may kamaganak o pamilya man lang na umc na pupuntahan natin

1. Time management
2. Lack of knowledge
3. Availability of Resources
4. Unexpected challenges and hindrances
5. Lack of manpower
6. Health condition
7. Anxiety
8. Persecution
9. Anxiety
10. Saturated area
11. Ethical considerations
12. Unfamiliar territories
13. Fear of failure
14. Ethical considerations

13. alangan naman na pupunta ka na doon na magmimisyon o magchurch planting eh ano ang sasabihin ng ibang denominasyon. Kung minsan balakid din yon problema din yon. Yon ang nakikita kung minsan.

14. Pero kung may family kaibigan na pumupunta dito na taga ibang lugar eh di yung pupuntahan. Pero kung wala paano tayo magiistart. Kanino tayo magpapaalam. Alangan naman na parang Baptist na basta ka nalang pupunta doon at magevangelize eh hindi lang naman pageevangelize kundi magtanim tayo ng iglesiya. Yun ang isa sa mga nakikitang limitasyon problema o balakid.

R2:

15. Tatta usto dayta ta isu ti ringeringebek ti riknak tatta ti BCFUMC nga kasla limited ta nga mangipatungpal iti church planting.

16. Gamin kunak tattay kasla ngay nga pastor lang ti namnamaen da nga mangaramid kadagiti dadduma nga akkem iti simbaan,

17. tapno no awan layko nga agrabaho, malimitaran ka nga talaga nga mapan agmisyon.

18. Maysa pay ti Sistema tayo nga Methodist apay kuma nga baliwan ti regionalization dayta, daydiay ialis alis da ti pastor ket ti church planting dapat bumayag ka nga talaga dita. Ti Sistema tayo ngay nga alis nga alis, awan, kasla mauma ak metten nga agpaalis alisen. Ta no alis ka nga alis kasla met lumangayo nga imulam ialis mo.

19. Diay pastor kasla agadjust manen idiay banger, diay mission nga pinanawan nga irugrugin agadjust manen diay sumaruno.

20. Awanton ti maimulmula. Masapol nga adda ti change ti sumaruno uray diay Sistema tayo nga Methodist. Sapay koma ta daytoy nga regionalization ilukat na dayta. Baliwan tayo diay sistema no ikabil ak forever ittoy Africa wenno kwa kayat kon bareng makamula ak ti ado. Didiay ti limitation.

21. Ken maysa ti Sistema ti church growth wenno church planting di kuma main vision ti church major task of the church is making disciples.

15. Manpower

16. Church administration responsibilities

17. Lay involvement

18. Church worker appointment system of UMC

19. Adjustment period

20. Church worker appointment system of UMC

21. Program priorities of churches

22. Common goal

23. Allocation of resources

24. Current system of the church

- 22. Amin nga committees subservient idiyay koma ti maymaysa haan ng diay Kanya kanya ngay nga agplano ti witness, ti outreach, ti nurture.
- 23. Amin kuma nga resources suportaan na diay making disciples tapno makagrow tayo, maka church planting tayo pay.
- 24. Daytoy ti maysa nga limitation nga kasla ngay kuma clear the track, change the system.

- R3:
- 25. Ay no siak kwa a ado dagiti opinion ken plano. Ngem ti problema support.
 - 26. Ken ti maysa mangipatakder koma ti pilot church ti district tapno Makita no kasano nga dumakkel dadiay nabayagen nga local church awan metten nga dumakkel nga local
 - 27. church tapno ti distrito isu ti mangfinance mangsupport ti sweldo ti trabahador nga mapan idiyay nga ti sweldo na daydiay minimum salary ti annual tapno awan ti problema na nga awan met sweldo kasdiay.
 - 28. Ti dadduma ti limitasyon daytoy isu dagitoy support dagiti trabahador. trabahador pay ti dapat koma ket agasem ibaga da pay nga no adda iruar ko nga isu ti kwa isu ti ikabil you nga kwa chairmanen.
 - 29. Ay ket nagadu ti pagchairmanakon. Siyak payla amin ti chairman ken ti district lay leader. Ay apo kunak. Agiruruar akon tapno ada input nga pagadalan tayo. Dagidiay ti limitasyon nga daduma.
 - 30. Limitasyon ti support haan lang a pinansya. no siyak met nga district lay leader agdama nga akkemo kunana na gamin.
 - 31. Talaga nga nakapsot ti mission program ditoy.
 - 32. Kaaduan na nga maintenancesen ti administrative isu dayta nga administration maintenance.
 - 33. Isu nga dagiti aggraduar ti seminaryo tatta kayat da a ti maintenance kayat na nga mapan iti dadakkel, haan na kayat ti mapan ti misyon.
 - 34. Daydiay koma ti pagkakitaan ti kwa isu daydiay ti maysa nga proposal ko na no adda agraduar iti seminaryo dapat mapan ti bassit nga local church

- 25. Availability of support
- 26. System
- 27. Financial support
- 28. Task delegation and manpower
- 29. Overwhelming responsibilities
- 30. Availability of support
- 31. Implementation of church planting mission programs
- 32. Mission focus programs
- 33. Comfort zone
- 34. Church worker training in mission
- 35. Financial support
- 36. Availability of support

35. ti mangfinance tapno mameet ti salary na dapat programa ti distrito ken annual
36. tapno daydiay programa na didiay ket suportado haan lang nga mapan didiay nga agsermon laeng.

R4:
37. Hindi nawawalan ng challenges kasi yan ang unang una nating makikita pagdating sa church planting yan ang unang una nating titignan kung ano yung mga challenges
38. di ba lagi nating ginagamit yung SWOT analysis yung strength natin yung strength din nila yung kwan natin weakness yung opportunities at tsaka threats so maraming challenges
39. at sabihin na nating may mga iba't ibang limitations din depende sa sitwasyon pero pagdating sa mga ganyang bagay so handa tayo sa mga gagawin natin maliwanag sa atin basta nakikita natin yung maraming possibilities.
40. Learn to know our limitations
41. especially normal yan na budget
42. lalo na pag malakihan ang Gawain mga intentional talaga na disciplemaker na talagang kasama mo sa pagchuchurch planting kasi hindi lahat ay magaling sa church planting
43. hindi lahat ay tinawag doon
44. so the challenge is you need to identify kung sino yung mga taong may puso sa mga yon.
45. So pagdating naman sa misyon in a positive way kapag ang nwpac naman ay magkaroon ng intentional na paggawa niyan its God's work naman na iprovide niya yung mga kailangan natin especially ipapakita niya yung mga taong kailangan mo Siya yung magdadala at doon ka nalang maaamaze. Yun yung mga possibility. So out of impossibilities, gagawin ni God yung mga possibilities out of impossibilities. Yun yung magiging kwan sana natin motto natin sa pagchuchurch planting. Yun lang ho.

R5:
46. Para kanyak Pastor Wesley (Cesar). Ako bilang District Superintendent of course wala sigurong limitation. Dahil sa aking trabaho na gawin ito, na lalong lalo itong church planting. Pero minsan ang limitation dito, kapag may pinag usapan sa mga workers association, ay minsan

37. Addressing challenges
38. Evaluation
39. Addressing situational and contextual limitations of manpower
40. Training and education
41. Availability of funds
42. Training and education
43. Manpower
44. Recruitment
45. Faith and trust in the provisions of God

46. Information dissemination
47. Training and education
48. Knowledge
49. Information dissemination

may nakikita akong gaps. Pag nag chacharge conference ako, may mga churches na parang hindi nai cascade sa kanila yung pinagusapan, regarding sa church planting o regarding sa BEA flagship.

47. Patungkol sa pag BEA flagship, church planting diyan yung tinatawag natin na multiply in discipleship. Multiply in membership. Yun ang nakikita ko. Pero sa aking posisyon, siguro wala sigurong limitation. It is a privilege na i-ano ko sa mga local churches.

48. But in my observation, pag sa charge conference, parang may gaps kung bakit.

49. Hindi ko alam kung doon sa Pastor, o doon sa delegates sa District Conference o sa Annual Conference na hindi nila naicascade. Yun lang ang aking observation regarding this. Pero pangkalahatan, kung ikaw ay Pastor, kung ikaw ay Layko, there's no such limitation para sa akin.

50. Kung ito'y gawin po natin, itong narinig natin, na pakinggan natin, nakita natin dito sa bibliya regarding sa mga bagay na ito na curriculum na ito, wala siguro. Maliban lang kung may problema sa atin.

50. Execution and implementation

R6:

51. Gaps or Limitations. Siguro, ang mahirap sa tingin ko dito yung pag down load mo nang mission sa church.

52. Kasi kung minsan yung church planting sa local church natin dito sa ano, parang Pastor's initiative lang.

53. Yung Lay involvement, iyon ang kakulangan.

54. Pero if you can share, yung mai download mo yung vision mo, tatanggapin nila iyon,

55. pwedeng pas istartan ng mga Layko to get involved also in church planting initiative.

56. Pero hindi naman natin to pwedeng sabihin na si Pastor na yung gagawa.

57. Kasi yung church na established kasi, susupport in terms of ano din sa prayer.

58. Kasi hindi sila makakapag preach, hindi yung mag church planting mismo.

59. Pero sabi nila, pupwedengmag volunteer kami na magpreach na mag pipray kami for the project,

- 51. Information dissemination
- 52. manpower
- 53. lay involvement
- 54. clarity of vision and mission
- 55. lay involvement
- 56. task delegation
- 57. availability of support from members
- 58. abilities
- 59. limited capacities
- 60. Congregational Support
- 61. teamwork
- 62. ministry program
- 63. area survey and information gathering
- 64. consistency
- 65. Information dissemination
- 66. consistency

60. mag support kami financially sa project. Ganun yun. pupwedeng ganun din yung support din nila sa ngayon.

61. Pero yung, tayo na mismo ganyan yung dapat may team kung kailangan may team kasama ang mga Layko, parang sa experience ko, may kakulangan sa ganoon. Halimbawa sa Bachelor noon, kasama ko kasi Diakonesa.

62. Ang strategy doon, VCS.

63. Aside from sinabi kong profiling, alamin mo yung mga pangalan ng mga miyembro, anong religious organizations nila o affiliations nila,

64. inistart kasi namin sa VCS yung sumunod. VCS hanggang naging Junior League. Junior League nung walang VCS, pero nagpatuloy ka pa rin.

65. Hanggang lumaki na yung mga bata

66. Actually, ganun din yung strategy daw yung mga Baptist ngayon. Mga kasama naming Baptist diyan sa Asingan na Bible Baptist. VCS, papatulan na nila yan kasi mahirap nilnang kunin yung mga nagwowork o kaya yung mga matatanda na.

67. Kung yung family, gusto nila manurture yung anak nila, yun. Iti kuna tayo iti Ilocano, ananusan da. Pagtiyatiyagaan nila yun na idevelop yung bata hanggang lumaki hanggang maging Kabataan. Ganun sila kasigasig.² Ewan ko kung makakatulong din na tignan din na strategy yun.

68. Isa sa mga practical ways to do church planting. Baka nga pupwede ngang iconvert yung VCS na church planting din yung isa sa mga activities. Kung magiging intentional sa pag chuchurch planting, baka pwede eh sa tingin ko. Kasi sa karanasan namin, nangyari at mayroon ngang local church doon. Siguro kung seryoso niyo na yan yung record recording. Ilan yung umaattend, syempre alam mo yun yung sino inunurture mo. Pag gumawa ka na ng history ng church, alam mo na kung sino yung mga tao doon. Yung sa gaps, tingin ko yung, sabi ko nga, kung sharing the Gospel ang isa sa mga strategy mo, yung pag nurture nila sa small groups ministries. Baka kailangan din may mapaghandaan din ng church at gagamitin ng Layko doon.

69. Di uubrang Pastor lang yung gagampan nun.

67. Christian growth strategies

68. Intentional mission programs

69. manpower

R7:

70. Siguro, iti biggest problem ti church planting, ti akem iti maysa nga Pastor iti gaps and limitations iti church planter, uray bali-baliktaden tayo ket financial. Yes, financial a supporta

71. ken moral support

72. agsipud ta saan unay a silulukat iti daytoy a conferencia tayo, ta addu unay dagiti alagaden a masurot. Aydiay siguro iti medyo gap wenno beddeng iti pannakaitungpal wenno pannakaitungpal iti role tayo maipanggep iti church planting.

73. Di kuma ket ag church plant ka ket kuwa, nakasagana kuma “oh, daytuyen ti pondo iti church planting, go!” Kasdiay kuma kaso, haan nga kasdiay.

70. Financial support

71. Moral support

72. Overwhelming activities

73. Financial support

R8:

74. Gaps or limitations. On my part yong parang pansarili lang na kung ikaw ay nakapagpatayo

75. especially ngayon parang nire-require sa mga mao-ordinahan na dapat mayroon kang adda napataner mon nga from mission church to become local church

76. yon nga lang nagiging pride ito ng church worker bagama't sa tagal mo na naroon ka sa church assignment.

77. Incidentally maaari sigurong incidentally na naging kaya na, kasi nga ikaw nga yong ano, sika ti nangpataner na tumayo sila sa sarili nilang paa.

78. And you can be proud of yourself and that could be your right to say na ako ito, but if we, yon nga lang the gap here is yong doon sa sarili mong kakayanan baka mawawalan yong lugar ng paggalaw ng espiritong banal. It could be affected will God will allow us to obtain in a scene that we want to be. Hinahayaan lang ng Diyos yan alam natin yan mga hari nga na hinirang nagkasala pa sila nasaplit da but the good things is bumalik sila. So, ito yong nakikita ko for me na maaaring gap when it comes to church planting. In our church na it really non see

79. yong ano natin na sistema na palipat-lipat unlike the other sect.

80. like the born again the pentecost 30 years na yon yong ano nila kasi nga mas makakapag-established ka ng mga programa na pang long-

74. Manpower

75. Output based responsibility

76. Commitment

77. Capability

78. Motivation

79. Church worker appointment system

80. short term appointment of church workers

81. problems and challenges

82. addressing the needs

term at hindi kaya magsasawa yong tao doon sa Pastor kung ano. Anyway, may benefit yong ganoon, iba naman yong sistema nila, iba naman yong sa atin. As long as, we are living by and walking by in God's ways bringing people in the kingdom of God ang nag-di-disturb lang naman diyan is yong pagkasala.

81. Along the way, we can meet struggles maaari tayong matumba rian we are not perfect enough to plan a church but we have a perfect God na maaaring tumulong sa atin.

82. It could be normal na mayroon ngang gaps especially in meeting the needs of the young people kung matanda na yong Pastor kailangang mag adjust sa pangangailangan at magagawa natin yan dahil sa grasya ng Diyos.

R9:

83. Nu limitasyon, umuna nga talaga nga sumsumrek panunot ko ket kwarta. Isu't mangi limit uray kayat tayo, nu awan iti usaren.

84. Panag travel langenen, masapul mo nangruna ket nu dayjay adayo. Isu't makitkitak daytoy nga limitasyon na.

85. Maikaduwwa, dayjay kuna tayon nga haan nga maaramid jay seminar,

86. para kaniyak maysa nga limitasyon met lang daytoy ta bassit met lang iti kwarta,

87. bassit met obraem.

88. And then, maikaduwwa dayjayen uray nu adda kwartam nu haan mo nga ammo dayjay nilaon malimitaran met laeng dayjay trabaho tayo.

83. Financial availability

84. Distance

85. Trainings and seminars

86. Financial availability

87. Capabilities

88. Clarity of goals, vision, and mission

R10:

89. In my current role as a retired Pastor, but you see I'm more of a community person now.

90. I will have to interact with people and I will be more intentional in doing it.

91. It's ironic that when I retire it's where I wish more I'll be more intentional.

92. Why? because I'm not paid to do so

93. and of course I will be more involved in training if you allow me. I can help in developing the curriculum. This is much impetus actually in the district even in churches wala ng

94. masyadong nagpapatayo ng mga churches tinatamad na rin sa pag-mi-misyon yong ganon even if i would have to be more on encouraging

89. Health condition

90. Establishing presence and building relationships

91. Intentional mission programs

92. Financial availability

93. Involvement in trainings and seminars

94. Intentional mission programs

95. Clarity of goals, vision, and mission

pastors to really give importance to mission because that's the growth of the church, that's how the church growth. And not only that the church growth the transformation of the communities will happen.

95. That's really my burden, my burden is how is the church becoming more relevant to the community.

R11:

96. Sa totoo lang, may mga panahong nakakaranas din tayo ng parang hindi lumalago o nagbubunga yung ginagawa natin,

97. kung ganito man ang pakiramdam huwag titigil dahil nga sabi natin pag gumagawa tayo ginagawa natin ito hindi ito para sa atin kundi para sa Diyos.

98. Huwag titigil isipin nating part ito ng pagmimisyon regarding church planting, minsan tama yun nakakaranas tayo ng kahinaan or parang napapaisip tayo na tutuloy ko pa ba o hindi na,

99. maaaring hindi pa panahon na sila'y mahinog darating at darating din yung panahon na yung kailangan lang ng tiyaga ang isipin natin magpatuloy tayo

100. at least ang punto doon ginagawa natin kung ano ang kagustuhan ng diyos tungkol sa pagmimisyon or church

101. planting yun po isipin lagi natin gaya ng yung the parable of the seed na itong seed na ito ay sa ibat ibang lugar ay napunta yung seed na ito sa ibat ibang lugar pero may mga seed na napunta doon sa mabuting lupa gaya din yun, kahit minsan may mga rejection nakikita tayo,

102. alam naman at naniniwala tayo na mayroon at mayroon pa rin yung pintuan pusong bubuksan ng Diyos para sa kanyang salita.

R12:

103. Maysa a makitak a limitasyon ko eti bukod ko a bagi, eti agdama nga akem ko ket isu ti, wenno akem maipan ti misyon a panagmula ti Iglesia wenno simbaan kunana ket mabalin nga daytoy siguro present nga trabaho ti

104. gobyerno ta san met amin nga time during the week ket maipokus eti daytoy a trabaho

105. ta adda met sabali a trabaho nga na ikomit kanyak

96. Expectations

97. Faith and trust in God's provisions

98. Persistence

99. Commitment and motivation

100. Ministry involvement

101. Persistence

102. Commitment and motivation

103. Professional work

104. Time management

105. Overwhelming responsibilities

106. commitment

106. ngem mabalin ko met nga ipaay eti sabali a wagas ken mabalin ko met eti tumulong eti kastoy met laeng nga trabaho.

R13:

107. Maraming mga challenges, ang isang challenges yan yung finances, una dun alam naman natin na ang trabaho ng isang alipin ng panginoon Diyos ay hindi naman lucrative yan, hindi kagaya ng mga professionals na they look on money they are motivated by salary

108. but to be a pastor you're not motivated by salary

109. and there is no support okay lang na mapunta ka dun yung mga challenges,

110. iba pa yung sa mga kasamahan sa trabaho sa mga partner, hindi mo maiwasan kasi tao din yung mga kasama mo, humihina din sila

111. pati din ikaw humihina ka din.

112. Kaya madaming challenges ang problema mo sayo, problema mo sa kasama mo, at problema mo sa trabaho, tao tayo lalaki o minsan babae may mga challenges na talagang struggle talaga.

113. Hindi mo naman kayang iovercome yun na kasi ikaw lang, kailangan mo talagang magpray everytime we will go to certain place we have to start in prayer, pupunta ka sa isang lugar mag preach dapat mag pray ka muna. Prineprepare mo ang mensahe mo at katawan mo.

114. Yun yung mga estratehiya para sa ganun ang pagtatanim ng iglesia mas maunlad very victorious naman tutulungan ka ng panginoon dun, bigla na lang na may gagamitin ng panginoon na hindi mo alam. Yan yung mga strategy na alam ko na harapin mo at gawan mo ng paraan.

R14:

115. Kung minsan pinansya sa ayaw at sa gusto natin

116. naniniwala tayo sa kapangyarihan ng Diyos kung minsan nga kung lilipat ka nga na pastor huwag kayong magdala pero hindi natin alam may pagbabago hindi naman pare-pareho na sana yong mga tao rin, mahirap naman na you're in decipating na ganoon sana pero kung minsan walang kalamam-laman so parang ganoon na sabi ko,

107. Financial constraints

108. Financial availability

109. Support system

110. manpower

111. health condition

112. problems and challenges in life

113. devotional life

114. Faith and trust in God's provisions

115. Financial availability

116. Faith and trust in God's provisions

117. Financial availability

118. Faith and trust in God's provisions

119. Financial availability

120. Distance

121. Travel time

122. Financial availability

117. kaya isang nakita rito na puwang or limitasyon yong wala kang pera parang yan yong gasoline mo, sa ayaw at sa gusto mo alangan naman pag-naglalakad ka lang parang nanghihingi ka na lang, parang palimos naman na siguro yong ganon.

118. Kahit sabihn mo napaka-humble mo puwede bang tumulong kasi ganito, parang ano ka ba naman akala mo ba ikaw yong pinagpapala ng Diyos na nag-si-share ng salita ng Diyos di ba? Pero kailangan pa rin ng, mayroon at mayroon ka talagang...

119. So, yon yong nakikita kong limitasyon sa pinansya sa totoo lang

120. lalong-lalo na pag malayo.

121. Yong sa sinasabi nga ni Lorena kung sa urban ka pupunta kung okay lang diyan sa rural area puwede mong lalakaran.

122. So, yon yong nakikita ko na isang puwang o limitasyon sa pag-mi-misyon, pagtanim, talagang pinansya. Sa ayaw at sa gusto

123. natin alam natin mapagpala ang Diyos, kaya nga ang hirap sabihin mo na parang oh mapag-pala ang Diyos sabten na ti amin a kastoy yong ganon

124. after all parang nagtitimpi ka lang hindi mo na alam kung saan mo kukunin. Yon yong nakikita ko na limitasyon.

R15:

125. Ako po kasi bilang lay leader po ng district, kasalukuyan din akong isang nanay, isang negosyante at isa rin pong partner,

126. pero naniniwala po ako na kung gagawin niyo po kasi lahat yun para kay Lord, sa tingin ko po ang pagiging nanay, ang pagiging anak lahat po yan hindi siya magiging hadlang kasi gagawin mo.

127. Sa tingin ko po ako sa pananaw ko po kasi lahat ng gagawin mo para kay Lord so hahanapan mo talaga po yun ng oras

128. at sabi nga po dun sa nabasa ko bilang isang anak ng Diyos o bilang isang volunteer po na worker ay ipoprovide mo lang po yung effort yung best effort mo and God will do the rest, wala po akong nakikitang hadlang sa pagiging leader ko.

R16:

123. Faith and trust in God's provisions

124. Availability of resources

125. Overwhelming responsibilities

126. Faith and trust in God's provisions

127. Commitment

128. Faith and trust in God's provisions

129. Misunderstanding

129. Ang tanong na 'to, pastor. Parang sa reality na ng buhay ko. Minsan, 'yong hindi pagkakaunawaan ng mga kasama / mga miyembro o kaya 'yong pride kung minsan.

130. Nagmamataasan, may mga na experience eh. Pero ayun, nagkakaroon ng gap doon sa church. Hindi ka makapag implement ng tulad nito, church planting activity kapag gano'n 'yong problema sa church. Lalo na't sabi nila, "may tainga ang lupa, may pakpak ang balita".

131. Dahil syempre, tulad nung church planting program dito sa mouging, marami kaming challenges din na ano dun, pastor.

132. Pero sa awa ng Diyos at sa pagdadasal sa Diyos na maitayo 'yon, kumbaga magawa.

133. Iyon ang isang problema, pastor. Iyong gap o kaya differences sa mga kapwa miyembro.

134. Pangalawa, nakikita ko 'yong financial constraints. Diba kapag kulang ka sa pondo, mahirap din kasi magsisimula ka pero kapag sana bago mo gawing ang church planting activity, may naka ready ka nang pondo. Napaka dali sanang... lahat ng kasi, hindi lang naman ano, pastor. Pati rin doon sa pag prepreach, 'di ba? Kailangan mo parin ng pondo roon eh, lahat ng gagawin mo doon ay kakailanganin mo 'yon.

135. Para hanggang doon sana sa... kapag nakapag simula kana, simula ka sa maliit. Mas magandang unti-untiing maitayo mo na. Hindi ba, pastor? Parang 'yong ginagawa ng mga korean missionaries. Ewan ko lang saatin, pastor. Sa ating mga korean mission, may mga nag fail na ba?

136. Pangatlo po siguro, pastor. 'Yong mother church, hindi rin nagcoconduct ng masyadong outreach program. Para ang outreach program, doon dapat mag simula eh. O kaya, hindi naman sa hindi coconduct o kaya hindi masyadong dedicated yong pag outreach. O kaya 'ykng pag outreach baka mamaya minsan baka ma taken for granted lang . Ayun ang isang nakikita ko kaya hindi mag prosper o kaya maging successful 'yong church planting activity or curriculum. Ayun po, pastor.

130. Disunity

131. Problems and challenges

132. Faith and trust in God's provisions

133. Differences in nature

134. Financial availability

135. Initiative

136. Intentional mission programs

R17:

137. As a deaconess assigned in an institution I am not exposed directly to the needs of the church

137. Overwhelming responsibilities

138. Trainings and seminars

at this point in time. Because I work here in institution, different kind of work.

138. My knowledge is limited as to how I should be involved in the mission.

139. However, I am not closing the door for the opportunity to help in any way I can.

139. Willingness or commitment

R18:

140. I'll be speaking based on my experience, kasi ang church planting hindi siya pwedeng one man committee,

141. it's a church work.

142. So siguro yung nakikita kong parang kulang o sabihin na nating weakness natin yung team ministry na tinatawag,

143. para kasing pag sinabing church planting ay sa pastor lang yan o sa worker lang yan ganun ang isip ng mga tao

144. pero dito sa Cordillera nakita ko kung gaano kalakas ang pagkilos ng church planting pag kasama mo ang layco ko kasi sila talaga yung kikilos.

145. Kaya ako talaga namang hindi kaya pag ikaw lang na worker.

146. Noong first years ko dito siguro mga first five years ko dito sa Baguio na enjoy ko yun hindi ako masyadong nagstay sa Baguio office dito although may kinder work ako pero mas na enjoy ko yung pagpunta sa bundok sa iba ibang lugar kasi makita mo talaga na yung mga tao they hunger and thirst sa word at trabaho ni Lord, so sabi ko kawawa naman sila lalo na sa mga bata wala silang kagaya nung regular churches na talagang nakatutok sa kanila,

147. so napaka importante yung consistency ng work sa pagmimisyon kasi hindi siya one time big time na napunta ka lang dun tapos iwan mo na see you ulit next summer ganun,

148. walang nagfollow up kaya ang lagi kong hinaing din sa mga church workers namin dito mga mission workers naming magstay sana kayo sa mga distino niyo kasi sayang man yung nasimulan, ang dami na nilang pumunta tapos mamaya wala ng follow up so wala hindi siya one time big time kasi.

149. So yung team ministry ang parang nakukulangan ako na kulang sa atin, team

140. Manpower
141. Organizational mission work
142. Teamwork
143. Training and seminar
144. Lay involvement
145. Manpower
146. Intentional mission work
147. Consistency in mission work
148. Importance of follow up
149. Teamwork
150. Consistency in mission work

ministry yung consistency na tinatawag, kaya dahil ito church task ito hindi pwedeng punta ka lang isang beses dalawang beses di pwede kulang na kulang siya. So yun yung naging karanasan ko dito at sa kahit sa anong lugar naman, pag walang teamwork

150. at tsaka walang consistency ng trabaho, tingnan natin hanggang simula lang mamaya wala na.

<p>How would you describe your ideal solution to make a more effective church planting mission program? Why?</p>	<p>Open Coding</p>	
<p>R1:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Kailangan magumpisa sa pagtitipon. 2.Halimbawa sa isang church kailangang planuhin kung ano ang mga hakbang na gawin. Hindi lang yung nakaisip na punta tayo doon magmisyon cguro pwede rin yon pero mas effective yung talagang pagplaplano. 3.Pagplaplano talaga ang kailangan para mabuo ang isang direksyon na magumpisa sa pagmimisyon. 4.Halimbawa sa church hindi lang yung magisip ka na ganito ang gagawin natin kailangang magbibigay din ng idea ng leaders ng iglesiya kung ano ba dapat talaga ang gawin. Hindi yung ganito ang gagawin ko dapat gagawin nating pagplaplano. 5.Pagtingin nung kailangan yung need ng isang lugar o isang tao. 6.Pagkatapos ng planning yung implementation, maimplement na. 7. Pagkatapos ng implementation dapat may evaluation. Evaluate ng mga nagawa o mga gagawin pa. Kung ano ang weakness strength cguro ganoon, ganoon ang pagtingin ko 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Community involvement 2. Strategic planning 3. Roadmap 4. Team planning 5. Needs assessment 6. Implementation and execution 7. Evaluation SWOT analysis 	
<p>R2:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8.Nagtungtong kami dagiti pastors nga kunkunada nga haan da epektibo ti church planting. Kunada ummuna nga dagita seminary tayo ket haan da nga naisagana dagitoy nga church plant. Agmaintain lang ti nakaisaganaan da. 9.Ta kukunak, ay wensa, di napanak ti aldersgate agpayso nga adda ti ministry area mi ngem kasla met di inadaddal mi ket age level ministries, dagidiay traditional ngay nga ararimiden tayo idiaiy uneg ti simbaan. 10. Su kunkunak nga masapol nga apayso nga mabaliwan to curriculum dagitoy seminaryo tapno maisaga dagiti papastor nga inton ummay da practice dagita ay ket atleast adda ti guide da. 11. Kasla ngay no agraduate ka ti seminary kasla maintenance ti kwa na ngay to 12. goal na ta haan nga didiay although kanya kanyang specialization ngem ada dapat ti inPLACE nga curriculum nga agpayso. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Training and seminars 9. Intentional mission programs 10. Addressing the needs 11. Clarity of goals 12. Clarity of vision and mission 13. Training and seminars 14. Clarity of vision and mission 15. Importance of specialized ministries 16. Discipleship making 17. Focus on mission programs 18. Recruitment of manpower 19. Small group ministries 	

13. Kasanno to agchurch plant, kasanno ti ag disciple, kasano nga agrow.
14. Adda kuma amin ngay ti option nga nailatag. Nu siyak, masapul nga agiyan ka nga talaga ti maysa nga church, agfocus iti maysa nga misyon.
15. Worshipping congregation siguro nga igoal mo nga agbalin nga mission congregation and then local church
16. ngem masapol nga bumayag ka dita ken ibagbagak ti DS me ditoy nga nu masapul nga i-appointarak ti small church maappointarak nga specialized ministry.
17. Kaya't ko nga ang major idia task nga making disciples. Agconcentrate ta, ag major ta ti church making disciples, baybayaam pay lang dagiti committees.
18. Inton dumakkel ti church, mabalin ton ti committees, umaddon ton ti tao. Ag evangelize tayo pay, agpaado, disciple tapno haan da mapan iti bangir nga simbaan ang agdisdisciple - alagaan system.
19. Paigtingin ti care group. Awan ti innalisan, agconcentrate ka iti making disciples, agplano ka ti strategim, iaramid mo daytoy nga strategim.

- R3:
20. Ti makitak nga ideal solution no nakaaramid tayon daytoy curriculum iti the whole NWPAC then syempre idownload mo daydiay ipan mo dagiti district.
 21. No napan iti distriton masapol nga adda makipagna daytoyen adda committee wenna board nga mangigem iti daytoy tapno isuda iti
 22. mangkita nu kasano ti panagimplementariti kadagiti local church.
 23. No saan syempre kwa met daytoy district met no agprogram ti distrito maipanggep iti daytoy ti church planting masapol nga well
 24. organized ken masapol nga maorient well supported kadagit local church.
 25. Ket no local church met ti papanan na masapol nga subaybayan ti distrito dagiti local church nga mangimplementar iti daytoy nga programa.
 26. No kayat ti distrito nga idownload ipan da ti nababbaba a local church a dadakkel a mabalin nga agimplementar.
 27. So masapul nga identification iti local church nga able nga makaimplementar kadagdiay nga programa.

20. Information dissemination
21. Organization structure
22. Strategic planning
23. Organization structure
24. Trainings and seminars
25. Support system
26. Information dissemination
27. Strategic planning
28. Adopt proven strategies and methods
29. Information dissemination
30. Framework

28. Ket no addan ti existing na, mabalin nga ireinforce.
29. Suportaran tayo ireinforce tayo babaen dadiay met laeng nga curriculum diyay wagas nga maaramid.
30. Isu nga kunak nga blueprint daytan nga sursurten tayo nga tultuladen tayo.

- R4:
31. Yun nasabi na natin yung iba kanina. Yung hinihingi natin is mas epektibo? Kasi lahat naman para sa akin ay epektibo according to their context.
32. So magiging epektibo lang ito hindi naman natin nililimitahan kasi trabaho ng panginoon ito kung minsan hindi lang naman tayo nakabase lang sa stratehiya ganoon pero dahil gusto nating God is the God of order naman kailangan may maayos tayong matutunguhan maayos na gagawin na.
33. planado ba? Intentional ba?
34. So magiging effective ito kung ito ay talagang pinagaralan.
35. Magiging effective ito kung Nakita mo na yung buong sitwasyon at kung ito ay napaghandaan mo.
36. So hindi naman its not about sa dami ng makukuha mo sabi nga nila its not about yung dami ng nakinig sayo kundi kung ilan yung nagrow dahil sa narinig nila sayo.
37. So when it comes naman sa effectiveness naman ng Gawain hindi lang yung nakabase ka sa bilang hindi lang yung nakabase ka sa quality depende kasi yan sa Panginoon eh.
38. Siya yung nagbibigay ng quality ng magagawa.
39. So yung sinabi ko kanina napagaralan
40. napaghandaan
41. at akma sa konteksto at reasonable naayon sa kanilang tradisyon
42. ito ba ay bible based
43. at the same time fit ba yan sa current experience natin at saka koma sa future experience ng mga taong paglilingkuran natin. Yan ho yun. Salamat ho.

- R5:
44. Ideal solution to make effective church planting. Pero sa akin Pastor Cesar, kailangan na tignan natin ang perspective ng mga Matatanda, Kabataan at mga Bata na kagaya ng sinabi ko kanina.
45. Pag sinabi nating perspective kasi, pag makita po natin lalo't lalo na sa kalagayan po natin ngayon

31. Contextual analysis
32. Faith and trust in God's provision
33. Strategic planning
34. Trainings and seminars
35. Situational analysis
36. Evangelism
37. Consistency in doing mission work
38. Faith and trust in God's provision
39. Trainings and seminars
40. Strategic planning
41. Contextual analysis
42. Bible based mission programs
43. Contextual analysis

44. Learning from the perspective and experience of others
45. Contextual and situational analyses

lalo na sa mga Kabataan na there's a big gap sa mga Matatanda. For example, tignan natin doon sa worship. Di ba ang mga Kabataan, talagang pwede na yung Praise and Worship. Doon sa internet, ang mga Matatanda iba naman. Parang solemn. So, para sa akin, kailangan natin ito na yung perspective nila, makita natin.

R6:

46. Siguro sa tingin ko magiging. Masyado din tayong structural din, pagkaisahan yan, yung talagang. Bagamat ang gagawa nun ay local church, baka sa tingin ko, Maganda na institutionalize in the District level yun.

47. Ibig sabhin nun, monitored din ni District.

48. Halimbawa, kasi kung minsan, hindi kaya ni local church na magprovide ng training sa paano mag handle ng small groups kung siya lang. Pero pwedeng ibigay yun ng District or yung training ng church planting. Sabagay, kung curriculum magawa niyo, at may parang manual, o di yan andoon na yun.

49. Pero paano mo dadalhin yun?

50. Isang local church lang. pero kung the whole District, it's the whole District during the church planting project o ministry.

51. Di sayang din yung susulatin ninyo. Kasi matutulog yung susulatin ninyo na produkto ng Doctorate niyo, matutulog yun kung hindi magagamit.

52. Pero kung the whole NWPAC yun o District, start sa District, magagamit. Ang ganda. Ang gandang magagamit. Kung ma institutionalize as program o mission initiative, mission project ng District, monitored ng DS.

53. Ang DS din monitored niya rin yung performance ng mga Pastor, kung Pastor man o kaya Layko.

54. Baka pwede pa ngang ano to, sa tingin ko dahil ako ang director ng Lay Servant. Baka pwedeng pag aralan, Layko ang pupwedeng sa Layko na side, di ba? Hindi lang naman para sa Clergy yung gagamit. Involve na ang Lay Servant diyan o kaya Lay Minister.

55. Yun yung nakikita ko, institutionalization ng church planting.

56. Kasdiay, aside from void ng local church parang, Pastor center in terms of ministry kasi. Alam

46. Organizational structure

47. Support system

48. Trainings and seminar

49. Information dissemination

50. Organization wide mission program

51. Utilization, implementation, and execution

52. Organizational structure

53. Evaluation and performance monitoring

54. Lay involvement

55. Organization wide mission program

56. Partnerships and integration with other programs

57. Support system

na nila yung mag bible study, alam na nila yung mag discipleship class, pero yung mag church planting ay wala pa sa local church. So, ang training nila sa District o kaya baka pwedeng ganun.

57. Ipartner natin yung opisina ng DS or i-institutionalize yung term ko kanina. Tapos gamitin natin yung Lay Servant ministry para mainvolve talaga Layko. Isang kurso yun ng Layko..

R7:

58. Kasi, mayroon na tayong committee. Addan ti committee iti misyon iti Iglesia tayo. Addan.

59. Maspol laeng nga ilawlawwa da kuma iti saklawen da

60. iti financial a wagas.

61. Ken, kasta met iti moral.

62. Ngem no saan, nasaysayaat met nga adda kuma, maymaysa a target iti misyon iti tunggal Distrito iti unos iti makatawen.

58. Organizational structure

59. Trainings and seminars

60. Financial support

61. Moral support

62. Uniform vision, mission, and goals

R8:

63. Ideal solution for me, if there is opportunity and if there is preparedness and it could be better kasi nga kung minsan nariyan yong nakikita mo na solution, ito yong alam natin na

64. solution maaari din naman tayong mag tap ng ibang tao na

65. makatulong na magkakaroon din tayo ng solution A, solution B kasi nga baka hindi mag operate yong solution A. Atleast may B, kung hindi mangyari atleast may ano pa isa pa atleast may magagawa sana tayo. Kung wala yong paghahanda baka mapapa-atras tayo kung may mas mabigat pa na haharapin tayo para hindi matuloy yong pinagplanuhan so again preparation and then opportunity can be resulted in a ideal solution for church planting.

66. Kasama na rin diyan yong pag-aaral doon sa community. Ano ba yong tradition nila don. Ano ba yong lengguwahe nila. Ano yong buhay nila.

67. Ano yong needs nila na maaari tayong makapag-ugnay-ugnay at magiging church kung wala pang church doon.

63. Strategic planning

64. Manpower

65. Strategic planning

66. Contextual and situational analyses

67. Needs determination

R9:

68. Daytoy jay kuna tayon nga, panangadal.

69. Umuna iti amin, masapul nga adda maiproduce nga manual para kadaytoy.

68. Lectures and seminars

69. Production of church planting curriculum materials

70. Maikaduwwa, isu daytoyen jay kuna tayo nga, manual then ibiyagen. Isu dayjay panagadalen. Isu daytoy iti makitkitak kasi, narigat nga patauden iti maysa nga korrikulum nu awan dayjay pangibasehan. Siguro, mabalin mo nga isearch ti... agi search ka kasi tatta ngamin ket isu number 1 nga... ag research ka, adu iti ma research mo.

71. Ngem, dayjay ba ket usto nga maiyannatop na ditoy pagillian tayo daytoy nga naalam kadayjay nga internet? Baka napintas lang iti ibagbaga na ngem haan met nga maiyannatop kadaytoy nga lugar. Isu nga masapul nga makita tayo, dayjay panangpa taod iti korrikulum, makita tayo dayjay talaga nga area ken needs tapno maaddressan tayo dayjay sitwasyon ka dayta nga lugar. Dayjay laeng, sir.

R10:

72. To me, like I said focus on communities and community

73. building it would look more like a social work project but then it would be effective in changing or transforming communities because the gospel that goes with it and of course the holy spirit that empowers is the one that really makes the church planting mission program effective

74. mahirap yong mission program ng walang ka-latoy-latoy, walang ka-espi-espírito nandoon dapat yong the passion comes from within. It's a faith persuasion that makes you do mission. In your zeal for it even as you implement a curriculum would be the one that would affect people and encourage them parang mukhang bilib na bilib tong taong to sa sinasabi niya sabi nila kaya makikinig sila and give it a try in fact maraming ganoon nakukuha sa salita.

75. When I say community building it means that we engage like in the barangay; like we would be effective workers agencies in the barangay so that we are felt by the community. So that, when we propose something they will also listen to us because we are integrally a part of the community gone are the days when the church was isolated. Yong nakabukod, may sariling ethos ang church may sarili siyang buhay ngayon hindi ang sinasabi ko ang dapat ang church ay kasali siya sa buhay ng komunidad, integrated siya don na hindi siya yong naka-hiwalay na ito secular na gawain, ito religious na gawain. Hindi, like for example doon sa

70. Lectures and seminars

71. Contextual and situational analyses

72. Community engagement and building

73. Social ministry programs

74. Spirit-filled mission programs

75. Community engagement and building

<p>Villanueva pag fiesta ang chairman ng fiesta for them is Metodista yong ganon, it's that church is not isolated kundi talaga integrated into the life of the community.</p>	
<p>R11: 76. Kailangan natin ng focus, 77. at hindi rin maipagkakaila kailangan din natin ng budget totoo yun sa panahon ngayon ay talagang kung gusto nating mabilisan halimbawa transportation kailangan din natin ng budget, hindi natin ipagkakaila yan. 78. And then willing heart to go kung saan man tayo magpaplant ng church ito yung mga kailangan natin yung willingness na gagamitin ka ng panginoon at yung voluntarism kailangan natin po ang mga ito.</p>	<p>76. Mission focus programs 77. Financial availability 78. Spiritual empowerment</p>
<p>R12: 79. Ti bukod ko a kapanunutan maipanggep ti ideal a solusyon tapno maaddaan ti epektibo a programa isu ti kas kunak attay nga adda eti maaramat kuma a tattao ket adda da nga sipapasnek daytoy nga 80. trabaho ken kasta met nga adda kuma kuna tayo a nabileg a relasyon da kenni Apo 81. Diyos tapno dayta ti pangrugyan daydiay situtudyo nga 82. rikna a mangidagadag eti daytoy nga pamay-an tapno adda agbalin a kunatayo nga daydiay adda support system a mapasamak.</p>	<p>79. Commitment to missional work 80. Spirit-filled 81. Motivated 82. Support system</p>
<p>R13: 83. Sa akin bilang pastor, iba iba kasi yung mga estratehiya ng mga pastor, ako naman ang ibinibigay ng panginoon sa conviction ko lang talagang pag nagplano ka, 84. when you start a program even how many years you are in that place continue to do it don't stop even though you encounter many struggles, just go. 85. Dahil metodista nga ako ay natututo tayo sa mga methods na prineprepate, ito na yung programa na pinagprapray hindi pag naisip mo kaagad. 86. Ang council ay minimeeting at committee on 87. evangelism at may asking din naman, ito yung budget na kailangan kung sakaling maprovide ganito bu-bugetan naman ng council 88. at hindi programa yun ng pastor programa na yun ng isang iglesia,</p>	<p>83. Strategic planning 84. Consistency and faith 85. Spiritual empowerment 86. Organizational structure 87. Financial availability 88. Organization wide mission program 89. Consistency and continuity 90. Spiritual empowerment 91. Financial availability 92. Social ministry programs</p>

89. ibig sabihin niyan kahit na ang metodista kasi patransfe-transfer, kung sakaling matransfer ka man pagpatuloy yung kung sino yung pastor, sasabihin naman ng council ito yung pinag usapan naming ayan ganito na ituloy lang, kung kahit anong mangyari tuloy tuloy lang kasi yun ang pinag usapan ng iglesia, si pastor ang promotor ng mga bagay na iyon.

90. Ganun ang nasa conviction ko pinagkaloob ng panginoon dahil pastor ako. Ganun ang estratehiyang nasa puso ko, pinaplano ko na pinagprepray na minimeeting-meeting hindi kaagad pinaplano ko na pinagprepray na itong panahon na to sisimulan

91. natin ito din yung budget minsan may one hundred fifty lang yung budget nagfefeeding pa kami sa outreach namin, ilan kaming pupunta apat yung tricycle na lang mag gasolina ka nough ba yung one fifty?

92. magfefeeding ka minsan bibili ka ng papaluto mo pa arroz caldo

93. kulang pa yung one fifty

94. pero hayaan mo na ang Diyos naman ang magbibili tuloy tuloy lang yan.

93. Financial availability
94. Faith and trust in God's provision

R14:

95. We need to tap people nga they are trained, na-orient sila nakasama natin

96. kasi sa ibang churches two by two yong ganoon para atleast kung hindi mo man agad-agad ma-absorb kasi minsan sa pagod mo na sa dami ng gusto mo atleast siguro expecting na baka yong kasama mo kung dalawa kayo baka mayroon kang mapag

97. tanungan yong parang mag brainstorming ano ang nangyari na yon, yon yong nakikita ko na solution na minsan.

98. Kaya kailangan siguro mag-train tayo o may kasama hindi lang iisa yong gagawa dito kasi limitasyon sa iyong kasalukuyang tungkulin sa misyon ng pagtanim,

99. diba kung minsan nga plano natin itong e-revive?

100. Pero minsan kinukulang

101. na may mga pastor na dalawa-dalawa ang destino how much more na kukunin mo pa dito.

102. Kaya nga ini-encourage kung may mga lay people para maging lay minister atleast pero equip pa rin sila. Yon yong nakikita kong ideal solution

95. Training and seminars
96. Strategic planning
97. Situational analysis
98. Training and seminars
99. Revival of church planting mission program
100. Manpower recruitment
101. Overwhelming activities
102. Lay involvement and empowerment
103. Training and seminars
104. Manpower recruitment

siguro we need to develop members of people na hindi naman yong parang " oh umay kayon"
103. pero kulang naman sila sa kaalaman, siyempre lalo na pag doctrinal yan. Diba may mga biglaan kaya minsan yong mga kabataan natin pag- ini-interview natin sila to become officer kailangan mayroon silang kaalaman kunti sa mga doktrina natin or any structure.
104. Yon yong nakikita ko talaga para makakatulong kasi minsan hindi natin kaya na mag- isa, kaya man pero alam ko na mapa-pagod pa rin tayo kung mayroon tayong kasama atleast mayoon ng karilyebo parang ganoon lang yong nakikita ko.

R15:
105. Simple lang, may kurikulum pag aaralan mo
106. tas wag ka pong sumuko, ang pagmimission po ang pagtatanim ng church hindi po siya ganun talaga kadali kasi nasa isip ko rin po siya.
107. Marami po tayong pagdadaan pero mapapagod tayo
108. pero wag po tayong sumuko kasi lahat po ginagawa natin yan para sa panginoon at wag po tayong titingin dapat
109. kung ano po yung misyon natin kung yun lang po nakafocus po tayo dun kasi kung magpapadistract po tayo wala pong mangyayari dapat po
110. pag gusto talaga natin yang maging effective po sa misyon sa pagtatanim dapat po talagang kasama si Lord talagang matatag po ang loob natin.

R16:
111. Saakin, pastor. Kailangan siguro sabi ko nga. Una, magkaroon ka ng team na magiging dedicated doon sa gagawin mong church planting program.
112. Sinabi nating dedicated, dapat lahat ng time ay dapat present sila na kailangan sila. Ang oras nila ay maibuhos sa programang gagawin.
113. Pangalawa, hindi mawawala ang pag pray doon sa gagawin. Ipagray muna tulungan tayo ng Diyos. Iyon ang hihinhin natin sakaniya na ang idudulot niya, dapat 100% makita nating tulong ng Diyos saatin. Kasi, maniwala tayo na kapag sinarili lang natin 'yan, walang silbi dahil alam nating kakailanganin natin ng tulong ng Diyos sa pag church planting program natin. Sa pagray, nasabi ko na 'yong help ng Diyos. Kasi kung hindi tayo tutulungan, ay walang silbi 'yan. Hindi tayo magproprosper.

105. Trainings and seminars
106. Faith and trust in God's provision
107. Addressing problems and challenges
108. Faith and trust in God's provision
109. Focus and consistency
110. Faith and trust in God's provision

111. Organizational structure
112. Committed manpower
113. Faith and trust in God's provision
114. A time to rest
115. Trainings and seminars
116. A time to rest
117. Critical thinking and reflection
118. No time pressure

114. Tapos ang mga nabasa ko rin, pastor. Although dedicated ang mga tao, ano may time rin sa pagpapahinga rin. Kasi sabi ko nga, kailangan mong magpahinga para rin ano... baka mamaya kasi parang pinipilit mo na 'yong mga tao kung saan tayo mag church planting diba, sila 'yong grupo. Minsan nag iisip din 'yan eh.

115. So, bigyan mo sila ng time para pag-aralan, pag-isipan, baka mag muni-muni sila kung pag-aralan din itong grupo natin na nag aano tayo sa church planting program.

116. Iyan siguro ang isang importante. Habang sila'y nag aaral, 'yong chance na 'yon ay igrab din natin para mag pahinga.

117. Pero ang totoo niyan, binibigyan natin sila ng pagkakataong mag isip din kasi mahirap 'yong pipilitin mo kasi baka lalong ano.... diba, pastor?

118. So, it takes time. Ayun siguro ang ano roon, pastor. Iyon po naisip ko para sa tanong na 'yon.

R17:

119. An effective church planting mission program must be integrated with the entire mission calling of the church.

120. There has to be integration of all programs.

121. You need not to do the mission program independently. For example; you are the evangelism committee kami lang ito, ito lang yong trabaho namin it has to be rather the committee in charge should have a clear and shared vision with other leaders of the different committees.

122. So that there has to be a collaborative work of all people concerned.

123. And then the church worker/s of course first and foremost should empower the mission team that is expected of us. They empowered the mission team, and the empowered team must trust the leadership of the committee.

124. The effective ways to engage people in mission should also match the spiritual gifts of the different individuals to be used in different missions of the church.

125. So, kung ito yong kaniyang gift, halimbawa; if to preach, the gift na marunong siyang mag pray, healing that's one way. So, kung mai-ma-match mo yong mga spiritual gifts na yan don sa mga tao na

119. Alignment to the whole mission of the church

120. Partnerships and integration with other ministry programs

121. Teamwork

122. United vision, mission, and goals

123. Support system

124. Assessment of spiritual gifts

125. Proper utilization of spiritual gifts

iyong gagamitin para sa program o sa mission magiging successful.

R18:

126. From the word planting, pag nagchurch plant tayo para ka din sa isang pagtatanim ng halaman kailangang nireready mo lahat hindi pwedeng yung naisip mo ay dito pwede, dito hindi, dapat hinahanda mo rin parang ipeprepare mo rin yung soil, ano ba yung soil? yun yung mismong lugar na gusto mong puntahan o yung mga tao.

127. You start from where they are, halimbawa may mga magsasaka sila magstart ka kung saan sila, wag mo silang piliting pumunta sa isang lugar na hindi naman sila sanay ganun, ikaw ang pumunta sa kanilang lugar. Parang yung ginagawa ni Jesus nung panahon niya na siya mismo yung pumupunta sa mga tao gumagamit siya ng mga kwento nag evangelize siya sa pamamagitan ng pagdadala sa kanila nung kung ano yung sitwasyon meron sila para mas naiintindihan siya at napakadali nilang maintindihan yung mga turo niya kasi nakakarelate sila relatable yung mga stories niya, kung papano niya hinahalintulad ang kingdom ni God, nakakarelate yung mga tao.

128. So maganda yun start from where the people are kung nasaan sila then build people first before church building, kasi di ba ang church naman hindi yung building, hindi lang yung building kundi yung church ay yung tao.

129. Yun yung nakita kong parang medyo nagkulang ang dito sa area namin kasi ang mga nagpatayo ng mga church building dito ay yung mga koreano. Ang style ng mga koreano kasi magpapatayo muna sila ng church parang pang come on nga sa mga tao so parang doll out ang nangyari, so nung wala nang masyadong ibibigay unti unti na silang umaalis tas nakahanap na ulit sila na kung saan makakapagbigay sa kanila, although very practical naman talaga yun na can reality nga kailangan nilang kumain ganun, so naghahanap talaga ang mga tao ng ganun pero yun nga kung nabuild mo muna yung tao before yung building matibay yung foundation nila na meron man at walang feeding program mag istay pa rin sila sa church.

130. Tapos yung constant follow up very ideal tong sinasabi ko kasi talaga namang kailangan yung

126. Strategic planning

127. Contextual and situational analyses and relevance

128. Establish presence by building relationships

129. Strategic planning

130. Consistent engagement with the community

131. Consistency in doing mission work

132. Availability of funds

133. Careful and not time-pressured implementation and execution of mission program

134. Addressing the needs

135. Social ministry programs

constant na follow up kahit na siguro wala pang church building doon meron na dapat tayong worker na full time na nagbabantay doon na nag nagpupunta doon para magturo mag evangelize ka sa gimongan na tao, igather niya yung mga tao ganun.

131. Yung lagi ko ngang sinasabi yung consistency is the key parang dun tayo nagkukulang hindi tayo consistent mamaya burning tayo ganun very passionate tayo mamaya parang very cold na tayo yung mga ganun tas sila pagod na tayo

132. lalabas na yung mga issues natin like wala na tayong budget ganun,

133. so strategic planning ba ganun, hindi yung biglang andun ka tas nag nagpatayo ka kaagad.

134. Mas gusto ko pa yung mabagal pero at may pupuntahan kaysa yung biglaang andiyan na tayo sabay sabay na yung ministries tas pinunduhan mo na ng bongga tapos mamaya unti-unting hindi nasusustain, hanggang ngayon nauwi sa wala na so sayang siya. Ang sayang ng mga ganun na di na pagpapatuloy, tsaka yung wholesome na ministry kasi alam nating pareho na mga tao lalo sa mga area talaga na mahirap ang buhay nila, kaya kailangan naman din talaga nila yun.

135. Kung may pagkakataon naman na pwede tayong mag medical mission yung mga basic needs na pwede naman nating extend kasi nga ang mga tao maiintindihan nila yung pagmamahal ni Lord sa pamamagitan ng pagmamahal din na mararanasan nila sa tao, so kung nafefeed sila hindi lang sa word ni Lord i-fefeed din sila na matuturuan silang mamuhay nang marangal na pamumuhay. Alam natin na kung saan sila ma fefeed saan nila mararamdaman yung pagmamahal ni Lord, dun sila talaga mag iistay.

What other recommendations would you propose in the development of a church planting curriculum? Why?	Open Coding
<p>R1</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.i-identify talaga yung need. 2.Paano ito isakatuparan 3.para ma meet ang pangangailangan. 4.Pagkatapos mameet ang pangangailangan, 5.paano ito i-apply, paano ito gawin. 6.Pagkatapos na gawin ano ang susunod, nagawa na kailangan may susunod pa para mamaintain yung talagang purpose na curriculum na dapat mabuo. Yun. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Needs assessment 2. Strategic planning 3. Addressing the needs 4. Need determination 5. Implementation and execution 6. Follow up and evaluation (SWOT analysis)
<p>R2:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7.Daydiay impaaw ko ditoy nga napan ni DS Fajardo nagpreach ditoy di pentecost Sunday kunana ket nu dumakkel ti church agkararag tayo, amen kunkuna met dagiti tatao ta naragsak da met ta naragsek nga agprepreach ni DS Fajardo. 8.Idi prayer meeting excited kami kenni matthan ta kunak aysus baka 100 ti umayen ta wen nag amen da met aminen dagidiay. Idi prayer meeting ket isu met lang nga isu. 9.Su kunak di da nangngeg didiay ibagbaga ni apo Dios nga sapulem ti church growth, 10.masapul ti sama samang panalangin. Daydiay ti mapukpukkaw minsan. 11. Addu payso ti plano, strategy, adda vision 12.ngem no minsan mapukpukkaw diay anointing ni Apo Dios. Wala ang power ang Holy Spirit to convince people. 13.No awan ni pastor nga agkararag, awan metten ti layko nga agkararag. 14. Madevelop pay kuma ti prayer. 15.Kasla koma diay template wenno pattern ti prayer. Adda koma ti process ti kararag. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Strengthening devotional practices 8. Manpower recruitment 9. Church programs focused on church growth 10. Teamwork 11. Clarity of vision, mission, and goals 12. Spiritual empowerment 13. Lay empowerment and development 14. Strengthening devotional practices 15. Trainings and seminars
<p>R3:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 16.Ti makitak daytoy kwa ti Makita tayo ti masapol nga diyay umuna diyay potential nga lugar no mano da nga target nga tao didiay. 17. Umuna nga underground, mapan ka ka didiay lugar. 18. Maysa diay profiling mabalin. Mapan ka diay barangay, ibagam ti kapitan, masapol nga ang courtesy call ka kenni kapitan or mapan ka iti profiling 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 16. Area surveying or profiling 17. Establish presence and building relationship 18. Area surveying or profiling 19. Strategic planning 20. Clarity of goals 21. Information dissemination 22. Evangelism

19. no mano ti target mo didiay out from the total population.
20. Masapol diay naananay nga record ken dagidiay targets mo no mano ti target mo then no adda dagidiay targets mo,
21. masapol nga i-orient, ada ti plano mi nga kastoy,
22. syempre no kayat mo evangelismon ah.
23. Masapol nga ada ti evangelistic program mo.
24. Ken syempre sika met ti agaramid ti daytoy gaput ta siyan ti proponent mo agidentify ka met kadagiti inputs mo sa bagay daytoy survey mon inputs daytoyen daydiay panagbuom ti curriculum.
25. Nakapsut talaga tayo ti church planting ken dayta human resource tayo awan ti agtrabaho. Awan metten ti agpastoren.
26. Dayta kunakon nga support.
27. Adda ni nabasak nga libro na kunana awan ti problema ti pinansya
28. ti mission no di ket commitment. No haan nga committed diay tao ang agtrabaho awan nga talaga.
29. Ngem kadatayo tatta ditoyen no awan ti kwarta awanen. Anusam dagiti inputs ko a.

23. Evangelistic programs
24. Strategic planning
25. Recruitment of manpower
26. Establishment of support system
27. Fund generation
28. Spiritual empowerment
29. Fund generation

R4:
30. Tulad ng sabi ko kanina ulit na yung mungkahi we need to develop our own own talaga that fits to the need of nwpac that fits according to our context
31. especially yung hinahanap talaga ng mga tao at yung kailangan talaga ng tao.
32. Yun po yun so kailangan po talaga nating alamin muna kasi katulad ng isang bata kapag umiiyak pag binibigyan mo siya ng dede umiiyak pa rin so kumbaga hindi ito ang kailangan niya yun pala ay ang gusto pala niya ay kalungin mo.
33. Kumbaga hindi mo malalaman yung isang bagay kung wala kang immersion kailangan nating magimmerse muna. Yun yung kwan natin para kapag naging ganito ba ah okay. Hindi nalang tayo basta magassume.
34. Iimerse nating yung mgasarili natin sa mga lugar kilalanin natin sila,
35. ilan sila ano yung buhay nila. Yun po yun para mas malaman natin kung ano yung the best way to address them. Yun lang po

30. Contextual church planting curriculum
31. Needs determination
32. Addressing the needs
33. Immersion activities
34. Contextual and situational analyses
35. Establishing presence and building relationship

R5:

36. Organization structuring

36. Di ko alam Pastor Cesar. Para sa akin, meron sanang committee sa Annual o sa District

37. na I summarize ang mga bunga ng bawat lokal ng Iglesia patungkol doon sa church planting nila.

38. I summarize yung mga best practices ng local churches kung papaano sila lumago upang sa ganoon ay yung mga local churches,

39. ibang iba yung strategy yung pamamaraan natin,

40. ibang iba ang kanilang konteksto sa kanilang pagpapalago,

41. kaya kailangan ang isang committee na ito upang makita natin yung buong pangkalahatan kung ano talaga ang kailangan para sa buong Annual Conference.

42. Although, meron naman yung tinatawag na Christian Education. Yung Discipleship Program.

43. Pero minsan, nawawala itong summarize na talagang nakikita natin kung ano talaga ang iyong best practices sa pagpapalago ng every local church ng Annual Conference. Ang nakikita ko talaga in general sa reporting sa Annual Conference, ini rereport ang ang ating mga programs. Ito po yung mga na-involve. Ito yung mga attendance. But here, wala akong Nakita na sina-summarize nila

44. for example, ang ganitong Distrito, ganito ang mga best practices.

45. Itong local na ito, because of the CDG, ito ang nagiging dahilan kung bakit nagiging Five (5) Million ang kanila, okay.

46. Yun sana ang makita natin upang sa ganoon, gawin po natin na magkaroon ng isang committee,

47. na patungkol lamang dito na makita upang mai summarize kung ano ang best practices

48. ng bawat lokal na Iglesia.

37. Information dissemination
38. Adopting proven methods and strategies
39. Strategic planning
40. Contextual analysis
41. Organization-wide mission program
42. Establishment of discipleship – Christian education programs
43. Information dissemination
44. Adopting proven methods and strategies
45. Small group ministries like covenant disciple group (CDG)
46. Organization structuring
47. Adopting proven methods and strategies
48. Information dissemination

R6:
49. Curriculum atsaka siguro, manual niya.
50. Para alam mo kung papano ka magbubukas, paano mo uumpisahan, paano mo tapusin ganun. (So, within the curriculum po, mayroong manual?) Sa tingin ko, kasi si

49. Church planting curriculum manual
50. Church planting curriculum as framework
51. Training and seminar

curriculum parang manual na yun, pero study kasi yun eh.

51. Studihin ng ano yun pero yung application niya, kahit may isang booklet lang na manual paano mag start.

52. Pero sa tingin ko kasi, yung pag church planting kasi diyan yung, ako'y naniniwala pa rin power ng prayer kasi dapat may isa sa mga discipline ng napalalob sa church planting initiative yung prayer talaga yung isa. Hindi ko alam kung saan mo na daldahin yun pero yung recommendation ko na pang walo yun.

53. Baka maganda paano, yung how to do it na step by step lang. Parang bullet point lang siguro. Step one, pano gawin, kasi kung minsan yun ang mahirap anong unang hakbang kung anong gagawin. Hanggang sa paano ma accomplish.

54. Ito ba eh hanggang sa maging local church, o ang pag buo lang ng community.

55. Di ba kasi yung susulatin niyo, curriculum lang, kasi pag aaralan ng church planter yun

56. yung actual implementation niya yun yung mas sa tingin ko baka kailangan.

57. Tapos it works sa ano mang context, rural man o urban parang ganun kasi yung nature na natin dito sa NWPAC, rural, urban ganyan di ba? Mayroon tayong ganun. Kung sa tao, may ID tayo ganun.

52. Strengthening devotional practices

53. Detailed church planting curriculum that will serve as a guideline

54. Clarity of goals

55. Church planting curriculum development

56. Implementation and execution

57. contextualization

R7:

58. Umuna nga maisingasing ko, dagiti mangbukel ken mangadal iti curriculum, ket dagiti kuman addan padas na iti church planting.

59. Hindi yung kumbaga, bubuo ka ng curriculum tapos yung sasali doon eh hanggang Theory lang. Kahit pinag aralan mo ang church planting, kahit hanggang Theory ka lang, kung wala ka namang experience, useless din yun para saakin ha.

60. Sorry sa iba. Pero, mas Maganda kung nagbukel tayo iti curriculum, ag adal tayo iti curriculum, para iti daytoy, kadagiti tartariggayggayen tayo. Rumbeng nga dagiti

58. Manpower recruitment

59. Implementation and execution

60. Organization structuring

61. Strategic planning

62. Financial support

63. Manpower recruitment

64. Establishment of support system from the organization

65. Information dissemination

66. Trainings and seminars

67. Information dissemination

68. Trainings and seminars

agtugaw sadiay, ket addan kapadasan na iti church planting.

61. Maikadwa, iti praktikal a pamay-an kuma iti curriculum, ket maaddaan iti “one church, one year policy” iti tunggal Distrito nga iti unos ti makatawen, sadiay ti paka konsentretan dagiti programa,

62. tulong financial. Kumbaga, for example kuma ket: one percent of church income monthly, iti mapan sadiay,

63. ken manpower sakbay a iyawat daytoy iti mission wenno Pastor in-charge kasdiay aydiay. Kasi adaddallek dagidiay Pastor, adaddallek dagitay daddumma nga churches. Kumbaga, dagitay haan ko banggitten iti nagan da ta mapadayawan da met unay. UMC tayo eh, ngem kasta iti inkasta da.

64. Diay masya nga biggest churches ket tatta ket kuwa, no adda mapatakder nga church da, idiay da nga I concentrate iti financial support da. One percent of all of their income, monthly, mapan idiay mang tulong ti evangelistic service, etc. . At lahat ng mga church workers sa isa ring church, ganito rin ginagawa. Dagiti amin nga church workers, iti dayta within that district or within that zone, mapmapan da iti daydiay nga church nga tumulong da nga agmission iti daydiay nga church until nga kabaellan diay nga church iti bumangon, isissu nga agbatin ton idiay nga church diay Pastor in-charge iti mission, kasdiay. Innut da nga ikkatten, kasla diay style ti Koreano, ganoon. Nag mayat diay nga strategy.

65. Maikatlo ken maudi, dagitoy a curriculum ket maibingay iti Annual Conference session. Ket dagiti delegado, isu dan to metten iti mangi-relay iti churches da. Ganoon yun.

66. Magkaroon tayo ng kahit mga, let’s say, one hour. One hour is enough na yun. Marami ka nang maibabagahi doon.

67. Tapos, mag babahagi kayo ng mga manuals, yun na rin ang irerelay nila sa pagdating nila sa distino nila. Yung mga Pastor at mga Layko, “Oh ito, napintas daytoy” kunada.

68. Syempre, eh di parang nagseminar, sila na magseminar sa mga churches nila.

R8:

69. When it comes to curriculum on church planting hindi talaga nawawala yong evangelism, tungkol sa preaching.

70. Dapat components ng church planting and then siguro puwedeng idagdag kung ano ba yong kalagayan ng mga tao doon.

71. We can specify the people living in the community.

72. This could be an addendum doon sa kung may naka set na curriculum yong buhay ng mga tao. Halimbawa yong community ng mga magsasaka. Ano ba yong kaugnayan ng pagsasaka sa pananamapalataya? paano ba natin i-u-ugnay yong pagsasaka doon sa ginawa ni Kristo and we can understand that the living of the people there na yong ginawa ng ating Panginoong Hesu Kristo ay naka benefit ang lahat ng tao na mananampalataya sa kaniya.

73. Ganoon din yong mga magsasaka yong sinasaka nila ay naka benefit ito sa ibang tao. Kung ito ay kanilang iga-gather ilalako ito, eh di this people can be benefited kasi tayong mga Pinoy we need rice yan yong bumubuhay sa atin unlike the other countries.

74. Ganoon din don sa ating pananampalataya that we can be benefited on the goodnews, the death and resurrection of our Lord Jesus Christ. Siguro yon yong idadag-dag natin sa curriculum what is the life and then what we can see on the life of our Lord Jesus Christ and then they can understand Jesus Christ doon sa kanilang buhay and it will be the church.

69. Evangelistic programs
70. Contextual and Situational analyses

71. Area survey / profiling

72. Contextual and Situational analyses

73. Addressing the needs of the community

74. Trainings and seminars

R9:

75. Daytoy jay kuna tayon nga, panangadal.

76. Umuna iti amin, masapul nga adda maiprovide nga manual para kadaytoy. Maikaduwwa, isu daytoyen jay kuna tayo nga,

77. manual then ibiyagen. Isu dayjay panagadalen. Isu daytoy iti makitkitak kasi, narigat nga patauden iti maysa nga korrikulum nu awan dayjay pangibasehan.

78. Siguro, mabalina mo nga isearch ti... agi search ka kasi tatta ngamin ket isu number 1 nga... ag research ka, adu iti ma research mo. Ngem, dayjay ba ket usto nga maiyannatop na ditoy

75. Trainings and seminars

76. Production of material resources

77. Trainings and seminars

78. Contextual

79. Strategic planning

80. Area survey / profiling

81. Needs determination

82. Addressing the needs

pagillian tayo daytoy nga naalam kadayjay nga internet? Baka napintas lang iti ibagbaga na ngem haan met nga maiyannatop kadaytoy nga lugar.

79. Isu nga masapul nga makita tayo, dayjay panangpa taod iti korrikulum,
80. makita tayo dayjay talaga nga area
81. ken needs
82. tapno maaddressan tayo dayjay sitwasyon ka dayta nga lugar. Dayjay laeng, sir.

R10:

83. I would like an ecumenical approach to church planting hindi siya denominational masyado in this day and age kasi people don't really matter about the label hindi naman siya masyadong

84. particular it is how that movement affects their life that really really kahit na they don't care from independent church niya or they're are more taken in but is it effective for them to live a life mas makakatulong ito because in the end pupunta sila mag-jo-join sila sa isang

85. movement na makaka affect ng kanilang buhay how they live their lives in this world and how purposeful may goal na nakikita nila na makakatulong ito ng mga tao, nagjo-join ng mga movements dahil don.

86. And of course, the people also finding ways by which their life can be more meaningful and useful.

83. Ecumenical or inclusive type of church planting mission curriculum

84. Contextual

85. Addressing the needs

86. relevant

R11:

87. We need to pray, nagsisimula yan sa panalangin and ask for the lord guidance, dahil ang trabahong ito hindi natin trabaho kundi ay to ay trabaho ng Diyos

88. kung trabaho natin ito ay talagang maiistress tayo pero dahil nga trabaho ng diyos ito kailangan nating manalangin kasi siya mismo ang magpapalago nito at siya din yung bahala kung saan nya tayo dadalhin, we need to pray and ask for the lord pati rin yung place na kung saan saan tayo pupunta, we need to pray kasi hindi po kasi pwede yung naisip mo na o gusto ko doon punta ka na agad

89. alalahanin natin may karanasan din si pablo na ganun gusto niyang pumunta sa isang lugar pero pinagbabawalan ng Espiritu kaya we need to pray

87. Strengthen devotional practices

88. Faith and trust in God's provision

89. Training and seminars

90. Leadership development

91. Involvement of lay people

92. Clarity of vision, mission, and goals

93. Recruitment of manpower

94. Proper utilization of manpower

kung saan ang lugar na na dalhin tayo ng panginoon hindi po madali ang sabihing halikayo punta tayo doon para mag church planting

90. at saka pastor ang nangunguna pa rin sa

91. pagmimisyon hindi mga laico kung kaya ng mga laico suportahan kasi gaya nga sinabi ko hindi lahat ng bagay kayang kaya ng pastor na solohin.

92. Kung walang vision ang pastor na mag misyon magiging maintaining pastor yan.

93. Bigyang pansin ang mga pastor na nagmemisyon at bigyan ng mas mahabang termino sa iglesia kung saan sila, kung masipag sila

94. at nakikita naman na talagang maganda yung vision bigyan mo ng mas mahabang panahon para siyay makapaglago isang taon na term of conference year naku nakikipagkilala ka lang non sa kanila.

R12:

95. Maysa a banag nga mabalin a mai-suggest ko ket adda kuma daydiay mapili tayo nga maawagan daytoy kasla curriculum consultant kuma

96. tapno ti kasta ket within NWPAC or ti kabangibang tayo a konferensya ken uray pay dadduma a annual conferences a tumulong eti pannakabukel daytoy,

97. mabalin nga dagitoy a consultant ket mabalin da nga maka-e-share eti best practices tapno isu ti tuladen tayo ken e-enhance tayo.

R13:

98. Ang isang nakikita ko may mga alipin ng Diyos na binigyan talaga ng ministry ng pag o-open sa church nandun sila may mga pastor naman na binigyan ng panginoon na para bang division ang labor na kung sino yung nakitang mas effective na pastor doon sa misyon ay doon sya.

99. May mga pastor na doon lang sa mission kagaya ng kasama nating pastor ngayon sa diyan sa baguio nag DS pa siya, mas ginugusto niya ang isang mission, nasa mission siya ngayon diyan sa Baguio.

100. Inayawan niya yung magandang trabaho ng isang district superintendent then pumunta siya sa misyon yun kasi nasa puso niya, ako naman ay

95. Organizational structuring
96. Organizational support system
97. Trainings and seminars

98. Determination and utilization of spiritual gifts of the manpower
99. Focus on mission programs
100. Motivation
101. Recruitment of manpower
102. Establishment of support system

sang ayon dun na may mga pastor talaga na binigyan ng panginoon na siya lang talaga magtatayo,

101. may mga pastor naman na pupunta siya sa urban place nagha-handle ng iglesia, yun naman lang ang mairerekomenda ko kung sino yung mga pastor na nakikita na dito ka magmisyon

102. pero kailangan mo ng suporta talaga kasi nasa misyon siya.

R14:

103. Nowadays, sa ating present issues ng ating simbahan siguro yong doctrinal foundation, kasi minsan kahit sabihin mo silang nanampalataya na, kasi hindi naman tayo naka focus sa biblical paano siya

104. like sa konteksto na ito in real world pagkatapos sasabihin mo itong biblical pero ang hirap minsan... so yon yong nakikita ko.

105. So, siguro tignan natin yong doctrinal foundation yon yong kailangan na ma-enhance ma-nurture na bigyang pagtuunan sa pagbuo ng curriculum yan yong nakikita ko

106. tsaka doon sa mga beliefs may mga IP's may mga remote place minsan ang problema doon sa baguio yon ang sinabi nila kasi may mga ani-anito doon sa Cordillera yon yong problema pagkatapos magsasalita ka ng bibliya tungkol sa panginoong Diyos. Ito yong nakalakihan nila lalo na pag mga matatanda na yong mga kanunuhan kung ano yong mga tawag nila don mga anito, siguro sa mga beliefs, sa doctrine yon talagang mga makitang bigyan...

107. kung ire-rekomenda ko kailangan yong doktrinal. Kasi nakakalito minsan sa dami ng mga nagsusulputang mga paniniwala pagkatapos ito pang social issues paano natin ire-reconcile kung minsan dugo pa lang pagkain sa dugo, mga LGBTQ or whatsoever yon yong nakikita ko na isang mabigat na bigyang rekomendasyon yong mga doktrina kasi yon yong foundation natin kahit na anong mangyari kung matagtag na ang doktrina natin alam ko kahit anong issue yan na mame-meet natin alam ko matatag at matatag hindi sila magigiba.

103. Training and seminars

104. Relevance

105. Training and seminars

106. Contextualization

107. Biblically grounded curriculum

R15:

108. Trainings and seminars

108. Yun nga po yung mga trainings, after trainings po

109. kasi hindi lang po siya natatapos doon, sa tingin ko so napakaimportante po na after nitong mga trainings na to yung mga tao po na nate-train natin para sa kurikulum na to dapat patuloy natin inu-nurture. Hindi po kasi yung nagtraining ka tas trinain mo sila tas mag iistop ka na po dun. Kailangan po meron po yang ganyan nurturing, mentoring, pwedeng yung mga ganun po kasi yun po yung madalas na nawawala. Sa tingin ko ah based on my experience, yun po yung madalas na nawawala kaya yung simbahan nawawala din.

109. Discipleship and mentoring programs

R16:

110. Kailangan pong ano... siguro, kailangang tutukan. Ibig kong sabihin, dito sa mother church ay kailangang iparamdam na ginagabayan sila ng mother church siguro, pastor. Na huwag iiwanan kasi parang mga anak din na saating mga pilipino ay kumbaga ay adult na siya pero ndoon parin ang suporta ng parent ay nandoon parin, pinaramdam parin hanggang sa mag pamilya. Gano'n din po siguro dahil ang magandang gawin bilang mother church ay iparamdam natin na " oh, kapag may problema kayo nandito lang kami, parang ganoon po, pastor. Iparamdam na hindi sila iniwan maging full local church man siya ay

111. kailangan ano... kasi kung minsan, may nakikita akong gano'n, pastor. Kasi kung minsan may nakikita akong gano'n na, para bang kung minsan ay mayro'n pang hindi pagkakaintindihan doon sa mother church at doon sa anak na church niya. So kapag kasi nangyari 'yon, baka kasi mag fail 'yong bagong church.

112. So, dapat isustain 'yong pag-gabay. Lahat na, kapag sinabing pag- gabay, iparamdam 'yong hindi sila naiiba at sila'y nandito lang para bahagi sila sa kqtawan ni Kristo dahil nga tayong lahat ah part ng body ni Jesus Christ so, iparamdam natin 'yon na kapag may pangangailangan sila ay handang tumulong 'yong mother church. Iyon po ang importanteng mairerecommend ko para maging tuloy-tuloy 'yong pag lago nung nai plant o naitanim na church, lqlo na po sa mouging na pinag uusapan.

110. Establishment of organizational support system

111. Sustainability and accountability

112. Establishment of organizational support system

R17:

113. I recommend that the development of a church planting curriculum must be approved during the annual conference, may bisa yon mas ma bisa pag ito ay approve during an annual

114. conference and it has to be adapted in each district and to be in full implementation by the local church.

115. Minsan kasi nata-traffic doon sa district and the local churches no matter how small it is.

116. I know big churches, small church pareho lang iyon all have to implement and then it has to be intentional in its purpose it's really part of the program of the church hindi lang yong ginagawa mo dahil ito ay legislation na annual conference and you have to do it intentionally and then there has to be a guide directly to the team who will do it not only for a conference year, but it has to be a long-term program of the church.

117. May continuity kahit sinong Pastor and dadating, malilipat, o kaya'y iba yong maghahandle ulit na committee members there has to be a

118. continuity and then a very important is the assessment and feedbacks it must be given attention to, every now and then for a clearer purpose. Because sometimes along the way meron kang makikitang flaws or kailangan mong i-produce shoot na mga issues or problems na mai-encounter mo.

119. And then I also, in particular with the funding it has to be stable and available always to mobilize the mission work of the church.

113. Organizational – wide mission program

114. Implementation and execution in local church levels

115. Information dissemination

116. Intentional church planting mission programs

117. Sustainability and consistency

118. Evaluation and reflection (SWOT analysis)

119. Financial stability

R18:

120. Maganda yung magkaroon din ng survey kasi sabagay in a way tong ginagawa mo parang survey na din ito na nagiinterview ka ganun, pero kung halimbawa pupunta ka sa isang lugar para dun nga magchurch planting mag survey ngayon sa mga tao kasi meron at meron na niyang maibibigay na maganda like malalaman mo na marami pala sa lugar na yun kahit sabihin mong madaming church building doon meron pa rin palang hindi nagsisimba o meron pa rin palang naghahanap kasi hindi nila gusto dito halimbawa kasi may hinahanap sila. Survey

120. Area survey / profiling

121. Feasibility study

122. Church mapping

123. Support system

121. tapos feasibility study alam ko basic naman ito tas nakapaloob din syempre sa feasibility study

122. na meron ka na ding church mapping para nga may aangla mo siya maiconnect mo siya makakahanap ka ng mother church niya kasi importante yun yung may mother church

123. siyang magsusustain talaga na magfofollow up mga ganun. So yun so far yun yung naiisip ko na pwedeng ishare.

Appendix 5. Transcription and Open Coding

Axial Coding

What is the importance of developing a church planting curriculum in NWPAC?
Why?

Main Category: Assessment Framework

Causal Condition	Phenomenon	Strategies	Consequences	Context	Intervening Condition
Church Planting Mission Engagement	Educational Resource	Critical Needs Analysis in Church Planting Initiatives	Enhanced Church Planting Efficacy	Contextualization	Organizational Structure
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of church planting mission and need for more endeavors (2) • Engagement in missional activities (2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Curriculum as the framework and necessity of Church Planting (40) • Curriculum as a teaching manual and internal resource material (2) • Importance of curriculum as a guide in church planting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs assessment, contextual and situational analyses (7) • Concrete planning and strategizing (1) • The curriculum as a need determinant (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Result oriented or output based curriculum (1) • Lay empowerment and involvement in church planting (3) • Spiritual growth and empowerment (2) • Training and equipping (2) • Sustainability and structural 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biblically aligned curriculum, evangelism, discipleship, and community growth (8) • Church planting curriculum in Wesleyan identity (1) • Technologically integrated curriculum (2) • Experiential and joyous learning (2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematically organized curriculum (4) • Curriculum as foundation, guiding principle, and universal system for church planting mission (3) • Curriculum as an objective tool (1) • Developing a committee to handle church planting mission (1)

	mission (2)		integrity (2)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of expert group (1) • Limited structure due to lack of curriculum (1) • Vision as the guiding principle (1) • Commitment driven curriculum (2)
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What do you think are the needs to develop a church planting curriculum for NWPAC? Why?

Main Category: Grounded Methodology

Causal Condition	Phenomenon	Strategies	Consequences	Context	Intervening Condition
Social Geography	Contextual Adaptation	Cultural Immersion	Contextual Missiology	Community Dynamics	Collaboration of church workers and lay people
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contextual study of NWPAC and situational analysis (3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action based on context, situation, and need (1) • Contextual 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct area surveys for church planting / site assessment (1) • Survey 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evangelism (1) • Spiritual formation of the community (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of potential members (1) • Community needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborative work between the church workers and the lay people (2) • Informatio

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determining the geographical and contextual situations (1) • Community presence and location feasibility (1) • Situational assessment of a community (1) • The need for data and information gathering (1) 	<p>relevance (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizational adaptability (1) • Addressing the needs of the community in a relevant manner (1) • Continuous education and adaptation (1) • Need for a unified curriculum (1) • Improvement of the curriculum (1) • Ensuring the united methodist identity (1) • Pursuing the right doctrine and biblical teaching (1) 	<p>and Assessment of community background and needs (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of studying the community (1) • Understanding the identity of the church (1) • Knowing the perspective of the lay people (1) • Needs assessment (4) • Determination of specific curriculum to assess the needs (1) • Assessment of overall needs including the church planter, the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Congregational building (1) • The church's identity of bringing people to God (1) • Membership growth, invitation, and soul winning (1) • Intentional disciple ministries (1) • Social ministry programs (1) • Spiritual empowerment (1) • Effective strategies and methods on church planting endeavors including impleme 	<p>assessment (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Program development for specific needs (1) • Addressing financial needs (1) • Being resourceful and utilizing available resources (2) • Realization of goals and objectives (1) • Organizational Structure (2) • Specific team for implementation / Focus team (2) • Strategic planning (2) • Concrete planning and needs 	<p>n sharing (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive team members (1) • Lay empowerment (1) • Passionate and committed people for church planting mission (1) • Inclusivity and openness to others (2) • Encouraging the spiritually gifted people to join the cause (1) • The need for manpower (3) • Recruiting the right manpower (2) • Training and equipping (1) • Leadership trainings
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		<p>y, and the people involved (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs determination (1) 	<p>ntation (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical application (1) 	<p>determina tion (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity of vision and mission (3) 	<p>for task delegation (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership training for church leaders (1) • Importance of training in biblical and UMC doctrines, and evangelis m (2) • Invol vement of experience d church planters in the curriculum (2) • Basis for church planting curriculum developme nt (1) • Impo rtance of having a curriculum for guidance and strategy (1) • Emp hasizing commitme nt in doing ministry (1)
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					<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The importance of commitment (1)• Combination of desire, commitment, and knowledge as a holistic need (1)• Understanding commitment as integral part of manpower (1)• Assessment of spiritual gifts (2)• Importance of consistent actions in mission programs (1)• Sustainability and consistency (1)• Importance of follow up (1)
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Do you have any biblical and theological bases on the church planting mission? Can you share them to me? Why?

Main Category: Church Planting Missiology

Causal Condition	Phenomenon	Strategies	Consequences	Context	Intervening Condition
<p>Church Planting Mission Basis</p>	<p>The Biblical and Theological Philosophy of Church Planting</p>	<p>Intentional Discipleship Programs</p>	<p>Vision and Mission Articulation</p>	<p>Spiritual Empowerment</p>	<p>Human Resource</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The great commission Matthew 28:16-20 as the biblical and theological basis of church planting mission (11) • Acts 1:8 as additional basis for church planting mission (1) • Acts 2 as biblical and theological basis for church 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritizing the great commission as the foundation of church planting mission (1) • The church activities must be in line to the great commission and should be implemented (1) • Theological framework of church planting mission (1) • The biblical and theologic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic and clear approach on discipleship programs (1) • Intentional discipleship and mentoring (3) • Christian education (3) • Evangelism and preaching (1) • Evangelism without borders (1) • Action based ministries and programs (3) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of vision and intentional discipleship as a response to the great commission (2) • The goal of mission (1) • Establishment of program and mission strategies to strengthen church planting mission endeavors (1) • Strengthening of missional support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The importance of the empowerment of the Holy Spirit (1) • The Holy Spirit as the helper in all mission endeavors (1) • The Holy Spirit provides the gifts and provision for missional purposes (1) • Spirit-filled people 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement of the lay people (3) • Educating the church leaders (1) • Goal oriented and output based training programs for church leaders (2) • Recruitment and training of manpower in biblical doctrines (1) • Importance of commitment of those who will be

<p>planting mission (2)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Romans 10:14-15 as the biblical and theological basis for church planting mission (2) • Acts 8:4 as the biblical and theological basis of church planting mission (1) • The letter of Paul to Timothy as biblical and theological basis for church planting mission (1) • Matthew 19:14 as 	<p>al basis of church planting in a holistic approach (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mission of God (1) • Church planting of early churches in the 1st century AD (1) • The birth of the church started in Acts (1) • Core beliefs of faith (1) • Different context but one faith. Unity in diversity (1) • The importance of church planting curriculum in addressing the needs of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intentional mission programs (1) • Implementation of bible-based programs (1) • Improvement and enhancement mission programs (1) • Systematic and orderly implementation (1) • Result-based mission programs (1) • Evangelism (6) • The importance of evangelism as ministry (1) • Soul winning by letting them respond to the good news of God (1) • Soul winning (2) 	<p>from other churches</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of support system (1) • Adapt and realign mission programs according to the contextual needs (3) • The curriculum will bring hope and motivation to the people to participate in God's mission (1) • The curriculum as a transformative endeavor inclusive and open to all (1) • Community building (1) 	<p>for church planting mission endeavors (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spiritual empowerment (3) • Devotional life (2) • Emphasis on the importance of having spiritual gifts (1) • God's provision for the mission work (1) • Diversity of spiritual gifts to be utilized in God's mission (1) 	<p>involved in the support system (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of manpower (2) • The importance of manpower as workforce to God's mission (1) • Recruitment and training programs (1) • Lay empowerment (1) • Inclusiveness and openness (3) • Openness to possibilities (1) • Taking action on certain conditions (1) • Preparation, initiation, and taking
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<p>the biblical and theological basis for mission (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 Corinthians 12:8-12 as biblical and theological basis for church planting mission (1) • Sharing the gospel or evangelism (1) • Importance of evangelism and knowledge of the bible (1) 	<p>the church (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasizing the importance of church planting curriculum (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasis on Christian growth (1) • Letting them learn and discover something (1) 			<p>responsibility (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusivity, nondiscriminating faith, and openness to all (1) • Inclusive approach (1)
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What is your idea of integrating Wesleyan Identity (Scripture, Tradition, Experience, and Reason) in the development of church planting mission curriculum? Why?

Main Category: Missiological Identity

Causal Condition	Phenomenon	Strategies	Consequences	Context	Intervening Condition
Guide in Understanding	Wesleyan Identity Integration	Education Among Church Leaders	Spiritual Growth	Relevance	Educational Adaptability

<p>anding Faith</p>					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The scripture as authority and foundational basis (4) • The Wesleyan identity as a guide in understanding faith (5) • The framework of the Wesleyan identity as a guide in understanding faith (1) • Tradition as guiding principle in understanding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of Wesleyan identity (3) • The Wesleyan identity as framework for program planning and implementation (1) • Wesleyan identity as framework for church planting mission endeavors (3) • Emphasizing the importance of utilizing the Wesleyan identity in missional work (7) • The Wesleyan Identity as a system (2) • The importance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasis on Wesleyan identity education among the church leaders (1) • Training and education on Wesleyan Identity (2) • Christian education (1) • Experiential learning and teaching (3) • Critical thinking and reflection (5) • Emphasis on practicality and simplicity (2) • Importance of experience (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A faith that transforms lives (1) • Spiritual empowerment (2) • Experiencing God in a personal basis (1) • Understanding God's missional work (1) • Calling to do mission with God (1) • Evangelism (1) • Discipleship (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of tradition as basis for inspiration and planning of missional programs (2) • Importance of the Methodist tradition as model in church growth (4) • Contextual analysis (3) • Using Wesleyan Identity as a lens for situational analysis (2) • Contextual, situational, and relevant (1) • Learning from tradition and experience of others (1) • Organization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practicality of doing church planting mission (1) • Action oriented Wesleyan identity (2) • Praxis (action reflection) model of Wesleyan Identity (1) • Adjustment and teachability (1) • Emphasizing the importance of reason as an agent of transformation (1) • Teachability of Wesleyan identity framework (1)

<p>Understanding the word of God (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • God's mission of salvation (2) • The Wesleyan identity as a means of grace to experience and worship God (1) 	<p>Integration of Wesleyan Identity into the church planting curriculum as a resource material for church planting mission endeavors (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Profound meaning of Wesleyan identity (1) • Beneficial (1) • Consistent (1) • Time proven effectiveness (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of experience in church planting mission (2) • Emphasizing the importance of experience (1) • Emphasis on the importance of the experience of others (2) 		<p>and community building (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement of lay people in church planting mission (1) • Organizational restructuring (1) • Importance of organizing and strategic planning (2) • Importance of group ministries like small groups, covenant discipleship groups (1) • Inclusiveness of the Wesleyan identity (1) • Diversity (1) 	
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What do you think are the practical ways including methods and strategies, in implementing a church planting mission curriculum in NWPAC? Why?

Main Category: Strategic Planning and Implementation

Causal Condition	Phenomenon	Strategies	Consequences	Context	Intervening Condition
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Optimal Missional Strategy	Practical Implementation	Community Engagement and Relationship Building	Network Enhancement	Rural-Urban Disparities	Inclusivity and Openness
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic planning (8) • Contextual and situational analysis (8) • Adapt proven methods and strategies (4) • Inclusion of external methods and strategies (5) • Contextualization (3) • Clarity of vision, mission, and goals (1) • Systematic planning (1) • Critical thinking and reflection (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation and utilization of the church planting curriculum (5) • Training and lectures about church planting curriculum (10) • Information dissemination about the church planting curriculum (4) • Execution and implementation strategies (2) • Full utilization of the church planting curriculum (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing presence by building relationships (6) • Conducting ministerial activities (visitations, bible studies, prayers) (5) • Social ministry programs (3) • Need determination (3) • Addressing the needs of the community (3) • Evangelism (1) • Approach household 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lay involvement and participation (6) • Recruitment and manpower (8) • Organization structure (7) • Support system (3) • Discipleship (3) • Task delegation (1) • Diversity of responsibilities (1) • Availability of manpower (1) • Support from external 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct area survey and information gathering (7) • Contextual church planting curriculum (2) • Difference of rural and urban areas (2) • Strategic planning depending on the area of focus (3) • Familiarization (2) • Area profiling (2) • Skill in approaching unfamiliar territories (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion of small group ministries (2) • Inclusivity and openness (1) • Faith-building curriculum (1) • Spiritual empowerment through prayer (1) • The curriculum as a guide (1) • The curriculum as framework (1) • Church planting curriculum

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiential learning and studying (1) • Engaging and experiential curriculum (2) • Evaluation and reflection (1) • Integration to annual conference program (2) • Integrate in other ministerial programs (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ds for bible studies, devotions, and prayer ministries (1) • Importance of courtesy call to the leaders of the area (1) • Importance of the tribe or family elder in establishing church planting mission (1) 	sources (1)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> um in the context of NWPA C (1) • Time management (1) • Addressing financial needs on church planting mission programs (1)
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Are there any gaps or limitations in your current role regarding church planting mission? How so?

Main Category: Navigating Impediments

Causal Condition	Phenomenon	Strategies	Consequences	Context	Intervening Condition
Mission Readiness	Missional Mobilization	Programmatic Development	Community Development	Mission Harmonization	Mission Optimization
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time management (2) • Lack of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manpower / recruitment (9) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intentional mission programs (5) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing presence and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical considerations (2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial availability /

<p>knowledge (2)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of resources (3) • Health condition (3) • Capabilities/abilities (3) • Area survey and information gathering (1) • Clarity of goals, vision, and mission (3) • Limited capacities (1) • Professional work conflicts (1) • Distance and travel time (2) • Devotional life (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lay involvement (5) • Church worker appointment system of UMC (3) • Task delegation (2) • Overwhelming responsibilities (4) • Commitment (5) • Motivation (3) • Fear of failure (1) • Comfort zone (1) • Church administration responsibilities (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mission focus programs (2) • Christian growth strategies (1) • Implementation of church planting mission programs (1) • Execution and implementation (1) • Organizational mission work (1) 	<p>building relationships (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing the needs (2) • Addressing challenges (1) • Addressing situational and contextual limitations of manpower (1) • Ministry involvement (1) • Importance of follow up (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common goal (1) • Program priorities of churches (1) • Current system of the church (1) • Adjustment period (1) • Unfamiliar territories (1) • Saturated area (1) • Unexpected challenges and hindrances (1) • Persecution (1) • Misunderstanding and disunity (2) • Differences in nature (1) 	<p>support (12)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faith and trust in God's provisions (10) • Training and seminars / education (7) • Information dissemination (5) • Support system / Availability of support (5) • Evaluation (1) • Teamwork (3) • Consistency in mission work (4) • Persistence (2) • Output based
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					responsibility (1)
					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moral support (1) • Initiative (1) • Willingness (1) • Anxiety (2) • Problems and challenges in life (2) • Expectations (1)

How would you describe your ideal solution to make a more effective church planting mission program? Why?

Main Category: Church Mission Dynamics Maximization

Causal Condition	Phenomenon	Strategies	Consequences	Context	Intervening Condition
Recognizing Discrepancies	Church Mapping	Geographic Assessment	Strategic Execution	Sociological Sensitivity	Local Engagement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs assessment/determination (3) • Contextual and situational analyses (7) • Evaluation and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic planning (11) • Roadmap (1) • Team 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community involvement/engagement (4) • Establish presence by building relationships (2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation and execution (3) • Intentional mission programs (2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing the needs/problems/challenges (3) • Bible- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and seminars (14) • Information dissemination (5) • Manpower

<p>SWOT analysis (2)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical thinking and reflection (1) • Learning from the perspective and experience of others (1) • Assessment of spiritual gifts (1) 	<p>planning (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Framework (1) • Organization structure (6) • Clarity of vision, mission, and goals (5) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistent engagement with the community (1) • Social ministry programs (3) • Adopt proven strategies and methods (1) • Partnerships and integration with other programs/ministry (2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on mission programs (2) • Organization-wide mission program (3) • Consistency in doing mission work (3) • Careful and not time-pressured implementation (1) 	<p>based mission programs (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spirit-filled mission programs (2) • Relevance (1) • Alignment to the whole mission of the church (1) • Revival of church planting mission program (1) 	<p>recruitment (4)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support system (5) • Lay involvement and empowerment (3) • Financial availability/support (5) • Spiritual empowerment (4) • Faith and trust in God's provision (8) • Commitment to missional work (1) • Motivated (1) • Teamwork (1) • Discipleship making (1) • Small group ministries (1)
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					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evangelism (1) • Importance of specialized ministries (1) • Proper utilization of spiritual gifts (1) • Moral support (1) • A time to rest (2) • No time pressure (1) • Overwhelming activities (1)
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What other recommendations would you propose in the development of a church planting curriculum? Why?

Main Category: Ministry Area Analysis

Causal Condition	Phenomenon	Strategies	Consequences	Context	Intervening Condition
Challenging Conditions	Church planting mission impediments	Church Resource Optimization	Productive Mission Deployment	Institutional Framework	Congregational Care and Support

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needs assessment/determination (4) • Area surveying or profiling (5) • Contextual and situational analyses (5) • Evaluation and reflection (SWOT analysis) (2) • Feasibility study (1) • Church mapping (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support/stability (2) • Fund generation (2) • Sustainability and accountability (2) • Motivation (1) • Faith and trust in God's provision (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic planning (7) • Adopting proven methods and strategies (3) • Organizational-wide mission program (2) • Focus on mission programs (1) • Intentional church planting mission programs (1) • Church programs focused on church growth (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation and execution (4) • Evangelism/Evangelistic programs (4) • Establishing presence and building relationship (3) • Addressing the needs of the community (5) • Immersion activities (1) • Sustainability and consistency (1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Church planting curriculum as framework/manual/guideline (4) • Clarity of vision, mission, and goals (4) • Organization structuring (5) • Biblically grounded curriculum (1) • Ecumenical or inclusive type of church planting mission curriculum (1) • Production of material resources (1) • Contextual church planting curriculum (3) • Relevance (2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and seminars (13) • Lay empowerment and development (3) • Support system/Organizational support system (7) • Information dissemination (7) • Discipleship and mentoring programs (2) • Strengthen devotional practices (4) • Spiritual empowerment (2) • Small group ministries like covenant disciple
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					<p>group (CDG) (1)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Determination and utilization of spiritual gifts of the manpower (1)• Teamwork (1)• Manpower recruitment (5)• Leadership development (1)• Involvement of lay people (1)• Proper utilization of manpower (1)
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Appendix 6. Axial Coding

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the *Dissertation of CESAR TAQUEBAN REYES JR* entitled *“Sowing the Seeds of Faith: Towards Development of a Wesleyan Identity of Church Planting Mission Curriculum”* has been examined by the Ethics Review Committee of the Philippine Christian University, was proven to abide by the ethical codes of **honesty and integrity, objectivity, confidentiality, legality and respect for human subjects and intellectual property.**

This is **APPROVED** on August 29, 2025, and issued for legal and academic purposes.

JULIET K. BUCOY, PHD, RSW
Chair, Research Ethics Committee
Philippine Christian University

Noted :

Junnell E. Guia, MBA, MEI, Ph.D.(C)
Director, Institute for Research, Innovation, and Sustainability
Philippine Christian University

Note 1. Institutional clearance was given before data gathering. No Research Ethics Committee (REC) was organized during that time. After the REC was organized in 2025, the study underwent ethics review, and was proven to abide the ethical codes, hence the date August 29, 2025.

BIONOTE

Cesar Taqueban Reyes Jr. is an ordained elder in the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference and a registered Mechanical Engineer, whose career path reflects a unique blend of religious devotion and technical expertise. His academic journey has been primarily focused on theological studies at the Institute of Philosophy and Religious Studies, Philippine Christian University in Manila. Reyes is currently in the final stages of his PhD in Religious Studies, with his dissertation expected in 2024. He has already earned a Master of Divinity with a major in Missiology in 2020 and a Master of Arts in Christian Education in 2019, for which he received the Best in Thesis award. His master's thesis, titled "Leadership Mentoring Program For The Northeast Pangasinan District United Methodist Youth Fellowship," showcases his commitment to nurturing young leaders within the church community. Before embarking on his theological education, Reyes laid a foundation in engineering, obtaining a Bachelor of Science in Mechanical Engineering from Saint Louis Univeristy, Baguio City in 2012.

Reyes' professional experience spans both religious ministry and engineering fields. In his current role as Administrative Pastor at Bobon UMC & Calaoacan Mission Congregation in San Manuel, Pangasinan, which he has held since July 2023, Reyes continues to build upon his previous pastoral work at Bethel UMC in Sto. Tomas, La Union from 2018 to 2023. His leadership extends beyond local congregations, as evidenced by his numerous appointments within the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference. These include serving as Registrar & Faculty at the School For Christian Youth Development, and holding the positions of Council on Youth Ministry Chair and Youth Coordinator from 2022 to 2024. At the district level, Reyes has maintained long-term commitments as Statistician (2016-2024) and Outreach Committee Chairperson (2021-2024). Prior to his full-time ministry, Reyes applied his engineering skills working as a Mechanical Engineer from 2012 to 2014 at Loadstar Shipping Co., Inc. & Genuino Ice Co., Inc. in Metro Manila.

Throughout his ministry, Reyes has made significant contributions in church planting and campus ministry. His efforts include initiating bible study groups at Pangasinan State University & Urdaneta City University from 2014 to 2016, which continued independently from 2017 onwards. He established a mission in Maiquez Compound, San Fabian Pangasinan from 2018 to 2019, which has since been continued by Inmalog UMC. Perhaps his most notable achievement was leading Bethel UMC from its status as a Mission Congregation to becoming a fully-fledged Local Church between 2018 and 2023. During this period, he also established three preaching points in Brgy. Cabaruan & Narvacan, Sto. Tomas La Union, and initiated a mission area in Bauang La Union.

Reyes' professional qualifications include his ordination as an Elder in 2022 by the Northwest Philippines Annual Conference and his registration as a Mechanical Engineer (License no. 0079809) with the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC). He possesses a high level of computer literacy, particularly in Microsoft Office applications and hardware & software troubleshooting. His academic background has honed his skills in research and documentation, complementing his practical ministry experience. This combination of theological expertise, engineering background, and diverse skill set positions Reyes as a unique and valuable leader within his religious community and beyond.